

Crop Science Notes 2019 revised

A-level

Gwanzura.R. 0773 266 377
HOLY CROSS HIGH SCHOOL | P.O.BAG 2000

Table of Contents

TOPIC 1: CYTOLOGY AND PLANT CLASSIFICATION	1
SUB TOPIC: CLASSIFICATION AND CELL BIOLOGY.....	1
CLASSIFICATION OF PLANTS	1
Cell structure.....	9
Cell division	16
TOPIC 2: PLANT MORPHOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY	28
SUB TOPIC: PLANT GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT	28
MERISTEMS.....	28
SUB TOPIC: FLOWER AND FRUIT DEVELOPMENT	34
Flower initiation and fertilization	34
Double Fertilization	38
Fruit set and seed development	40
SUB TOPIC: SEED AND SEED DEVELOPMENT	42
Seed structure	42
Seed germination	43
SUBTOPIC: PLANT-WATER RELATIONS	45
Water properties.....	45
Water Movement.....	46
Water Potential (ψ) Concepts	46
Diffusion	48
Radial movement of water	48
Transpiration	50
SUBTOPIC BIOLOGICAL NITROGEN FIXATION	51
Biological Nitrogen Fixation	51
SUB TOPIC: RESPONSES OF PLANTS TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS.....	55
Environmental factors.....	55
TOPIC 3: SOIL FERTILITY AND PLANT NUTRITION.....	56
SUBTOPIC: SOIL COMPOSITION AND CHARACTERISTICS	56
Main constituents of soil.....	56
Soil aeration	58
Soil water	59
Physical soil properties.....	61
SUBTOPIC: PLANT NUTRITION.....	75

Essential nutrients	75
SUBTOPIC: SOIL ORGANIC MATTER.....	79
Constituents of soil organic matter	79
Decomposition of organic residues.....	80
Factors affecting soil organic matter levels.....	82
TOPIC 4: PRINCIPLES OF CROP BREEDING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY.....	84
SUB TOPIC: GENETICS.....	84
Principles of genetics	84
Structure of DNA.....	85
DNA Replication /DNA Synthesis	86
Protein synthesis	88
1. Transcription - RNA Synthesis	88
3.Post-Translational Modification.....	91
THE GENETIC DIAGRAM	93
TEST 1 BACK CROSS TECHNIQUE.....	93
MANDEL’S LAW OF SEGREGATION	93
DIHYBRID INHERITANCE	94
THE SUMMARY OF MENDEL’S 2nd LAW.....	95
TOPIC 5: PRINCIPLES OF CROP PROTECTION	99
SUB TOPIC: WEED, PEST AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT	99
Weeds	99
Pest.....	104
Diseases.....	106
TOPIC 6: CROP PRODUCTION.....	109
SUB TOPIC: AGRONOMIC PRINCIPLES.....	109
Agro- ecological zones	109
Tillage practices	113
Plant population	119
Crop rotation.....	120
SUB TOPIC: CEREAL AND LEGUME CROP PRODUCTION.....	125
Crop origins; soil and climate requirements.....	125
Crop management	126
TOPIC 7: CONSERVATION FARMING	130
SUB TOPIC: PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES.....	130
Conservation farming.....	130
FORM 6.....	133

TOPIC 1: PLANT MORPHOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY	133
SUB TOPIC: PLANT GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT	133
Plant growth regulators	133
SUB TOPIC: SEED AND SEED GERMINATION	137
Seed dormancy	137
Photosynthesis	144
Factors Affecting Photosynthesis	144
1. Light intensity	144
2. Concentration of carbon dioxide	145
OXIDATIVE PHOSPHORYLATION [ETC]	151
Photosynthetic pathways	151
Cellular respiration	153
TOPIC 3: SOIL FERTILITY AND PLANT NUTRITION.....	156
SUBTOPIC: SOIL CHARACTERISTICS.....	156
Soil chemical properties	156
SUBTOPIC: PLANT BREEDING METHODS	170
Plant Introduction	170
Plant selection	171
Hybridization	172
Genetic engineering	177
TOPIC 4: PRINCIPLES OF CROP PROTECTION	183
SUBTOPIC: WEEDS, INSECT PEST AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT	183
Safety precautions.....	183
Weed management	184
Pest management	190
Disease management.....	192
Sprayer calibration.....	194
TOPIC 5: CROP PRODUCTION.....	197
SUBTOPIC: CEREAL AND LEGUME CROP PRODUCTION	197
Crop management	197

CROP SCIENCE COURSE OUTLINE

FORM 5 & 6

	Form 5 Topics
1	Classification and cell biology

2	Plant growth and development
3	Flower and fruit development
4	Seed and seed germination
5	Plant- water relations
6	Nitrogen -Fixation
7	Responses of plants to environmental factors
8	Soil composition
9	Soil characteristics
10	Plant nutrition
11	Soil organic matter
12	Genetics
13	Agronomic principles
14	Cereal and legume production
15	Weeds
16	Pests
17	Diseases
18	Principles and practices (conservation farming)
Form 6 Topics	
1	Plant growth regulators
2	Seed dormancy
3	Bio-energetics (photosynthesis/cellular resp./photosynthetic pathways
4	Soil chemical properties
5	Plant breeding methods (introduction; selection; hybridization; genetic engineering.
6	Safety precautions
7	Weed management
8	Pest management
9	Disease management
10	Sprayer calibration
11	Crop management (cereal crop)
12	Crop management (legume crop)

TOPIC 1: CYTOLOGY AND PLANT CLASSIFICATION

SUB TOPIC: CLASSIFICATION AND CELL BIOLOGY

CLASSIFICATION OF PLANTS

- Classification according to:
 - Scientific
 - Families
 - Uses
 - Morphology
 - Life cycle
 - habitat

- This is the grouping of plants by their similar characteristics.

Importance of plant classification

1. Establish order
2. Refer to plants without need to describe them
3. Determine possible sources of genes for improvement of domesticated species
4. Determine the carrying capacity of the environment
5. Assess ecosystem development
6. Extrapolate behavior of some individuals in broad classes eg. Poisonous spp.
7. Determine spp composition.
8. It provides fairly accurate base of identifying plants and easy communication throughout the world.
9. Plant classification could provide satisfactory knowledge of propagation of plants.
10. It makes summarization of our knowledge of plants possible.
11. To construct the evolutionary history of the present flora based on a broad knowledge of their taxonomy.
12. It would be possible to find out other plants belonging to similar classes or families and therefore plant taxonomy allows for predictions.

Scientific or Botanical system of classification

- This system of classification was started by a Swedish botanist named **Carl Linnaeus**. The system was adopted in the 18th century when Latin was the written language of science.
- The advantage of this system is that there is no repetition as seen in other classification systems.
- Plants are classified within a KINGDOM. It is called the Plant Kingdom.
- Plants are further subdivided into major PHYLUM/ DIVISION. The plants are separated based on the evolutionary relationship basis.
- Example of the categories and subcategories of the Plant Kingdom is as follows;

KINGDOM
PHYLUM/ DIVISION
CLASS
ORDER
FAMILY
GENUS
SPECIES
VARIETY

How is the hierarchy formed?

- The hierarchy starts from the species (basic unit of classification).
 - After the species, closely related species are grouped into a category (taxon) called Genus and members of a genus have much in common morphologically. The number of plants in a genus lends itself well to studies of biochemical, cytological, ecological and genetic relationships.
 - Closely related genera form a Family- this grouping is frequently encountered in taxonomic studies because it is small enough to allow relatively easy study of natural relationships among its members. This is the most used category of the major taxa
 - From Family there is Order, Class, Division and up to the Kingdom.
 - Taxa from Kingdom to family are the major taxa while those below are minor taxa
- NB** Classification is a continuous process as new phylogenetic data arise.

Families of horticultural importance

Family Name	English Name	Dicot(D) or Monocot (M)
Brassicaceae	Mustard family	D
Bromeliaceae	Pineapple	M
Cactaceae	Cactus	D
Caryophyllaceae	Carnation	D
Cornaceae	Dogwood	D
Fabaceae	Pea	D
Poaceae	Grass	M
Rosaceae	Rose	D
Solanaceae	Nightshade	D
Theaceae	Tea	D

Variety

- When one or more of the populations of a species is significantly different from the remaining members it is given a varietal status. Eg purple and yellow granadillas are varieties. Cabbage, cauliflower and Brussels sprouts are varieties of the same species – they exist in nature as such.
- This is different from cultivar

Cultivar

- Short for cultivated variety
- This is a named group of plants within a cultivated species that is distinguishable by a character or group of characters and that maintain its identity when propagated either sexually or asexually.
- This does not exist in nature but maintained by cultivation thus a result of cultivation, selection and breeding and not by natural means

Classification based on life cycle (ontogeny)

-)All higher plants can be classified as;
 1. annuals,
 2. winter annuals,
 3. biennials and
 4. perennials.

Annuals

- Annuals complete their entire life cycle in a single season and then die. The growth duration is less than a year and they always reproduce by seeds.
- Examples of such plants are;

Winter annuals

- They utilize parts of the two growing seasons in completing their life cycles.
- They live through the winter, usually in dormant state and then mature and produce seed in late spring and die in summer.
- Examples of such plants are winter wheat, winter barley and oats.

Biennials

- These are crops that require two years to complete their life cycle.
- Vegetative growth occurs in the first year (note that vernalization occurs in winter) and then they flower and produce seed and die in the next year.
- Examples are sugar beet, carrot and sweet clover.

Perennials

- They have an indefinite life period ranging from a few years to many years. They do not die after reproduction.
- Some have herbaceous stems which die back to the soil surface every year in winter so that they resume growth from the crown or taproot in spring.
- Trees and shrubs are other examples of perennials which add new growth every year from woody stems. Some plants are perennials in climate and annual in another.
- Examples of such crops are castor beans, sorghum and cotton. These can grow for several years in tropical regions but tend to be killed by frost. Other perennials include sugar cane and forage crops.

Classification based on agronomic use

- **Cereal or grain crops** are crops grown for their edible seeds e.g maize, wheat, rice, oats, barley and grain sorghum.
- **Small grains** is a collective term used to include sorghum and millets in the tropics and wheat, oats, barley in the temperate. This is just a relative term.
- **Grain legumes** are legumes grown for their seed e.g ground nuts, dry beans, cowpeas, soybeans and pigeon peas.

- **Pulse crops** are large seeded legumes that are used as a source of protein for human beings or livestock e.g dry beans, ground nuts, soyabeans, lime beans.
- **Oil crops** are those crops grown primarily for their oil. They mainly used for food processing and in vegetable oils and shortenings. They are also used as lubricants and in industrial processing e.g. soyabeans, groundnuts, sunflower, castorbeans, maize, oilpalm.
- **Root crops** such as carrot, radish, sweet potatoes, cassava, yam and sugarbeet, their true roots are harvested for human food or livestock feed.
- **Tuber crops** are grown for their underground tubers. A tuber is not a true root but is a modified and thickened underground stem e.g Irish potato and the Jerusalem artichoke
- **Sugar crops** are grown for their sweet juices from which sucrose is extracted and refined e.g. syrup from sweet sorghum, sugar cane and sugar beet.
- **Fiber crops** are grown for their fibre for making textiles, ropes, twines, bags, cotton and flax for example are used for making linen from fibers contained in lint and stems respectively. Other examples are sisal, jute, kenaf and broom corn.
- **Forage crops** are those grown for their vegetative matter to feed livestock, especially ruminants e.g. pastures, hay crop, silage crop and a soiling crop.
- **Horticultural crops** are crops that require very intensive cultural practices as compared to field crops such as maize and dry beans e.g. vegetable crops, orchard crops, small fruits, ornamental plants and flowers.

Classification based on special use

- Cover crops are grown to protect the soil from soil erosion e.g star grass and rapoko.
- Catch crops, sometimes known as emergence crops are grown to fill in when the regular crop has failed or when planting has been delayed too long for regular crop to mature e.g. sunflower and dry beans in late summer.
- A companion crop is a crop grown with a main crop, normally perennial to aid it during establishment e.g. spring oats seeded with alfalfa.
- Green manure is a crop that is grown and then ploughed into the soil while it is still green and succulent to improve soil fertility.
- This is achieved by providing additional organic matter which improves soil structure or through increased nutrient availability.
- Trap crop is planted to attract certain insects and or parasites. Trap crop crops are ploughed under or destroyed once they have served their purpose e.g cotton to control striga ssp (witch weed).

Classification based on Habitat.

- A habitat is a biome or an environment in which plants live. A habitat is detected by what kinds of plants grow there, the climate and the Geography.
- **Classification based on growth habits**
 - This is classification based on growth habit or other significant physiological characteristics.
 - Nonwoody plants with comparatively soft tissues with relatively short lived aerial part are called herbaceous or succulent plants. Woody plants have long lived aerial, dense, strong aerial tissues that increase in length and diameter each year.
 - Herbaceous plants that are seed producing with self-supporting stems are herbs. Herbaceous plants with a trailing or climbing habit are vines.
 - Woody plants with self-supporting stems: trees or shrubs. Trees have single trunk and distinct elevated head while shrubs are usually low with several shoots or trunks produced at the base.
- **Classification based on foliage habits**

- Those always in leaf are called evergreens e.g Coconut, dates, banana, avocado, sweet orange, papaya, passion fruit, cashew nut and those that lose all their leaves during a portion of the year (usually winter) are deciduous. Eg guava, apple, fig, grape, mulberry, almond.
- Evergreens shed their leaves but at a gradual rate over one or more years and therefore are never without leaves
- Persistence of leaves can vary with climate as some plants that are evergreen in the tropics become deciduous in cooler regions

Classification based on Morphology.

- This is the study of various external features of a plant.
- Morphology classes depend on the modification of the root, stem and leaves.

The root

- it is an underground part of a plant and it develops from the radicle of the embryo.
- Tap root originates from the radicle ,examples are ;pea,mango,beans
- Fibrous roots originate from the base of the stem,examples are;wheat,paddy ,grasses
- Adventitious roots originate from parts of the plant,example are;maize,Rhizopra,Banyan tree.
- Roots are modified for support,storage of food and resapiation

Figure 5.3 The regions of the root-tip

- **For support**
 - This is seen in prop roots in Banyan, still roots in maize and suger cane
- **For respiration**
 - Pneumatophores in *Rhizopora* (Mangrove)
- **For storage of food**
 - Fusiform-radish
 - Napiform-turnip
 - Conical-carrot

Stem

- The stem is the aerial part of the plant and it develops from the plumule of the embryo. It bears nodes and internodes.
- **Modifications of the stem**
 - The stems may be modified to perform the function of storage of food, support, protection and vegetative propagation.
 - **Food storage;** Rhizomes (ginger), Tuber (potato), Bulbs (onion) and Corms (Colocasia)
 - **For support;** stem tendrils of lemon, grape vine and cucumber.
 - **For protection;** auxiliary buds of citrus stems, *Bougainvillea* get modified into thorns. They protect the plant from animals.
 - **For vegetative propagation;** underground stems of grass, strawberry and lateral branches of mint and jasmine perform as reproductive structure.
 - **For assimilation of food;** flattened stems of *Opuntia* contain chlorophyll and perform photosynthesis.
 - Stems may also be classified according to two groups; woody and Non-woody
 - **Woody plants** are those with stems that are hard and usually brown.
 - Big trees, like acacia and molave, are woody. The wood from these trees is often used to build houses. Other woody plants include *ipil-ipil* and *dama de noche*.
 - Woody plants can be divided into three groups: trees, shrubs and vines.
 - **Vines**
 - These are climbing or creeping woody plants. Vines have stems called twiners that entwine themselves or coil around solid support. Also, they have climbing organs called tendrils. Other examples of vines are grapes, poison ivy and morning glory.

Shrubs

- They have stems that grow upright. However, they do not grow very tall.
- Examples of shrubs are *sampaguita* and rose.
- Some shrubs have thorns to protect them. They need protection from hostile animals because they grow low or near the ground. This is to prevent animals from eating or destroying them.

Trees

- are woody plants that often grow big.
- They often have one very hard and wide stem, called the trunk. Many trees are found in the forests and mountains.

Non-woody plants

- They have stems that are soft, smooth and usually green.
- These plants are sometimes called herbaceous. Green, leafy vegetables, like *alugbati*, *kinchay* and *saluyot*, are non-woody.

The leaf

- It develops from shoot apical meristems, it is a flattened green structure that manufactures food by photosynthesis. It has a bud in axil
- A typical leaf has a leaf base, petiole and lamina

- A leaf may be simple or compound. A simple leaf has a single leaf blade but a compound leaf has several leaflets.
- Compound leaves are further divided into pinnately compound (Neem,Rose) and palmately compound (silk cotton)

Venation

- This is the arrangement of veins and veinlets in the lamina of a leaf
- **Types of venation;**

1. Reticulate;veins form a network as in leaves of dicotyledons

2. Parallel;veins are parallel to each other as in leaves of monocotyledons (grass,maize,sugar cane)

Phyllotaxy

- This is the pattern of arrangement of leaves on a stem or branch.
- Types of phyllotaxy include; Alternate, Opposite and Whorled.
- Alternate have a single leaf at a node
- Opposite have two leaves at a node
- Whorled has more than two leaves in a whorl at a node

Explain how farmers can use the knowledge of botanical characteristic of soyabeans of groundnuts in managing the crop. [8]

LEAVES

- broad; considered in applying fertilizer

ROOTS

- tap root system, deep, exhaust profile water. Less watering frequency

NODULATION-

- considered in water application, fertilizer application
- water stress or water logging suppress nodulation
- apply required fertilizers or lime to encourage nodulation
- high Nitrogen suppress nodulation. Diseases management.

Activity

1. Define classification. [2]
2. classify plants according to scientific nomenclature: [5]
 - a. families, [5]
 - b. uses, [5]
 - c. morphology, [5]
 - d. life cycle and [5]
 - e. habitat [5]
3. Outline the importance of classifying plants. [5]
4. Name the two components of the scientific name of every organism [2]
5. state the meaning of the following terms:
 - I. taxonomy, [2]
 - II. species,, [2]

Cell structure

- draw a plant cell
- label parts of a plant cell
- explain functions of cell parts
- identify cell organelles
- outline functions of cell organelles
- explain the relationship between organelles.

Ultra-structure of a typical Plant cell

-
- Plant cells tend to be uniform in their shape because the cell is bound by a rigid cell wall.
 - The cells give strength and support to plants due to insoluble cellulose fibres which are meshed in a matrix of carbohydrates called pectates or hemicelluloses.
 - Plant Cells have have the following:

Vacuole

- Is a fluid filled space in the cytoplasm.
- In plants a vacuole is a permanent feature.
- It is surrounded by a membrane called tonoplast.
- Is filled with cell sap.
- The vacuole determines the osmotic properties of a plant cell.

Nucleus

- It is the largest organelle in a (plant; animal) cell
- Spherical structure 10-20 micrometers in diameter
- Surrounded by a double membrane called nuclear envelope
- Contains nucleoplasm
- Nuclear envelope compartmentalises chemical reactions taking place in the nucleus
- Nucleoplasm contains chromosomes and nucleoli
- Chromosomes contain DNA attached to proteins (histones)
- Nucleoplasm also contains RNA (3 types of RNA)
- Nucleus functions to control the synthesis of proteins
- Controls the cell's activities
- Divide at the start of cell division ,
- ensuring that daughter cells have exact copies of the cell's genetic material
- To assemble ribosomes

Endoplasmic reticulum

- It is a system of flattened membrane bound sacs called cisternae, forming tubes and sheets.
- It is continuous with the outer membrane of the nuclear envelope.

a) Rough endoplasmic reticulum

- Have ribosomes on them.
- Their role is to manufacture proteins.
- Rough endoplasmic reticulum is abundant in cell that either secrete proteins or that are growing rapidly.

b) Smooth endoplasmic reticulum

- Lacks ribosomes on its surface.
- Abundant in cells that secrete steroids or lipid substances
- These are the site for lipid and steroid synthesis.

Functions of endoplasmic reticulum

- To provide area for biochemical reactions.
- To act as a pathway for the transport and exchange of material.
- To manufacture proteins e.g. enzymes
- To manufacture lipids and steroids.
- To collect and store any synthesized material.
- To form a structural skeleton for maintaining cellular shape

Ribosomes

- Very small organelles consisting of a large subunit and a small subunit.
- They are made of roughly equal amounts of protein and RNA.
- There are two types i.e. 70s and 80s ribosomes.
- They are responsible for protein synthesis.
- They are either bound to ER or lie free in the cytoplasm.
- They form polysomes i.e. collection of ribosomes strung along messenger RNA

Mitochondria

- 0.5–1.0 μm , diameter / width ;
- double membrane ;
- inner membrane folded / cristae ;
- hold, stalked particles / ATP synthase / ATP synthetase ;
- site of ETC ;
- ref. H^+ and intermembrane space ;
- ATP production ;
- oxidative phosphorylation / chemiosmosis ;
- matrix is site of, link reaction / Krebs cycle ;
- enzymes in matrix ;
- 70S ribosomes ;
- (mitochondrial) DNA ;
- They are envelope bound and the inner membrane folds to form cristae.
- It consists of a matrix with few ribosomes, a circular DNA molecule and phosphate granules.
- In aerobic respiration, cristae are the sites for oxidative phosphorylation and electron transport chain.
- Matrix is the site for Krebs's cycle of enzymes.

Golgi apparatus

- Composed of a series of parallel membranes that are flattened fluid spaces .
- The cristae are slightly curved the entire structure appear concave.
- Functions of Golgi apparatus:
 - Manufacture of glycoproteins which are required for secretions.
 - Production of secretory enzymes.

- Production of carbohydrates e.g. those involved in the manufacture of new cell walls.
- Transport and storage of lipids.
- Formation of lysosomes.

Chloroplast

- Are large organelles containing their own DNA and have a double membrane.
 - Chloroplasts have a folded inner membrane which gives a greater surface area for biochemical reactions to occur.
- Thylakoid membranes contain pigments/ electron carriers/ enzymes
- Used in cyclic and non – cyclic photophosphorylation/ light dependent reactions
- Stroma (contain enzymes) for the calvin cycle/ dark reaction
- Grana a network of proteins holding pigments into photosynthesis
- Light reactions on thylakoid which contain ATP/ stalked particles
- Membrane system separates the reactions of photosynthesis from other cell reactions
- Stroma fluid which surrounds grana so that products light dependent stage can easily pass into stroma.
- Contain DNA /ribosomes for manufacture of proteins needed for protein synthesis
- Grana are interconnected by membranes called lamella.

Longitudinal section through a chloroplast

(List any 3 structural similarities between a mitochondrion and a chloroplast. [3])

- Circular DNA
- Double membranes
- 70s ribosomes

Membranes

- Cell membranes separate their contents from their external environment controlling the exchange of materials between the two.
- Membranes also act as receptor sites for hormones and neurotransmitters and other chemicals.

- Membranes are described as **selectively permeable**, since other substances such as glucose, amino acids, fatty acids, glycerol and ions can diffuse through slowly.
- Membranes are made almost entirely of proteins and lipids.

The fluid mosaic model of membrane structure

Phospholipids

- Each phospholipid molecule consists of a polar head containing a phosphate and two fatty acids.
- The polar head is hydrophilic and the tails are hydrophobic.
- In aqueous environments, the hydrophilic heads face the external environments and the hydrophobic fatty acid tails come into close contact to exclude water.

Proteins

- Freeze fracturing reveals the presence of proteins which penetrate into and often through the phospholipid bilayer.
- The more metabolically active the membrane is, the more the protein cuticles are found.

Glycolipids and cholesterol

- Glycolipids are lipids with carbohydrate residues, like phospholipids they have polar heads and non-polar tails.
- Cholesterol acts as a plug reducing even further exit and entry of molecules through the membrane.

Fluid mosaic model membrane

(why is it called the fluid mosaic model membrane? [2marks])

- This was so called because of the protein molecules which float about hap-hazard in the phospholipid bilayer
- The membrane is 7nm thick.
- Its basic structure is the phospholipid bilayer.
- The phospholipids are fluid and move about rapidly by diffusion in their own layers.
- Unsaturated fatty acids are bent.
- Most protein molecules float about in the phospholipid bilayer forming a fluid mosaic pattern.
- The proteins stay in the membranes because they have regions of hydrophobic amino acids which interact with fatty acid tails to exclude water.
- The two sides of the membrane can differ in composition and function

(Explain how the phospholipid bilayer prevents the flow of protons)

- *The phospholipid bilayer is non-polar whilst the hydrogen ions are polar because of the charge they possesses so the polar substance cannot easily pass through the non-polar unless there is a hydrophilic channel.*
- *The cytoplasm is negatively charged whilst the hydrogen ions are positively charged such that they attract each other, so the phospholipid bilayer prevents the flow because the hydrogen ions will cause a change in electrochemical gradient of the cytoplasm.*

Channel proteins and carrier proteins

- These are involved in the selective transport of polar molecules and ions across the membranes.
- Qn. Outline the process of cell signaling? [4marks]
- Qn. Outline the route by which proteins are exported from a cell. [3marks]

Activity

6. Draw and label the structure of a plant cell as seen under an electron microscope. [8]
7. Describe the structure of a cell membrane. [5]
8. Draw and label the structure of a chloroplast. [5]
9. Explain the function of the following organelles of a plant cell:
 - a rough and smooth Endoplasmic reticulum, [3]
 - b Golgi body, [3]
 - c ribosomes, [3]
 - d lysosomes, [3]
 - e chloroplast, [3]
 - f cell membrane, [5]
 - g nuclear envelope, [2]
10. Describe the composition, structure and role of cell membranes. [5]
11. Discuss the structure and function of the various types of plastids. [5]
12. Discuss the origin of plastids from an ontogenetic (cytoplasmic inheritance) and from a phylogenetic perspective (endosymbiont hypothesis). [6]
13. Discuss the structure and roles (function) of the large central vacuole found in plant cells. Explain why animal cells lack these structures. [6]

14. Discuss the morphology (structure), chemical composition and role of the plant cell wall. [5]
15. Outline the similarities between chloroplast and mitochondria. [5]
16. Describe the structure of mitochondria with the aid of a diagram [5]
20. Draw and label the structure of chloroplast. [5]
21. State four functions that the plasma membrane provides. [2]
22. Name **the 4 main components** of the plasma membrane and state one function of each. [2]

Cell division

- Describe the process of mitosis
- Explain the significance of mitosis in crop production
- Describe the process of meiosis
- Explain the significance of meiosis and mitosis

Meiosis

- Is the process by which a cell nuclear divide to form four daughter cells containing half the number of chromosomes of the original cell .
- It is also called reduction division since it reduces the number of chromosomes in the cell from the diploid $2n$ to hypoid n .
- Meiosis occurs during gametogenesis in animals and during spore formation in plants .

PHASE	EVENTS WITHIN THE CELL
GROWTH PHASE	Intensive cellular synthesis mitochondrion, chloroplast divide .energy
G1/G2	store increases mitotic spindle begins to form.
M	Nuclear division occurs in four phases.
C	Equal distribution of organelles and cytoplasm into each daughter cells.

THE CELL CYCLE

- The sequence of events which occur between one cell division and next is called cell cycle. It has three main stages.

INTERPHASE	MITOSIS	CELL DIVISION
This is a period of synthesis and growth. The cell produces the material required for its own growth ,DNA replication also occurs .	The actual process of nuclear division.	This is the process of division of the cytoplasm into the daughter cells.

PHASE	EVENTS IN THE CELL
G 1	Intensive cellular synthesis including new organelle cell growth occurs.
S	DNA replication occurs. Protein molecules [histones] produced .

At this stage the cell is 4n.

MITOSIS

- Has 5 stages / phases

1. INTERPHASE

- Variable according to the function of the cell. .
- DNA replicates
- Each chromosome exists as a pair of chromatids joined at the centromere .
- The cell now has 4n.
- Chromosomes now visible as loosely coiled threads called chromatin.
- Centrioles replicate

2. PROPHASE

- Formation of spindle.
- It is the longest phase .
- Chromosomes shorten and thicken by coiling.

- Chromosomes now available as a double structure .
- In animal cells centrioles move to opposite poles .
- A star from short microtubules radiating from centrioles.
- The spindle is formed .
- Chromatids form chromosomes .
- Nuclear envelope disappear .

3. METAPHASE

- Chromosomes line up at the equator of the spindle attached by the centromeres to the spindle .
- Chromosomes move to metaphase plate.

4. ANAPHASE

- A very rapid stage.
- The centromeres split into two and the spindle pull the daughter chromosomes to opposite poles.
- The separated are pulled behind the centromeres.
- The shortening of the spindle fiber by the removal of the subunits account to moving of chromatids during anaphase.

Anaphase

- The links between sister chromatids break
- The centromeres of sister chromatids move apart, pulled by the spindle fibres

TELOPHASE

- The chromatids reach the opposite poles.
- They uncoil and lengthen to form chromatin again.
- The spindle fibers disintegrate and centrioles replicate.
- Nuclear envelope reforms.

Telophase

- Sister chromatids (now effectively separate chromosomes) reach opposite poles
- The chromosomes decondense
- Nuclear envelopes begin to form around the chromosomes at each pole
- The spindle disappears

CYTOKINESIS

- Is the actual division of the cytoplasm to form two daughter cells.
- The cell becomes evenly distributed towards the two poles.
- In animal cells the cell surface membrane invaginates around the equator forming a furrow which eventually meet up and completely separate the cells.
- In plant cells, spindle fibers remain around the equatorial plane and increase in number to form a barrel-shaped region called the phragmoplast. Cell organelles line at the equator
- Forming a cell plate. the cell plate spreads across the equator meeting the cell wall, thereby separating the two daughter cells.
- The new cell wall is called a **primary cell wall**, it later develops to a **secondary cell wall** by the deposition of cellulose and lignin.

Mitosis and cytokinesis in an animal cell

SIGNIFICANCE OF MITOSIS

1. GENETIC STABILITY

- Mitosis produces two cells with the same chromosomal number as the mother cell .No variation is introduced during mitosis.

2. GROWTH

- The number of cells in organism increase with mitosis .This is the basic of growth in a multicellular organism.

3. CELL REPLACEMENT

- Replacement of cell tissue involve mitosis.

4. REGENERATION

- Some animals are also regenerated some parts of their body by mitosis.

5. ASEXUAL REPRODUCTION

- Mitosis is the basic of asexual reproduction of new individuals of a spice by one parent organism.

MEIOSIS [REPRODUCTION DIVISION]

- Like mitosis involves DNA replication during interphase in the parent cell but this is followed by two cycles of nuclear division which are meiosis one and meiosis two.
- Meiosis occurs during gametogenesis and spore formation in plants.

Meiosis I

PROPHASE 1

- Longest phase.
- **Crossing over** may occurs.
- Chromosomes shorten and become visible as a single structure.
- Homologous pair up in a process called synapses.
- Each pair is called a bivalent.
- One of the homologues pair comes from the father paternal and the other from the mother maternal.

- The bivalents shorten and thicken by coiling.
- The homologous chromosomes partially separate some for a fill points along the length .These points are called chiasmata.
- Genes from one chromosome may swap with genes from the other chromosome leading to new gene combinations in the resulting chromatids.

METAPHASE I

- The bivalents become arranged around the equator attached to their centromeres .

ANAPHASE I

- Spindle fibres pull homologues chromosomes apart centromeres face opposite poles of the spindle.
- This separates the chromosomes into two haploid one set at each of the opposite spindle.

TELOPHASE I

- Chromatides usually uncoil and nuclear envelope reforms.
- Cytokinesis now occurs as in mitosis.
- In many plants there is no telophase I.
- Cell formation and interphase II and then the cell passes from anaphase II to prophase II.
- Reduction of chromosomes has occurred but sister chromatids are genetically different.

INTREPHASE II

- Present only in animal cells and varies in length.
- No synthesis occurs and no further and replication occurs.
- The second meiotic division is similar to mitosis.

PROPHASE II

- Only present if interphase two is present.
- The nucleoli and the nuclear envelope disappears, the chromatids, shorten and thicken.
- Centrioles if present move to opposite poles and the spindle axis of the first meiotic division.

METAPHASE II

- Chromosomes arrange them self at the centre of the equator and centromeres appear as double structure. The orientation or assortment of chromosomes is at the equator is random.
- Independent assortment occurs at metaphase II.

ANAPHASE II

- The centromeres divide and the spindle pulls to opposite poles and to double centromeres
- The separated chromatids now called chromosomes are pulled along the centromeres.

TELOPHASE II

- The stage is similar to that found at mitosis. The chromosomes uncoil, lengthen and become very indistinct. The spindle fiber disappears and the centrioles replicate.
- Nuclear envelope reforms around the nucleus. Cell wall forms in plants and four daughter cells are produced.

SIGNIFICANTS OF MEIOSIS

1. SEXUAL REPRODUCTION

- All organisms reproduce sexually use meiosis. Garment production involves meiosis.
- The number **2n** is restored during fertilization.

2. GENETIC VARIATION

- Meiosis provides a platform for new gene combinations of genes. This results in genetic variation in offspring when garments fuse.

a) Independent assortment

- The orientation of bivalents at the equator of the spindle in metaphase one is random. The bivalents separate independently of those in other bivalents during anaphase.

b) CROSSING OVER

- Is the result when chiasmata cross over of segments of chromatids occurs between homologues during prophase 1

Fig. 2.5 Crossing-over and recombination during the formation of gametes (germ cells) or meiosis

(Outline the difference between mitosis and meiosis. [8])

Similarities between the prophase stage of mitosis and prophase I

- Chromosomes shorten and thicken;
- Spindle fibres form;
- Nucleoli disappears.

STAGE	MITOSIS	MEIOSIS
PROPHASE	Homologues chromosomes remain separated	Homologues chromosomes Pair up in a process called synapsis.
	Crossing over occurs	No crossing over
	No Formation of chiasmata	Formation of chiasmata
METAPHASE	Pairs of chormatids line up on spindle equator	Pairs of chromosomes line up on spindle equator
ANAPHASE	Centriomeres divide	Centromeres don't divide
	Chromatids separate	Chromosomes separate
	Chromatids identical	Chromatids may not be identical

TELOPHASE	Cell contain the same number of chromosomes as the mother cell	Cells contain half the number of the chromosomes .
	May occur in haploid and diploid or polyploidy cells	Only occurs in diploid cells
	2 daughter cells identical	4 daughter cells
	Genetically identical to parents	Genetically different from parents

TOPIC 2: PLANT MORPHOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY

SUB TOPIC: PLANT GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT

MERISTEMS

- Describe the types of plant meristems.

Definition

- 1) A formative plant tissue usually made up of small cells capable of dividing indefinitely and giving rise to similar cells or to cells that differentiate to produce the definitive tissues and organs
- 2) Region of cells capable of division and growth in plants.
- 3) Meristematic tissues, or simply **meristems**, are tissues in which the cells remain forever young and divide actively throughout the life of the plant

MERISTEMS DESCRIPTION

- When a meristematic cell divides in two, the new cell that remains in the meristem is called an **initial**, the other the **derivative**.
- As new cells are added by repeated **mitotic divisions** of the initial cells, the derivatives are pushed farther away from the zone of active division.
- They stretch, enlarge and *differentiate* into other types of tissues as they mature which is the growth and development of a cell.
- Meristematic cells are generally small and cuboidal with large nuclei, small vacuoles, and thin walls, small the diameters of which in different directions are about equal.
- They have a dense [cytoplasm](#) and relatively few small vacuoles (watery saclike enclosures).
- Meristems are classified by their location in the [plant](#) as
- Meristems form anew from other cells in injured tissues and are responsible for wound healing.

Types of Meristematic tissue on the basis of position:

i. Apical meristem

ii. Intercalary meristem

iii. Lateral meristem

Apical Meristem:

- Position: present at apical parts of plant such as root tip and shoot tip
- It helps in increase in height of plants.
- Apical meristem has two distinct zone:
- Promeristem zone: contains group of dividing cell (apical initials)
- Meristematic zone: contains protoderms (epiderm), procambium (primary vascular tissue) and ground meristem (cortex and pith).
- Apical Meristems - Found at the tips of roots and shoots. Plants get taller, and roots get longer, from their tips.
- Increase in length as the apical meristems produce new cells (primary growth) Divide to produce new cells, which elongate, making roots get longer and shoots get taller.
 - Primary Meristems
 - Protoderm
 - Ground Meristem
 - Procambium

- Once cells elongate and differentiate into a particular cell type, they usually can't divide any more due to their rigid cell walls.
- Meristematic cells, however, continue to divide, enabling growth throughout the life of the plant.
- Indeterminate growth- keeps growing throughout life Determinate growth- stops growing when reaches maturity

Intercalary Meristem:

1. Position: present in intercalary position in the leaves and internode
2. It is a part of apical meristem
3. It also adds to height of plants
4. Commonly present in monocots, grass and pines
5. produced as stems elongate in the angle between the stem and the petiole of each leaf May remain dormant until apical meristem has grown and moved away from the axillary bud.
6. When apical meristem is far enough away, the meristems of the axillary bud begins to grow forming a branch.
7. Branches can be forced to grow by removing the apical meristem which wakes up the axillary meristem of the main shoot.

- Grasses and related plants do not have vascular cambium or cork cambium, but do have apical meristems in the vicinity of the nodes.
- **Intercalary meristems** - Develop at intervals along stems where they add to stem length- cells get added to the middle to increase length. This is why you can mow grass and the grass will continue to get longer.

Lateral Meristem:

- Position: present on lateral side of stem and root
- It helps in increases the diameter or thickness of plants.
- Example: vascular cambium (primary meristem) and cork cambium (secondary meristem)
- Lateral meristems are thin cylinders of tissue that form in mature regions of shoots and roots of many plants, especially those that produce woody tissue.
- They divide to produce secondary growth, growth that increases the diameter [girth] of a shoot [stem or trunk] or root. Plants have two types of lateral meristems.
- Vascular Cambium – Produces new vascular tissues that function primarily in support and conduction.
- Thin cylindrical cells.
- Cork Cambium - Lies outside vascular cambium just inside the outer bark of woody plants.

Plant growth

- Discuss plant growth and development;
- Describe the phases of growth of plant cell growth

- **Growth** can be defined as an irreversible increase in dry mass of a plant.
- “**Development** can be defined as an ordered change or progress, often towards a higher, more ordered or more complex state”

Primary growth and development

Primary growth

- Increase in length and occurs in regions of cell elongation just behind the meristematic regions of dividing cells. Primary growth is a direct result of mitosis.
- The cells produced then differentiate into the tissues of the primary plant body.
- The primary shoot system is composed of the following:
 - 1) The apical meristem of the plant: Mitosis occurs
 - 2) Tissue differentiation in the stem: This produces the cortex, vascular bundles and pith tissues of the primary stem
 - 3) Development of leaves and lateral shoots

The primary root system

This is composed of the following:

- 1) The apical meristem of the root

2) Tissue differentiation in the root

Secondary growth and development

- Instead of growth in length, secondary growth is radial; increasing the diameter of a stem or root as dividing cells produce lateral or sideways growth.
- Whereas some plants do not develop further than the primary stage, others can add secondary tissues to the primary plant body.
- The secondary plant body is derived from lateral meristems, the most important of which are the vascular cambium and cork cambium.
- As the name suggests, the vascular cambium produces vascular tissues, which are called secondary xylem and secondary phloem to distinguish them from the primary xylem and primary phloem formed by the procambium.
- Development may take place with growth and growth may take place with development. Generally growth involves processes such as cell division, cell expansion, differentiation and morphogenesis.
- The most obvious manifestation of growth is increase in height and dry weight.
- Growth can also be expressed as the advance of a plant from one stage of development to another. E.g. from seed germination to maturity.
- Development is characterised by morphological and chemical differentiation.
- Over the past years, a great deal of effort has been made in attempt to unravel the physiological basis of plant growth. It is now apparent that growth and development of plants are the consequences of subtle interactions between many external and internal factors.
- In flowering plants growth and development begin when a seed germinates.

Phases of growth

Briefly describe plant growth under the following phases:

(i) *Meristematic*

- Growth as a result of cell division /mitotic;
- In cells of an apical meristem ;
- Found at tip of each shoot or root;
- Others differentiate to form other type of tissues;

(ii) *Cell elongation*

- Transitional stage on march of cells toward differentiation;
- Development of secondary cell wall;
- Change in shape;
- Vacuolation;
- Need to maintain turgidity;
- Increase in volume of cell cytoplasm and organelles;

(iii) *Differentiation*

- it is genetically controlled;
- cells may increase number of organelles of lose them;
- e.g palisade cells increase number of chloroplasts to photosynthesis; while xylem cells (sieve tube elements) lose cell contents (nucleus; organelles) to become hollow so as to transport water.

SUB TOPIC: FLOWER AND FRUIT DEVELOPMENT

Flower initiation and fertilization

- describe gamete formation in plants.
- Describe pollination mechanisms in plants
- Explain the concept of double fertilization in plants.

POLLEN DEVELOPMENT

- The anthers comprise pollen sacs(usually four) which contain a mass of diploid pollen mother cells. Each pollen mother cell undergoes meiosis to form a tetrad of four haploid cells.
- The cells round off and are called microspores.
- The nucleus divides by mitosis to give tube nucleus and generative nucleus.
- The wall thickens and forms an inner layer, intine and an often highly sculptured outer layer,the exine.
- When transferred to the stigma of a plant of the same species,the pollen grain germinates to produce a pollen tube.
- The tube nucleus moves down the tube first, followed by generative nucleus which soon divides mitotically to give two male nuclei.

Pollen formation; Development of a pollen grain within the pollen sac of an Anther

OVULE DEVELOPMENT

- The ovule consists of a mass of cells called the nucellus which is carried on a short stalk called funicle. The nucellus is completely surrounded by two protective integuments except the narrow channel at the tip called micropyle. One cell of the nucellus becomes larger and more conspicuous than the rest. This is called embryo sac mother cell.
- The embryo sac mother cell divides meiotically to give four haploid megaspore cells.
- The three cells nearest the micropyle degenerate while the remaining one enlarges to form the embryo sac.
- The embryo sac nucleus divides by mitosis and the resultant nuclei migrate to the opposite poles.
- Each nucleus undergoes two mitotic divisions to give a group of four haploid nuclei at each pole.
- One nucleus from each polar group moves to the centre of the embryo sac. These are the polar nuclei. The remaining nuclei develop cytoplasm around them and become separated by cell walls, leaving two groups of three cells at each pole.
- The three cells at the opposite end to the micropyle are called antipodal cells and play no further role in the process. Of the three cells at the micropyle end, one, the egg remains, the other two, the synergids, degenerate.

Pollination

- Pollination refers to the process of transferring pollen grains from an anther to a stigma. If an ovule is to develop into a seed, the female gametic nucleus must first be **fertilised** by a male gametic nucleus (*these we have discussed their formation in the previous sections*). But before fertilisation can occur, however, pollen grains from a mature anther must be transferred to a receptive stigma.
- If this process of pollination does not take place the ovules die and the flower fails to set seed. Let us note that the transfer of pollen occurs in two forms:

- 1) Self-pollination and
- 2) Cross-pollination

Self-pollination

- We will go through the process of self-pollination and note the importance of pollinating agents in pollination. Transfer of pollen from an anther to a stigma of the **same flower**, or the stigma of another flower on the **same plant**, is called **self-pollination**. Self-pollination occurs in many plants, e.g. wheat, barley, oats, rice, soybeans, cotton, tomato. Below are some the advantages of self-pollination.
 - Self-pollination greater reliability, particularly when members of the species are uncommon and are separated by large distances.
 - It is not dependent on an external factor, such as wind or insects, to deliver the pollen.
 - It is also useful in harsh climates where insects are less common, such as high up on mountains.

Features favouring self-pollination

For plants to be efficient in self-pollination they must be adapted in some way. Let us look at some adaptations by plants that favour self-pollination:-

- In cereals like wheat, barley and oats, the anthers shed their pollen on to the surface of the ripe stigmas before the flower opens.
- Other plants have flowers which never open. These closed or **cleistogamous** flowers, which are produced at or below the surface of the soil, are small and budlike and can form seeds from their own pollen. This type of flowers is found in groundnut.

Cross-pollination

- In the previous section we discussed self-pollination; now let us go through cross-pollination. You will need to note similarities and be able to make comparison between the two types of pollination. Cross-pollination is the transfer of pollen from the anther of one plant to the stigma of another plant of the same species. Cross pollination is more common than self-pollination; it leads to cross-fertilisation.
- Let us now briefly look at some of the disadvantages and advantages of cross-pollination
 - It increases the amount of genetic variation, resulting in a greater adaptability of plants to new environments.
 - It is a form of 'out-breeding'. However, it is also more wasteful of pollen than self-pollination.

Features favouring cross-pollination

- Again as earlier highlighted, plants must adapt well for cross-pollination. Let us go through some adaptations of plants to cross-pollination.

a) Separation of the sexes in space.

- This is separation of male and female flowers with respect to position on the plant. Some flowers have either stamens or carpels and are unisexual.
- In dioecious plant species, such as papaw (*Carica papaya*), where an individual plant is either male or female; cross-pollination is the only possible method.
- In monoecious plants, such as pumpkin, castor oil plant and maize, where separate male and female flowers occur on the same plant, the separation of the sexes into different flowers favours but does not ensure cross-pollination.

b) Separation of the sexes in time.

- In this case male and female parts mature at different stages hence the male gametes cannot fertilise the female gamete on the same plant. Examples are avocado and carrot.
- This separation in time of maturity is known as **dichogamy**, of which there are two kinds:

1) **Protandry**, where the stamens ripen first and

2) **Protogyny** where the stigmas ripen first.

c) Self-incompatibility or self-sterility

- In other plants with perfect flowers (e.g. almonds, passion flower, red clover), fertilization does not occur when the stigma is pollinated by pollen of the same flower or by another flower of the same plant.
- In all such cases there is a specific inhibition of pollen penetration of the stigma, or of pollen tube growth down the style, and this is genetically determined.

Double Fertilization

- At the time of pollination, the pollen grain typically consists of only the tube cell and the generative cell.
- After a pollen grain lands on a suitable stigma, it absorbs water and germinates by producing a pollen tube, which grows between the cells of the style toward the ovary.
- The nucleus of the generative cell divides by mitosis and forms two sperm.
- In response to chemical attractants produced by the synergids, the tip of the pollen tube grows toward the micropyle.
- Its arrival initiates the death of one of the two synergids, thereby providing a passageway into the embryo sac for the two sperm that are discharged from the pollen tube.
- Upon reaching the female gametophyte, one sperm fertilizes the egg, forming the zygote.
- The other sperm combines with the two polar nuclei, forming a triploid ($3n$) nucleus in the center of the large central cell of the female gametophyte.
- This large cell will give rise to the endosperm, a food-storing tissue of the seed.
- The union of two sperm cells with different nuclei of the female gametophyte is called double fertilization.
- Double fertilization ensures that endosperm develops only in ovules where the egg has been fertilized, thereby preventing angiosperms from squandering nutrients on infertile ovules.

Significance of Double fertilization

- It restores the diploid condition by fusion of haploid male and female gametes
- It results in the formation of triploid primary endosperm nucleus which develops into endosperm in the seed to produce nourishment to developing embryo
- It results in the formation of diploid zygote which develops into an embryo and gives rise to a new plant
- It gives stimulus to a plant due to which ovary develops into fruit and ovules into seeds
- It brings about recombination of characteristics resulting in variation among the off springs

Describe the structural changes which occur after fertilization leading to fruit development

- fruit develops from ovary
- pollination triggers hormonal changes
- ovary starts to grow
- wall of ovary becomes the pericarp
- ovule becomes seed

state the reason why a unripe fruit has a sour taste

- has high concentration of acids

Fruit set and seed development

- Describe the structural changes that occur after fertilization in plants;
- Differentiate endospermous and non- endospermous seed development;

Events following fertilisation

- Embryo development begins.
- The zygote divides to form 2 cells, the terminal (upper) cell and the lower (basal) cell.
- The terminal cell divides to form a globular shaped pro-embryo.
- In dicots, the developing embryo is heart shaped
- As the embryo and cotyledons enlarge, they become crowded inside the developing seed and are forced to bend.
- At this point the seed is ready for dispersal.

NON ENDOSPERMOUS SEED DEVELOPMENT

- (A) In the first stage of development, the terminal cell divides, forming a globular pro-embryo. The basal cell also divides, giving rise to the presence of the suspensor.
- (B) In the second stage, the developing embryo has a heart shape due to the presence of cotyledons.
- (C) In the third stage, the growing embryo runs out of room and starts to bend.
- (D) The cotyledons eventually fill the seed.

Double fertilization gives rise to the zygote and endosperm

- Directed by a chemical attractant, possibly calcium, the tip of the pollen tube enters the ovary, probes through the micropyle (a gap in the integuments of the ovule) and discharges two sperms within the embryo sac.
- Both sperm fuse with nuclei in the embryo sac. One sperm fertilizes the egg to form a zygote.
 - The other sperm combines with the two polar nuclei to form a triploid nucleus in the central cell.
- This large cell will give rise to the **endosperm**, a food-storing tissue of the seed.
- The union of two sperm cells with different nuclei of the embryo sac is termed **double fertilization**.
- Double fertilization is also present in a few gymnosperms, probably via independent evolution. □ Double fertilization ensures that the endosperm will develop only in ovules where the egg has □ been fertilized.

(i) describe the structural changes that occur after fertilisation leading to the development of the seed and the Fruit.

- After fertilisation, the zygote divides rapidly by mitosis and develops into the embryo, which then differentiates into a young shoot called plumule, a young root called radical and seed leaves called cotyledons.
- The primary endosperm nucleus also divides mitotically to give a mass of cells, the endosperm. This forms the food source for the growing embryo.
- In legumes like beans or peas, it is quickly absorbed by and stored in cotyledons.
- The most common food stored is carbohydrates. This is usually in the form of starch but some seeds store quantities of sugar. After fertilization, the following changes are observed in a flower:
 - ✓ There is formation of a diploid zygote and it develops into an embryo, which forms the future plant.
 - ✓ The endosperm cells serve as a source of nutrition for the developing embryo.
 - ✓ The ovule becomes the seed.
 - ✓ The ovary becomes the fruit.
 - ✓ In most of the plants the antipodals and synergids disintegrate before, during or immediately after fertilization.
 - ✓ The outer and inner integuments of the ovule become the testa or the seed coat of the seed.
 - ✓ Petals and sepals fall off.

SUB TOPIC: SEED AND SEED DEVELOPMENT

Seed structure

- A seed is an embryo plant with its food store.
- The three main parts of a seed are the **embryo**, the **endosperm**, and the **seed coat**.
- The embryo consists of the immature shoot, the **plumule** and the undeveloped root, the **radicle**.
- In monocots e.g. maize, the embryo is attached to a single seed leaf called the **cotyledon**.
- **Seed composition:** starch, protein, lipids, minerals, vitamins

Seed germination

- Discuss requirements for seed germination
- Describe the processes of seed germination
- Distinguish epigeal and hypogeal germination

The requirements of seed germination

1. Water;
2. Temperature;
3. Oxygen.

The process of seed germination

The activation of the metabolic machinery of the embryo leading to the emergence of a new seedling plant is known as germination. Germination usually starts after a period of dormancy. For germination to be initiated, 3 conditions must be fulfilled:

- The seed must be viable, so the embryo must be alive and capable for germination.
- The seed must be subjected to the appropriate environmental conditions like available water, proper temperature, a supply of oxygen and sometimes light.
- Any primary dormancy condition present within the seed must be overcome.

The first stage in germination is **the absorption of water** by colloidal substances within the seed (**imbibition**). Imbibition takes place through the micropyle. After water is absorbed, various **enzyme systems are re-activated**. These enzymes convert complex food storage molecules into simpler chemicals that can be translocated and used for growth. Other enzymes are involved in the respiratory processes, which release energy for cell division and growth. Food materials are translocated to root and shoot growing points. The third stage is the growth and development of the embryo. The first visible evidence of germination is the emergence of the radicle. The radicle comes out and penetrates the soil. After the radicle, the plumule grows out of the soil, often in a hooked position to help protect the growing point.

Initially, new growth of the embryo-axis is dependent on the food reserves manufactured during seed development and stored in endosperm or cotyledons. The major storage reserves are proteins, carbohydrates (starch) and lipids (oil). These are converted to amino-acids or sugar to support the early embryo growth. The embryo is dependent on the energy and structural material from stored reserves until the seedling emerges into the light and can start photosynthesis.

There are two types of germination:

1. Epigeal germination

- If growth is mainly in the region below the cotyledons (hypocotyl) then the cotyledons are carried above the soil surface as growth proceeds.
- This is called epigeal germination. It is characteristic of non-endospermic seeds e.g beans, squash, apple, cowpeas. The plumule and the cotyledon will appear above the ground.
- The plumule will be protected by the cotyledon. In some plants, the cotyledons will become photosynthetic and increase in size.
- Such cotyledons will remain alive for a long time even after the seedling has grown leaves e.g castor beans and soyabeans.

- Other cotyledons are normally full of large quantities of stored food reserves which support the seedling until it can make its own food

2. Hypogeal germination

- Hypogeal germination is shown by some dicotyledonous plants (pea, broad bean, mango) and by most of the monocotyledonous plants (rice, maize, wheat, coconut) and the dicots (cucurbits, mustard, sunflower, runner bean) and by some monocots like onion.
- If growth is mainly in the region above the cotyledons (epicotyl) then the cotyledons remain below the soil surface. This is called hypogeal germination.
- The cotyledon and the seed coat are left behind in the ground. These seeds have large food reserves in the endosperms and will nourish the seedling until the first green leaves appear.
- In cereals, the plumule is protected by a coleoptile, which is a tough sheath. The coleoptile bursts open with emergence of the first leaf.

SUBTOPIC: PLANT-WATER RELATIONS

Water properties

- Describe water properties in relation to its functions

1.Solvent properties;

- Water is an excellent solvent for ions and polar molecules (charged)
- Any substance that has fairly small molecules with charges on them or that can separate into ions can dissolve in water.
- If sodium chloride is dissolved in water, sodium and chloride separate and spread between water molecules
- The Positive charge on sodium bonds with the negative charge on oxygen,and the negative charge on chloride is attracted to the positive charges of the hydrogen atoms.
- By contrast, non-polar molecules such as lipids are insoluble in water and, if surrounded by water, tend to be pushed together by the water, since the water molecules are attracted to each other.

2. Acts as a transport medium;

- because of its good solvent properties, water transports substances around the bodies of organisms in solution.
- Water is the transport medium in the blood, in the lymphatic, excretory and digestive systems of animals, and in the vascular tissues of plants.

THERMAL PROPERTIES; -

3. High specific heat capacity;-

- The specific heat capacity of water is the amount of heat energy required to raise the temperature of 1 kg of water by 1 °C.
- Water has a relatively high heat capacity, because of the hydrogen bonds that tend to make water molecules stick to each other
- this makes it more difficult for the molecules to move about freely; the bonds must be broken by heat to allow free movement
- in simple terms, more energy is needed to raise the temperature of water than would be the case if there were no hydrogen bonds.
- The high specific heat capacity helps the temperature within cells and within the bodies of organisms to be more constant than that of the air around them.
- Biochemical reactions operate at constant rates and are less likely to be adversely affected by extremes of temperature.

4.High latent heat of vaporisation; -

- The latent heat of vaporisation is a measure of the heat energy needed to vaporise a liquid
- Since water has a high specific heat capacity, it takes a great deal of energy for vaporisation to occur,
- Hydrogen bonds have to be broken before molecules can escape as a gas.

- The energy transferred to water molecules during vaporisation results in a corresponding loss of energy from their surroundings, (e.g. skin and leaves) which therefore cool down.
- large amount of heat energy can be lost for relatively little loss of water, reducing the risk of dehydration.

5. Density and freezing properties; -

- Below 4 °C, the density of water starts to decrease. Ice therefore floats on liquid water and insulates the water under it.
- This is because molecules lose kinetic energy and get closer together.
- At four degrees celcius the molecules form an ice lattice in which they spread out than in liquid water.
- This reduces the tendency for large bodies of water to freeze completely, and increases the chances of life surviving in cold conditions as temp beneath the layer of ice is kept at four degrees celcius,.(insulation)

High surface tension and cohesion;

- Water molecules have very high cohesion – in other words they tend to stick to each other. This explains why water can move in long, unbroken columns through the vascular tissue in plants and is an important property in cells.
- High cohesion also results in high surface tension at the surface of water as water molecules are pulled down and closer to each other than on other parts of the water body.
- This allows certain small organisms, such as pond skaters, to exploit the surface as a habitat.

Water as a reagent;

- Water takes part as a reagent in some chemical reactions inside cells.,e.g., it is used as a reagent in photosynthesis.
- waste oxygen from photosynthesis is the source of the oxygen in the atmosphere which is needed by aerobic organisms for respiration.
- Water is also essential for all hydrolysis reactions

Water Movement

- Discuss factors that affect water uptake
- Explain the mechanisms of water uptake (osmosis, diffusion; bulk flow)

Water Potential (Ψ) Concepts

- Water potential quantifies the tendency of water to move from one area to another due to **osmosis, gravity, and mechanical pressure** and matrix effects.
- Water potential is a measure of the energy status of water.
- Pure water has an energy status of **zero**.
- It is the reference point.
- A technical definition of water potential makes reference to cell membranes, salts that exist in plants and creating certain pressure as you will shortly.
‘Water potential is the difference in free energy per unit volume between matrically bound, pressurized and osmotically constrained water and pure water at the same temperature’.
- Remember that that pure water has a water potential of zero. Addition of solutes like salt or sugar to water **reduces** its water potential.

- Since we started our water potential at zero, reducing the water potential means it attains a negative value.
- It makes the water potential negative. In other words the water molecules in this solution are not likely to move out of a membrane system.

Note the following definitions:

- *Osmosis- movement of water molecules **across** a cell membrane from a region of higher concentration to a region of lower concentration.*
- *Mechanical pressure- this is the resistance imposed to water molecules by the existence of membranes that create a defined volume for water to occupy.*

The water potential of a plant system is made up of the following components:-

- Matric potential
- Osmotic potential
- Pressure potential/turgor pressure

Below is an illustration of how water potential is calculated:-

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \Psi & = & \Psi_{(\text{Osmotic})} & + & \Psi_{(\text{Matric})} & + & \Psi_{(\text{Pressure})} \\
 (\text{Water potential}) & & (\text{Osmotic potential}) & & (\text{Matric potential}) & & (\text{Pressure potential}) \\
 & & (\text{Negative}) & & (\text{Negative}) & & (\text{Positive})
 \end{array}$$

Now let us explain the three components of water potential listed above.

a) The osmotic potential

- This comes about as an effect of solutes.
- If solutes are added to water, the free energy of water is reduced as a result of interactions between the solutes and the water molecules.
- The concentration of solutes and the type of solutes dilute with the water molecules reducing the water activity.
- The importance of osmotic potential is that both the inorganic (*potassium, sodium and chlorine*) and organic (*sucrose, glycerol and glycine*) solutes affect the osmotic potential of plant cells.
- Inorganic solutes occur predominantly in the vacuoles while occur in the cytoplasm. These components play an important role in water regulation of plants. This is defined as ionic adjustment of the cell.
- This condition makes it possible for plants to respond to changes in surrounding water conditions.
- The amounts of solutes dissolved in water constrain water movement and therefore it's designated as negative.

b) The matric potential

- This describes the availability of charged surfaces in the cell walls and in the cell system. There is interaction with water molecules resulting in the reduction of water's ability to freely move hence free energy or water potential.
- This water potential represents suction of water. Water can be held in cell wall and cell membranes and this is an **adsorptive** effect.
- Water can be held in capillaries by surface tension effect.
- All these forces reduce the mobility and activity of water within the plant thereby lowering the water potential.
- The amounts of matric forces or charged surfaces available bind water and reduce its movement and therefore it is designated as negative.

c) The pressure potential

- This describes pressure exerted on water by the cell wall which forces water to move. Pressure potential in plant cells is a result of cell walls which push against cell contents especially when the cell is turgid.
- The pressure potential of pure water is zero.
- Thus any increase in pressure increases the tendency of water to move (*out a permeable membrane*).
- Hence it is denoted by a positive value. The importance of pressure potential is **turgidity**. It increases turgor pressure in the cell.
- This exerts pressure on the cell wall and the protoplasm and the cell volume is increased by 10-30%. It is important for rigidity; shape and straightness in young plants which have not lignified i.e. cellulose, hemi-cellulose and lignin have not yet developed (*remember cell differentiation-Botany*).
- When water surrounding the cell is lower than that of the plant cell, water moves out of the cell. There will be shrinkage of the cell volume, the concentration of the cytoplasm increases and then there is separation of the cell wall. This condition is called **plasmolysis**. In crop plants it is observed as wilting.

Diffusion

- This is the random movement of individual molecules of a substance from a region of high concentration to low concentration of water.
- The tendency is a free distribution of water molecules throughout the available space until even distribution exists.
- The greater the difference between the high and the low concentration of molecules, the steeper the gradient and the faster will be the rate of diffusion.
- Diffusion is important in plant mineral relations because it is involved in the movement of water and mineral nutrients to the root surfaces.

Radial movement of water

- Describe water flow pathways from cell to cell.
 - Apoplast
 - Symplast
 - Vacuoler
- In fact the water potential of the roots is ten times lower than that of the soil. Water therefore moves down this gradient into the root hairs by **osmosis**.
- Once into the epidermal cells, water moves across the root cortex and enters the xylem in the centre of the root, this is because the xylem sap has a more negative water potential than the root hairs.
- Once water is in the roots, it moves across the cortex to the xylem down a gradient that exist between the roots and the xylem.

The water potential gradient is created by the active (energy requiring) accumulation of mineral ions in xylem. Remember what happens when we add salts! Water moves across the cortex by three different routes:

a) Symplast pathway

- Water moves into the cytoplasm of a cortical cell and then to adjacent cells through the interconnecting plasmodesmata.
- The symplast pathway is considered the ‘living route’ because water has to pass through the interior of the cell and get transmitted from cell to cell.

b) Vacuolar pathway

- Water passes from cell vacuole to cell vacuole through neighbouring cells, crossing the symplast and apoplast and moving through membranes and tonoplasts (*vacuolar membrane*) (*remember the plant cell structure*) by osmosis.
- Relatively little water moves through this pathway.

c) Apoplast pathway

- Water moves from one cortical cell to another through spaces in the cell wall, without entering the cytoplasm of the cell.
- This is movement of water through the non-living continuum of the epidermal and cortex cell. Note that the apoplast is the major pathway for water movement into the xylem
- . This is because the symplast route offers resistance to water movement.

Transpiration

- Describe environmental factors affecting the rate of transpiration.

Transpiration refers to the loss of water by plants.

Factors affecting transpiration in plants

Atmospheric factors that determine the rate of transpiration also determine the rate of water uptake. The rate of transpiration is directly proportional to the potential gradient between the leaf and the air.

a) Temperature

- Transpiration increases with increases with temperature.
- Temperature increases the vapour pressure between the leaf surface and the atmosphere. Any increase in temperature at any given water vapour will decrease relative humidity of air because air expands.
- Air spaces between the leaf and the stomata are always at saturation vapour pressure.
- A rise in temperature will increase vapour pressure gradient between the leaf and the atmosphere. This gradient is approximately doubled with every 1⁰C rise in temperature.

b) Wind

- Wind increases transpiration and water absorption from the soil by removing layers of unsteady air on leaf surfaces called boundary layers. The wind increases vapour pressure gradient between the leaf and the atmosphere by removing the boundary layer resistance.

c) Light

- Light affects the closing and opening of stomata. The stoma closes during the **dark** period and during **water stress**, greatly reducing the amount of water lost through transpiration.
- If the amount of water lost by the plant is minimal, indirectly the amount of water absorbed by the plant is also reduced.

Let us look at some adaptations by some plants to minimize water loss. These plants we call them **xerophytic** plants. These are plants that have developed adaptations to minimise water lose. They are adapted to the arid regions.

- They have well developed root systems compared to shoot i.e. have more roots than shoots.
- They have reduced leaf area.
- They lose their leaves at the onset of moisture stress.
- They have thick cuticle.
- They possess succulent storage tissues.
- They roll leaves during water stress.
- They close their stoma during the day e.g. pine apple.
- They have hairs on their leaves.
- They have leaves that reflect the sun.
- Osmotic adjustment: an increase in solutes in root cells occur in response to drought stress and water moves in the cell for storage. This enables the plant to take up more water.

SUBTOPIC BIOLOGICAL NITROGEN FIXATION

Biological Nitrogen Fixation

- Describe biological nitrogen fixation in legumes
- Describe the role of Nitrogen fixing bacteria in symbiosis with legumes
- Outline the importance of biological nitrogen fixation as alternative to inorganic fertilizers.

NITRIFICATION

- *Nitrification* is a biological process whereby ammonium is converted to nitrate is called nitrification. The process occurs only under aerobic conditions. Nitrification is carried out mainly by the nitrifying bacteria which can build new cell material from carbon dioxide, water and a suitable selection of minerals. The nitrifying bacteria obtain their energy from the oxidation of ammonium or of nitrite ion and are chemoautotrophs.

Nitrification

- The oxidation of ammonium in soil is carried out in two steps each of which results in the liberation of energy which is used by the nitrifying bacteria to fix atmospheric carbon dioxide for cell synthesis. The first step is the conversion of ammonium to nitrite (NO_2^-) by bacteria in the genus, *Nitrosomonas*.

Nitrosomonas

- Nitrosomonas have to oxidise between 35 and 70 ammonium ions to release enough energy to assimilate one molecule of carbon dioxide.
- The second step is the conversion of nitrite ion (NO_2^-) to nitrate ion (NO_3^-) by bacteria in the genus, *Nitrobacter*. Nitrobacter, which oxidise nitrite are even less efficient as they have to oxidise from 70 to 100 nitrite ions to assimilate a molecule of carbon dioxide.

Nitrobacter

- *Consequently*, nitrifying bacteria oxidise large quantities of ammonia or nitrite while producing little growth. Nitrite, if it accumulates in acid soils, can be toxic to plants. Fortunately *Nitrobacter* are able to oxidise considerable quantities of nitrite and it is unusual for nitrite to accumulate. As the nitrifying bacteria consist of a species with rather specialised requirements and in general intolerant of anaerobic conditions, acidity and extreme temperatures, it is not surprising that compared to ammonification, nitrification occurs under a much narrower range of soil conditions.

Soil conditions affecting Nitrification are more sensitive to environmental conditions compared to other heterotrophic organisms responsible for the release of ammonium from organic nitrogen containing compounds (ammonification). Let us briefly examine some conditions that affect nitrification according to Brady (2007), as follows.

- i) Nitrification can only occur in the presence *ammonium* to be oxidised. The soil ammonium level is determined by the C/N ratio of crop residues found in soils. Therefore, it may be prevented by crop residues with high C/N ratios which prevent the release of ammonium from nitrogen containing organic compounds when compared to residues of low C/N ratios. We will cover in more detail C/N ratios of crop residues in Unit 10.
- ii) Nitrifying bacteria require *oxygen* and therefore are aerobic. Oxygen is used in the oxidation of NH_4^+ and NO_2^- ions to NO_3^- ions. Good soil drainage promotes soil aeration and thus increases the rate of nitrification compared to a poorly drained soil with little amounts of oxygen.
- iii) Soil moisture: Nitrifying bacteria require optimum amounts of *soil moisture* for oxidation of NH_4^+ and NO_2^- ions to NO_3^- ions. Moisture rehydrates the bacterial enzymes so that they become active and be able to catalyse the first and second step chemical reactions. High and low amounts of moisture retard nitrification as high reduces oxygen concentration and low dehydrate the enzymes. Therefore, an optimum amount of soil moisture is necessary.
- iv) An optimum *soil temperature* range (20 to 30°C) is required as it enhances the enzymatic driven processes in first and second step of nitrification. High temperatures above 35°C will retard the process and extreme temperatures > 50°C will stop it because of enzyme denaturation.
- v) Commercially available *nitrification inhibitors*, such as nitrapyrin (N-Serve) and etridiazol (Dwell) can temporarily inhibit or retard the nitrification process. These chemicals achieve this by preventing bacteria nitrosomonas from converting nitrite ions (NO_2^-) to nitrate ions (NO_3^-). The chemicals normally are mixed with nitrogen fertilizers to prevent temporarily the formation of nitrate ions. As result nitrate leaching potential in wet and sandy soils can be reduced.

Conditions favouring nitrification

- Supply of NH_4^+ ions . Excess NH_4^+ is toxic to nitrobacter
- Oxygen supply --- well drained soils. nitrifying bacteria are aerobes
- Optimum moisture similar to that for plant growth (60%)
- Temperatures in the range 20-30 °C.
- Abundance of exchangeable Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} and optimum nutrient levels for plant growth

Biological Nitrogen Fixation

- Approximately 139 000Mg fixed annually globally
- Next to photosynthesis in importance
- A few organisms are involved:- Bacteria of the genii rhizobia brady-rhizobia, actinomycetes and cyanobacteria

Mechanism

- Dependent on nitrogenase enzyme - nitrogenase catalyses reduction of dinitrogen gas to ammonia
- Ammonia gas combines with organic acid to form amino acids and then proteins

- nitrogen reduction takes place on nitrogenase
- Nitrogenase is a complex of 2 proteins:
 - Small protein contains iron
 - Large protein contains molybdenum
- nitrogenase is destroyed by oxygen so it needs to be protected from oxygen
- This is achieved by the leghaemoglobin which binds oxygen from nitrogenase but available for respiration of other parts
- Nitrogen fixing nodules are red in colour which is a distinguishing mark
- Breaking the tripple bond in nitrogen requires a lot of energy
- This is obtained by association with higher plants which supply the energy through photosynthesis
 - The larger protein converts atmospheric energy to ammonia using electrons provided by the smaller protein
 - M sights capture nitrogen while P sites receive electrons provided by small protein
 - Reduction reaction is end product-inhibited. Ammonia accumulation inhibits N-fixation
 - Too much nitrogen soil inhibits the formation of nodules. N fixation takes place in nodules
 - N fixing organisms have a high rqmt of molybdenum, iron, phosphorous and sulphur
 - These are either part of nitrogenase or required in its synthesis and use

Symbiotic fixation with legumes

- Symbiosis mutually beneficial relationship
- In agric soils microorganisms are Rhizobium and brady Rhizobium
- Rhizobium are fast growers and acid producers
- Brady rhizobium are slow growers and do not produce acids
- Organisms infect root hair and cortical cells thereby inducing formation of nodules
- Host plants supplies carbohydrates for energy bacteria supply the host plant with reactive N compounds
- The relationship is usually specific

Genus	Species/subgroup	Host legume
Rhizobium	<i>R.leguminosarum</i>	<i>via(vatch),pisum I(peas),lens(lentles) lathyrus(sweet peas)</i>
	<i>bvtrifolli</i>	<i>Trifolium</i> sp
	<i>byphaseoli</i>	<i>Phaseolus</i> spp
	<i>R Meliloti</i>	<i>Melilotus,Medicago,Trigonella</i>
	<i>R loti</i>	lotus ,lupians,cicer
Brady rhizobium	<i>R.Fredii</i>	<i>Glycine</i> (soy bean)
	<i>B.japonicum</i>	<i>Glycine</i>
	<i>B. sp</i>	<i>Vigna</i> (cowpeas) <i>Arachis</i> (peanut) <i>cajanus</i> (pigeon pea)

Symbiotic Fixation with non-legume (with nodules)

- Some non-legumes nodulate and fix N (200 species and >12 genera)
- Their nodules are invaded by actinomycetes of the genus frankia
- important in disturbed lands that are extremely low in fertility as first colonisers
- important in areas undergoing succession eg established artificial wetlands forests
- Cyanobacteria also develop N-fixing symbiotic relationships with green plants

Symbiotic Fixation without nodules

- Cyanobacteria involved, important in rice paddies
- Association is with azolla floating fern
- anabaena cyanobacteria inhabit cavities in the leaves of the floating fern
- spirillum and azotobacter bacteria live in the rhizosphere of certain grasses and non-legumes
- exchange is for root exudates
- amt fixed is 5-30kgN/ha/yr

Non Symbiotic fixation

- Free living microorganisms involved
- Present in soil and water
- Not associated with plants → therefore free living and non-symbiotic
- These are heterotrophs obtain energy from saprophytic decomposition of organic matter
 - Occurs in anaerobic pockets of soils, inside aggregates
- Autotrophs- photosynthesizing bacteria and cyano-bacteria

SUB TOPIC: RESPONSES OF PLANTS TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Environmental factors

- Describe responses of plants to environmental factors
- Outline physiological responses to plants to adverse environmental factors.
- Explain the effects of environmental factors on crop productivity.

TOPIC 3: SOIL FERTILITY AND PLANT NUTRITION

SUBTOPIC: SOIL COMPOSITION AND CHARACTERISTICS

Main constituents of soil

- Identify the soil minerals.
- Describe the four components of soil
- Discuss the significance of soil water to plant growth.
- Explain the role of soil air in plants growth and microbial activity.

- Soil physical properties emanate from the understanding of the three phase of soil (gas, solid and liquid).
- The two most basic physical properties of soils are texture and structure, this chapter gives detail of these physical properties and the laboratory and field methods that are used to measure them.
- The primary method of addressing many of these soil physical properties has been the use of tillage.
- Tillage can change the soil structure, improve moisture intake and storage, improve aeration and fertility. However, tillage can also impact on soil loss from both soil water and wind erosion.

The phases of soils and their relationships

- The soil is made up of three phases, namely gas, liquid and solid.
- These phases can be defined in terms of their masses and volume

Where:

m = mass, a = soil air, w = soil water, s = soil solids, t = total, v = volume, f = soil fluids

From the diagram above:

$$\mathbf{Ma + Mw + Ms = Mt \sim Ms + Mw}$$

$$\mathbf{Va + Vw + Vs = Vt}$$

$$\mathbf{Va + Vw = Vf}$$

Therefore

$$\mathbf{Vf + Vs = Vt}$$

- Fluids occupy the pores or pore spaces in the soil (between the solids)
- **Example:**

If the total volume of a soil is 1 m^3 and the volume occupied by solids is 0.55 m^3 per m^3 of soil, then what is the volume occupied by the soil pores?

$$\mathbf{Vf = Vt - Vs}$$

$$\mathbf{\text{Therefore Vf} = 1 - 0.55 \text{ m}^3\text{m}^{-3}}$$

$$V_f = 0.45 \text{ m}^3 \text{ pores per m}^3 \text{ soil}$$

- So slightly less than half of the total volume of the soil is made up pore spaces which can hold air/ water. If two thirds of this pore space is occupied by water, what is the volume occupied by air

$$V_f = V_a + V_w$$

$$V_a = V_f - V_w$$

$$V_a = 0.45 - 0.67 (0.45)$$

$$V_a = 0.15 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-3}$$

Soil aeration

- Atmospheric air we breathe is composed mainly of: Nitrogen (N₂): 79% Oxygen (O₂): 20.9% Carbon dioxide (CO₂): 0.037%).
- Because O₂ is consumed and CO₂ released during respiration, soil air differs substantially from atmospheric air, and is depleted in O₂ and enriched in CO₂. Soil also has higher relative humidity in most cases.

Composition of gases in air and soil

Gas	Atmosphere	Surface soil air	Subsoil air
N ₂	79%	79%	79%
O ₂	20.9%	14-20.6%	7-18%
CO ₂	0.036%	0.5-0.6%	3-10

- A well aerated soil is one in which gas exchange between the soil and the atmosphere is rapid to prevent oxygen deficiency or carbon dioxide toxicity. Good aeration permits normal functioning of roots and aerobic soil organisms.
- Oxygen must be greater than 10% of the soil air. Aeration problems can be increased due to compaction

Gaseous exchange occurs through mass flow and diffusion

- **Mass flow**- refers to the movement of the whole air mass due to pressure differences between the atmosphere and the soil. Temperature changes or wind currents cause mass flow of gases.
- **Diffusion**- Gas exchange occurs due to movement of air along a concentration gradient caused by differences in partial pressures e.g. low partial pressure of oxygen in the soil cause oxygen to move from the atmosphere into the soil.

Factors affecting aeration

- Biological activity- It varies according to plant/organism type and season of the year among other factors. e.g. respiratory activity from soil organisms is greater during summer than winter, due to higher temperatures in summer.
- Soil factors- The most important factor is the soil water content. If the pores are filled with water, this greatly slows the rate of gas diffusion, as gas exchange is much slower in water than in air. Gas exchange decreases from top to subsoil because the path of movement is much longer. Subsoils are often wetter than top soils, and are therefore less aerated.

- Micro-organisms such as the nitrifying bacteria, which change ammonia to nitrite then nitrate, require oxygen. Nitrate can be denitrified and lost as nitrogen gases.
- Toxic ions such as Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+} can be formed in poorly aerated soils.

Soil water

- The water molecule is a highly polar molecule which interlinked by hydrogen bonding. Because of its polar nature, it is a good solvent, has a high surface tension, and high specific heat capacity.
- In Zimbabwe, water is present in the soil in liquid and gaseous phases.
- We can define the soil water content using **volume** and **mass** symbols (section 3.3)
- The two types of water are **gravimetric (mass)** and **volumetric (volume)** water content

$$\text{Gravimetric water content } \theta_g = M_w/M_s$$

$$= \text{mass of water/oven dry mass of soil}$$

$$\text{Volumetric water content } \theta_v = V_w/V_t$$

$$= \text{volume of water/total volume of soil}$$

$$= \text{mass of water/total volume of soil}$$

Volume of water is approximately equal to mass of water because the density of water = 1 kg m^{-3})

- Gravimetric moisture gives us a direct, clear of how wet a soil is.
- Volumetric water content is used for field measurements e.g. calculating the water requirements during irrigation.
- Therefore volumetric moisture content is usually determined from gravimetric water content.

$$\theta_v = V_w/V_t; \text{ but } V_w = M_w/D_w \text{ and } V_t = M_s/D_b$$

$$\text{Therefore } \theta_v = \frac{M_w/D_w}{M_s/D_b}$$

$$= \frac{M_w}{M_s} \times \frac{D_b}{D_w}$$

$$= \theta_g \times \frac{D_b}{D_w}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \theta_v = \theta_g \times \frac{D_b}{D_w}$$

$$\theta_v = \theta_g \times \frac{D_b}{D_w}$$

- Gravimetric moisture is usually expressed as fractional water content such as g water per gram of soil or kg water per kg of soil.

- Volumetric moisture content is expressed in units of m⁻³ water per m³ of soil or on a depth basis e.g. m m⁻¹ or mm mm⁻¹. In irrigation scheduling, a common unit used is mm water 100 mm of soil (percentage)

Example: If the gravimetric moisture content of a soil is 0.20 kg kg⁻¹ and Db = 1.3 Mg m⁻³, convert this into volumetric water content as a percentage

Answer: 1.3 Mg m⁻³ = 1.3 x 1000 kg m⁻³

$$= 1300 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$$

Density of water = 1000 kg m⁻³

Therefore $\theta_v = \theta_g \times \frac{D_b}{D_w}$

D_w

$$= 0.20 \times \frac{1300}{1000}$$

1000

$$= 0.26 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-3} = 0.26 \text{ mm}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$$

Therefore for a 100 mm of soil

$$= 26\%$$

Measurement of soil moisture

- Measurement of soil moisture is important for agronomy trials, irrigation management, drainage e.t.c.

1. Thermogravimetric analysis

- Soil samples are obtained from the field e.g. using a spade, auger at a given depth
- After careful sealing in plastic bags, the samples are brought back to the lab.
- They are weighed, and then oven dried at 105⁰C for 24-48 hours.
- They are reweighed after oven drying

$$\theta_g = \frac{\text{wet mass} - \text{oven dry mass}}{\text{oven dry mass}}$$

Oven dry mass

The moisture content can be expressed as a percentage.

Advantages – cheap, easy, accurate and direct

Disadvantages- laborious and time consuming, many samples are required, destructive

2. Electrical resistance methods

- A porous material with electrodes is inserted into the soil
- These are usually small cylindrical blocks
- Blocks are buried at different depths
- Soil moisture penetrates the blocks until after some time the moisture in the porous material is in equilibrium with soil moisture.
- When an electric current is passed through the block a certain resistance is measured. If there is a lot of water, resistance is low.
- Soil moisture content is then calculated from a calibration curve.

3. Neutron moisture probe

- It has a radioactive source which is lowered down an access tube into the ground
- The radioactive source emits a cloud of fast neutrons
- The neutrons collide with various atoms in the soil and are slowed down
- Hydrogen ions, being equal in mass to neutrons, are most effective at slowing down the neutrons
- The more hydrogen ions, the higher the resistance.
- The number of slowed down neutrons are then counted by a special detector and a count rate is sent to a digital meter.
- Soil moisture content is then calculated from a calibration curve.

Advantages – quick, accurate and non-destructive

Disadvantages- The machine is expensive, potential radioactive hazard.

Physical soil properties

- Describe the significance of soil horizons and the catena effect.
- Discuss the significance of soil color, texture and structure in crop production
- Describe the management practices of soil structure and texture in crop production.
- Discuss the importance of soil organic matter.
- Determine the soil bulk and particle density and porosity.

Soil Horizons

- A soil profile is a vertical section of a soil in the field that reveals the presence of more or less distinct horizontal layers. The individual layers are called horizons.
- The horizons above parent material are referred to as solum.
- All the loose material including the C horizon is the regolith. Each soil has its distinctive profile characteristics.
- Horizons are named according to their position in the profile and also according to their characteristics

O Horizon- this is an organic (litter) rich layer often found at the surface in humid climates (forested areas). It may contain decomposed/ undecomposed organic matter.

A Horizon- this is the layer that supports most plant/animal life. It is a mineral horizon that has decomposed (humus).

E Horizon this layer shows evidence of eluviation of clay, iron, aluminum sand & silt left behind.

B Horizon- characterized by accumulation of clay, iron (Fe) and Aluminum (Al) or humus. It is often more structured than the A horizon.

C Horizon – this is unconsolidated, or weakly consolidated mineral horizon ie the weathering rock in transition between weathered soil and the underlying unweathered parent material

R Horizon- is made up of continuous hard bedrock which may/may not be the material of the soil above it.

Soil Colour

- Colour shows an integration of chemical, biological and physical transformations and translocations that have occurred within a soil.
- In general, colour of surface horizons indicates biological processes, especially those influenced by the ecological origin of soil organic matter (SOM).
- For instance, SOM gives soil a dark brown to black colour.
- A bright-light colour can be related to an eluvial horizon, where sesquioxides, carbonates and/or clay minerals have been leached out.
- Soil colour is described by using the Munsell notation.
- The 3 properties are always given in the principles of light in the order of hue, value and chroma, and are chosen using a Munsell book which has a standard set of chips.
- This determines the soil colour when the soil is dry and when it is moist.
 - o **Hue** - dominant spectral colour
 - o **Value**- describes the degree of lightness or brightness of the hue reflected in the property of the grey colour that is being added to the hue.
 - o **Chroma** is the relative purity of the dominant (hue)
- The chip with the colour corresponding to that of the soil is selected and its hue, value and chroma written as the soil colour.

Significance / Importance of soil colour

- Soil colour can *provide information about subsoil drainage and the soil moisture conditions of soils.*

- For example in well aerated soils, Fe³⁺ is present which give soil a yellow or reddish colour.
- Colour is *also associated with minerals inherited from parent materials* which may also influence colour in horizons that have not been extensively weathered.

Soil catena

- Nyamapfene, (1991) defines catena *as a sequence of soils derived from same parent material, but differing in properties because they occupy different topographic positions.*
- The differences in soil properties arise because of:
 - i) the differences in soil moisture regime that exists between soils in the sequence, and
 - ii) the degree and nature of lateral water movement at each position.
- The A horizon development levels varies with the levels of climate and the position on the catena
- *In the upland position*, just below the crest, sufficient rainfall penetrates the soil to allow for weathering and development of a deep profile. This site is well drained (above the water table) and water moves internally and carries bases down slope. The soil is mostly composed of stable iron oxides and hence, has a **red colour**.
- *Lower down the slope*, the water table is now closer to the surface and influences the soil morphology. The soil experiences seasonal waterlogging which induces formation of mottles in the subsoil. The soil is **brown in colour** due to the iron oxides being reduced.
- *Still further down slope*, the soils become permanently waterlogged and under these reducing conditions all iron is reduced to the ferrous state. There is little stream flow and the poor drainage encourages accumulation of bases, organic matter and presence of active swelling clays. The clays combine with the organic matter to produce **black soil** above the waterline.
- However, *the soils below the waterline* which are permanently wet, exhibit **gley colours**.

Soil texture

- Soil texture indicates the relative percentages of soil particles making up a soil. Given the relative percentages of sand, clay, silt out of a total of 100%, the texture of a given soil can be determined using the textural triangle.

Sand- has the largest particles and they feel “gritty”

Silts- are medium sized, and they feel soft, silky or “floury”

Clay -are the smallest sized particles, and they feel “sticky”

How to use the Textural triangle.

- Given values of sand, silt and clay, first take the % sand value and follow the parallel direction of the zero axis into the triangle, see where this meets the % silt value by following the parallel direction of the zero axis of the silt.
- When these 2 lines meet, they lie within boundaries of a textural class
- Check that the % clay line also meets at the point by following the direction of the zero axis of clay.

Sand	Silt	Clay	Textural class
40	30	30	CL (Clay Loam)
54	23	23	SaCL (Sand Clay Loam)
95	1	4	(Sand)
23	35	42	(Clay)

Significance / Importance of soil texture

NOV 2019/P2/QN 3(a)ii – What are the importance of the following soil properties in crop production? -soil texture.

By knowing the textural class of a soil we can deduce much useful information about its chemical and physical behaviour. Soil texture influences soil physical and chemical properties (Brady, 2007) and (Foth, 1990) as follows:

- *Nutrient retention ability* of a sandy clay loam soil is more because of its increased clay content than a loamy sand soil. Increased clay content is an indication of high negatively charged surfaces for cation adsorption.
- *Water holding capacity* of a sandy clay loam soil is more because of its increased clay content than a loamy sand soil. Increased clay content is an indication of high % total pore spaces for water retention ability.
- *Aeration* is likely to be more in sandy soils because of macro-pores when wet compared to an equal mass of clay soil. However, when dry, clay particles will have more air content than an equal mass of sandy soil. This is because clay particles have high % of total pore space than sandy particles that can be occupied by air.
- *Soils easy of tillage* are likely to be difficult on clay soils than sandy loam soil. When wet clay particles become sticky and difficult to till and when dry they become hard and also difficult to till. The opposite is true sand particles are not sticky when wet and hard when dry and a result are easy to till when wet or dry.
- *Soil temperature*: soils high in stone content are likely to warm up quickly than stone-less soils of fine earth during winter in cool regions. This is because large stones absorb and gain heat during the day time and release it at night time for benefit of plants. As a result plants are protected from frost damage. However, soils high in stone content have marked low water holding capacity than stoneless soils of fine earth (White, 2006)

Textural triangle

Soil Texture

- soil texture refers to the relative proportions (%) of particles of various sizes (clay, sand, silt, gravel) in a given soil and soil structure is about the arrangement of soil particles into groups or aggregates (angular blocky, sub-angular blocky, spheroidal, platy etc.)

Soil texture determination (particle size analyses)

- Particle size analysis estimates the percentage sand, silt and clay contents of a given soil and is often reported as percentage by weight.
- This can be done qualitatively (*using a Finger Assessment Technique*).
- Finger assessment technique provides the broad textural category of soil.
- The more sticky and mouldable a wet soil is, the greater the clay content.
- Or quantitatively using sieving and sedimentation. The sieving and sedimentation techniques are two complimentary methods.

Sieving

- It is a simple procedure which separates soil particles > 50 micrometers in diameter.

- A sample is emptied into an assemblage of sieves of known diameters, with the largest sieve on top and smallest at the bottom.
- After a period of shaking, the sand grains will settle into the different sieves. These fractions can then be weighed and their size distribution calculated.

Sedimentation

- Sedimentation on the other hand is used to separate particles which are < 50 micrometers (silt and clay) in diameter.
- The two major sedimentation techniques are the hydrometer and the pipette method.

The hydrometer method.

- The hydrometer is an instrument which measures the density (g per litre) of a soil-water suspension at a given time (figure 3.1)
- the first stage is the dispersion of soil into individual particles.
- This is achieved through mechanical shaking in calgon (sodium hexametaphosphate) solution. Individual soil particles are often bound into aggregates hence the need for dispersion.
- In clay soils with high organic matter content, there may be need to oxidize cementing organic compounds using hydrogen peroxide.
- In highly calcareous soils, it is important to dissolve carbonates using acids.

The hydrometer method is based on Stokes Law which states that:

- The settling velocity of a particle is the net difference between its downward force (gravity) against the bouancy (resistance to fall) by surface friction and movement of the water.
 - When soil particles are suspended in water they tend to sink
 - The settling velocity of a particle is a function of liquid temperature, viscosity and specific gravity of the settling particle.
 - The particles are assumed to be spherical (weakness of Stokes Law).
- According to Stokes Law the settling velocity of a particle is proportional to the square of the radius of the particle.

$$V = \frac{2r^2 (P_s - P_w) g}{9n}$$

v = terminal settling velocity, r = particle radius, Ps = particle density, Pw = density of water, g = acceleration due to gravity, n = viscosity of water.

- High temperatures result in reduced viscosity (why?)

The sand grains settle first because they are larger followed by silt and the clay remains as a colloidal suspension.

Figure3.1: Hydrometer

Density of soils

- Soil texture and structure exert a large influence on the amount and arrangement of the soil solids, these solids in turn affect the density of the soil.
- Density is defined by mass/volume.
- Water is used as the reference and its density is 1 g cm⁻³.

Bulk density

- This is a measure of the density of the soil solids, expressed relative to the bulk volume of soil.
- **Soil bulk density, *Db***, is defined as the ratio of dry soil mass to bulk soil volume (including pore spaces).
- The SI unit for density is megagrams per cubic meter (Mg m⁻³), which is numerically equivalent to grams per cubic centimeter (g cm⁻³).
- Values range from 0.2 in organic soils to 1.9 in heavily compacted soils.

$$\text{Bulk density (Db)} = \frac{M_s}{V_t}$$

$$= \frac{\text{Mass of oven dry solids}}{\text{Total soil volume}}$$

- The measure of density is useful for converting amounts of water, nutrients or air in soil to the field situation.
- It also gives useful information about the state of the structure and pore space of the soil.

Factors affecting bulk density

1. Texture

- Bulk density of a soil varies with the amount of sand, silt and clay particles. Sand particles tend to be separate whereas minute clay particles are sticky and form aggregates.
- Therefore comparing sand particles and clay aggregates of equal size, a clay aggregate has a lower bulk density as it has more pore spaces and fewer solids than sand.

2. Packing of particles/aggregates

- Density varies according to the packing arrangement of the solids, flat, platy particles can pack more densely than rounded ones.
- The final density, therefore, depends on the dominant type of packing/structural arrangement.
- Clay soils have more interaggregate spacing (large pores between aggregates) and intraaggregate spacings (small pores inside the aggregate).
- This combination of inter- and intra-aggregate pores gives clay soils their lower bulk densities and larger total pore spaces. Therefore sandy soils have a higher bulky density than clay soils.

3. Organic matter

- High organic matter tends to produce well aggregated soils with higher amounts of pore space and lower densities.

4. Compaction

- Soils which are subjected to heavy loads tend to be compacted, this results in the reduction in pore size and amount as solids are pushed closer together.
- Subsoils are naturally compacted due to overweight of overlying soil. Subsoils often, therefore, have higher densities than topsoils. Besides this natural compaction, artificial compaction may occur due to activity of man and animals.
- Heavy machinery such as tractors and harvesters cause compaction, especially when soils are wet.
- Tillage, hooves of animals also cause compaction.

Methods of determining bulk density (Clod, Core and Sand replacement method)

1. Core method

- A sharpened, open-ended cylindrical metal container, or ring, is carefully pushed into a soil until the level of the ring is flush with the soil surface.
- The core is then carefully extracted, excess soil is trimmed away until flush with the ends of the ring. In the laboratory, the core plus soil are oven-dried and the soil is weighed.
- The bulk density is then calculated by dividing the oven dry mass of soil by the total volume of the core.

The volume of the core is given by:

$$\text{Volume} = (\pi)(r^2)(h)$$

2. Sand replacement method

- This method is mainly used by engineers. A hole is made in the surface of the soil, about 100 mm diameter by 150 mm deep and the extracted soil is weighed after oven drying to obtain (M_s).
- The volume of the hole is determined by filling it with a measured quantity of dry sand of known density ($D = M/V$).
- By dividing the mass of excavated soil with the volume, the bulk density is determined.

Example: Calculate the mass (kg) of soil in 1 hectare of top soil 0-0.25 m in depth, if the bulk density is 1300 kg m⁻³.

Particle density (D_p)

- This is a measure of the density of the soil solids, expressed relative to the volume of soil solids

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Particle density (D}_p\text{)} &= \frac{M_s}{V_s} \\ &= \frac{\text{Mass of oven dry solids}}{\text{Volume of soil solids}}\end{aligned}$$

- Particle densities are typically around 2650 kg m⁻³ for both clay and sand soils.
- Particle density is a fundamental property of the soil-not affected by structure, management or cropping practices on the soil.
- Soil particle density depends on the actual density of particles.
- Soils high in organic matter have lower particle densities due to the low density of the organic matter.
- Soils with heavy minerals such as Fe, Mn, Pb may have higher particle densities.
- Heavy minerals such as Fe may have particle densities as high as 7870 kg m⁻³. It is measured using the pycnometer bottle method (reading assignment).
- Units for particle density are the same as those of bulky density (kg m⁻³)

Porosity

- Porosity (f) is defined as the proportion of soil occupied by air and water, that is the pore space per unit volume. It is determined largely by the structural arrangement and texture of the soil solids.
- It can be defined as a unitless ratio/ expressed as a percentage

$$\begin{aligned}f &= \frac{V_f}{V_t} \\ &= 1 - \frac{V_s}{V_t} \\ &= 1 - \frac{\text{solids}}{\text{total volume}}\end{aligned}$$

- If we substitute in terms of densities

$$\begin{aligned}D_p &= M_s/V_s \\ \text{Therefore } V_s &= M_s/D_p\end{aligned}$$

$$D_b = M_s/V_t$$

$$\text{Therefore } V_t = M_s/D_b$$

$$f = 1 - \frac{M_s/D_b}{M_s/D_p}$$

$$M_s/D_p$$

$$\text{Therefore } f = 1 - D_b/D_p$$

$$f = 1 - \frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{particle density}}$$

Example: If the bulk density of a soil is 1400 kg m⁻³ and the particle density is 2650 kg m⁻³. What is the porosity as a percentage (%)

Types and functions of pores

Macropores > 50 micrometers (diameter)

Mesopores 0.5 – 50 micrometers

Micropores < 0.5 micrometers

Pores have three main functions and these are: transmission pores, which are vital for easy movement of water, nutrients and air, storage pores which are vital for retention of water for use by crops and Residual pores which are water tightly bound and plants cannot utilize it.

A good agricultural soil has a combination of the three pore types.

Aggregation

- Aggregates are secondary units or granules composed of many soil particles held together by organics, Fe oxides, carbonates, clays, and/or silica. Very important for soil aeration and water properties.

Biological Processes affecting Aggregation:

1 Earthworms and termites (burrowing and moulding)

- Move soil, ingest it, and produce pellets or casts
- Plant roots also move soil particles

2 Roots and fungal hyphae (stickiness)

- Exude sticky polysaccharides
- Soil particles and microaggregates bound into larger agglomerations called macroaggregates
- Mycorrhizae secrete a substance called glomalin

3 Organic glues produced by microorganisms

- Bacteria also produce sticky polysaccharides in decomposed plant residues

Effect of Tillage on Aggregation

Short term:

- Improvement in aggregation if done on moderately dry soil
- Breaks up large clods, loosening soil and increasing porosity
- Incorporates organic matter into the soil

Long term:

- Loss of aggregation
- Enhanced oxidation of organic material reduces aggregation
- Loss of macro-porosity occurs if tillage is carried out in a wet soil (puddled)
- Effect less pronounced where Fe & Al oxides plentiful

Soil Structure

- Soil structure refers to the aggregation of primary soil particles (sand, silt, clay) into compound particles or group/clusters of primary particles.
- Good management maintains or develops good structure that encourages an extensive root system. In the determining soil structure, the shape and size of aggregates is determined.

Choices of Soil Structure

Peds

- Structural units are called peds, and have distinct boundaries and well-defined planes of weakness between the aggregates.
- They consist of primary particles bound together by cementing agents like organic matter, clay, and hydrous oxides of iron and aluminum and they can take the following shapes; Granular, Blocky, Platy, Prismatic and Columnar.

Granular- porous and characteristic of the surface horizons (A) and are usually less than 0.5cm in diameter. They are subject to wide and rapid changes.

Blocky- can be in the shape of cubes or sub angular with an average diameter of 1.5 - 5.0 cm. This structure is common in the B horizon particularly in the humid regions.

Prismatic-can be in the form of level tops or columnar (rounded tops). Both of these are usually found in the B horizon. It is common in soils of arid and semi arid regions.

Platy- may occur in any part of the profile at times inherited from the soil material, but usually found in compacted soils

- In soils with good structure, the pore space that occurs between peds is relatively large and facilitates water and air movement.
- Well-developed structure is very important in clayey soils as it facilitates water and air movement.
- Unlike texture, structure can be altered by tillage or traffic. Tilling soils that are too wet, or compacting soils with heavy equipment can break down the natural structural units.

Importance of soil structure

NOV 2019/P2/QN 3(a)i – What are the importance of the following soil properties in crop production? -soil structure.

Soil structure is a very important physical property of the soil as it influences some properties of soils namely: Brady (2007) notes that some soil properties can be influenced by type of soil structure as follows:

- **Soil water retention ability** is more in crumb structures because they are small and porous and therefore exhibit a high % of total pore space and retain more water between their pores spaces. In contrast, blocky or prismatic structures are large and have low % of total pore space and retain less water between their pore spaces.
- **Soil porosity** is less in plate-like structures because they consist of piles of cemented clay particles that are horizontally laid on soil surface or created by compaction in the subsoil that are non-porous. They exhibit a low degree of porosity. Water is lost as runoff on surfaces or between layers of plate-like structures. In contrast, prismatic and blocky structures are vertically laid in soils and are porous. The large macro-pores between their structures allow rapid downward movement of water by force of gravity. In contrast to plate-like, prismatic or blocky structures, crumb structures are small in size and porous. They consist of many micro-pores and therefore exhibit a high degree of porosity.
- **Soil aeration** is high in crumb structures because they are small in size and are porous. They exhibit a high % of pore space which accounts for their good aeration and high water retention ability for the growth of plants and organisms. In contrast, blocky or prismatic structures are large in size and have low total % of pore space compared to an equal mass of a crumb structure. They exhibit a low degree of aeration that is favourable for soil organisms and root respiration.
- **Soil colour** of plate-like structures may show bluish and greenish colours an indication of poor drainage and poor nutrient holding capacity. In contrast, crumb structures are dark in colour because they consist of high organic matter content.
- **Compaction** in crumb structures is less because they are porous, friable and not compacted. They allow easy penetration of numerous roots between crumb pores that is necessary for the development and growth a plant with fibrous root system. In contrast, blocky, plate-like or prismatic structures are large in size, non porous and compacted. Therefore large roots can only penetrate between the structures but fibrous roots are restricted only to the outer surfaces of these structures. As a result plants with fibrous roots systems will absorb less water and nutrients from such structures.

- *Bulky density* of crumb structures exhibit high % of total pore space which accounts for their low bulk densities. This is an indication of reduced compaction which provides an ideal condition for water retention, aeration, nutrient retention, root respiration and penetration for plants/organisms. In contrast, platy, blocky or prismatic structures exhibit low % of total pore space and have high bulk densities. They exhibit low total surface area water retention, nutrient retention and root penetration when compared to equal masses of a crumb structure.

SUBTOPIC: PLANT NUTRITION

Essential nutrients

- Explain the role of macronutrients and nutrients plant growth and development
- Determine fertilizer requirements in crops.

Macro nutrients

Nitrogen

Functions

1. It is a constituent of amino acids, nucleic acids, nitrogen bases, nucleotides, amides and amines which have structural and physiological functions in plants
2. It is a constituent of chlorophyll
3. it is a structural component of cell walls

Deficiency/excessive symptoms

- Deficiency causes stunted growth and pale green to yellow leaves smaller than usual as nitrogen is mobilized from the lower leaves to new areas of growth causing chlorosis (yellowing) and firing (enhanced senescence) of lower leaves
- Excessive nitrogen delays senescence and stimulates growth e.g in cereals it increases susceptibility to lodging

Phosphorus

Functions

1. A constituent of plant compounds like enzymes and proteins
2. A structural component of phosphoproteins, phospholipids and nucleic acids
3. Energy storage and transfer through compounds adenosine diphosphate (ADP) and adenosine triphosphate (ATP)
4. It is involved in symbiotic nitrogen fixation
5. Important in maturation process and in seed formation

Deficiency

- Stunted growth and often leaves exhibit a reddish to purplish discoloration because of enhanced anthocyanin formation especially in maize.
- Dark green colour of leaves than normal is caused by reduced leaf area expansion with no effect on chlorophyll manufacture.

Potassium

Function

1. Maintains the osmotic potential for cells
2. Involved in water uptake from soil, water retention in plant tissue and transport of water and assimilates
3. Required as an activator of enzymes in meristematic tissue
4. Stomatal opening and closing

5. Necessary for good quality (shelf life) development in fruits and vegetables

Deficiency

- Leaf chlorosis followed by necrosis at the leaf tip and margins
- growth retardation as K^+ is retranslocated from mature leaves and stems and these organs become chlorotic and necrotic
- High susceptibility to water stress due to the role of K^+ in osmotic adjustment which maintain high cellular water contents under drought conditions
- High susceptibility to fungal attack due to changes in enzymatic activity and organic compounds and reduced lignifications
- Nutritional and processing quality of fruits and tubers is adversely affected

Sulphur

Functions

1. Constituent of amino acids cysteine and methionine which are essential for protein synthesis
2. Involved in formation of vitamins and some hormones synthesis
3. Present in glycosides which gives onion, garlic and mustard their characteristic odours

Deficiency symptoms

- Symptoms similar to those of nitrogen deficiency i.e leaf chlorosis
- The difference is that symptoms are more severe on young leaves whereas for nitrogen deficiency are more severe on old leaves as sulphur is not as mobile as nitrogen

Calcium

Functions

1. A component of every cell wall in the form of calcium pectate
2. Involved in cell elongation and division

Deficiency symptoms

- Stunted growth with curled and distorted leaves which often form a hook at the leaf tip
- Roots show a stubby brown appearance
- Blossom end rot in tomato, water melon and paprika, black heart of celery, tip burn of lettuce and bitter pit of apple due to loss of cell wall and membrane integrity

Magnesium

Functions

1. An essential constituent of chlorophyll and cellular pH control
2. A cofactor for a number of enzymes

Deficiency symptoms

- Interveinal chlorosis which starts with older leaves

Micro nutrients

Zinc

Functions

1. Has a direct influence on the level of auxin in plants
2. Involved in a number of enzyme systems

Deficiency /toxicity symptoms

- Severe stunting of leaves (little leaf) and lack of internode elongation (rosetting)
- Zn toxicity is associated with use of sewage sludge and causes inhibition of root elongation and chlorosis of young leaves

Boron

Functions

1. Involved in the transport of sugars across cell membrane and in the synthesis of cell wall material
2. Influences transpiration through the control of sugar and starch formation
3. Affects carbohydrate metabolism and plays a role in amino acid formation and synthesis of proteins

Deficiency symptoms

- Vary broadly with crops however stunting, discoloration and eventual death of the apical meristems of both shoots and roots are frequently encountered

Molybdenum

Functions

1. A part of nitrate reductase enzyme system involved in the reduction of NO_3^- to NH_4^+ after it is absorbed by the plant
2. A structural component of nitrogenase which is involved in the fixation of N_2 into the ammonium form in symbiotic relationship with legumes

Deficiency symptoms

- Mo plays a role in N metabolism hence early symptoms resemble those of nitrogen deficiency
- Margins may wilt, roll and cup as deficiency becomes more severe

DETERMINING NUTRIENT STATUS AND NEEDS

Nov 2017 zimsec

- Common diagnostic tools to determine nutrient needs of plants include deficiency symptoms, chemical soil tests and plant tissue tests
- What do you think are some of the disadvantages of using deficiency symptoms as a diagnostic tool?

Soil analysis

- Begins with soil sampling
- If soils are wrongly sampled then a wrong recommendation will be given even though the analysis of the wrong sample will be correct
- representative sample is needed
- Soil Ph and nutrient content changes through the soil profile hence soil samples should be taken from a consistent depth
- Generally for orchards and vine yards there is need to core to 46-51cm, ploughed fields to plough depth and fields planted or to be planted in rows but not ploughed there is need to core to the depth where 75% of plant roots will be found

Plant /foliar analysis (Leaf analysis)

- is the most precise method of monitoring plant nutrient levels
- While soil analysis reveals the levels of essential soil nutrients, leaf analysis shows the grower exactly what the plant has successfully absorbed

- Plant analysis can be helpful in detecting nutrient deficiencies before they affect plant health and yield.
- With perennial fruit crops, leaf analysis is better than soil tests for determining an optimal fertilization program as it shows exactly what the plant has succeeded in taking up.
- Leaf analysis is helpful in determining nutrient deficiencies especially of micro nutrients before they affect plant health or yield
- The time of sampling is critical and varies with crops but it must be when elemental status could make a difference in plant growth as well as times when accumulation is at its maximum or steady state -leaf samples should be taken when most vegetative growth has subsided
- To maintain optimal performance of orchard it is generally recommended to perform a leaf analysis for each block once every three years to ensure maintenance of adequate nutrient levels.
- If nutritional problems are suspected in a given planting it's good to take both leaf and soil tests

General Recommendations for taking accurate leaf samples

- Choose between 8 and 10 separate trees that are representative of the block.
- Collect 60-100 leaves to get a representative sample.
- Don't mix leaves from different varieties, rootstocks, ages, soil types, blocks, or farms. that a comparison can be made between them.
- Leaves should be taken at about the midpoint of the new growth and from all actively growing parts of smaller trees and between waist and head high on larger trees.

Describe the importance of liming the soil

[5]

- Increases soil pH;
- Improves availability of nutrients
- Flocculates the soil / improves soil structure;
- Supply calcium
- Enables activity of microorganisms;
- Example of biological nitrogen fixation;
- Improves soil workability;

SUBTOPIC: SOIL ORGANIC MATTER

Constituents of soil organic matter

- Identify constituents of soil organic matter.
 - Organic residues
 - Water-soluble fraction
 - Alcohol-soluble fraction
 - Proteins
 - Determining soil organic matter content
- **Organic matter**-These are plant and animal residue in their various stages of decay/ decomposition.
- Organic matter usually contain carbon.

Constituents of organic matter

2. organic residues, stable
3. Water soluble fractions-sugars
4. Alcohol soluble fractions-lipids

Organic residues

- Plant and animal residues make up 35% dry matter for decomposition
- The predominant element is carbon and oxygen with small quantities of hydrogen, nitrogen ,sulfure k and Ca²⁺
- As organic matter is decomposed by various organisms in the soil the organic matter changes until a stable product is formed (humus).
- **Humus:**
- The stable portion of soil organic matter that results from microbial degradation of residues.
- Dark colored
 - About 58% C, 5% N
 - Complex chemical structure, aromatic plus aliphatic functional groups
 - Difficult to break down because of structure
 - high CEC

Difference between organic matter and humus

Organic matter	humus
Ranges from fresh residues	Fully decayed residues
Reactive	Stable
Ranges from light brown to dark black	Darker brown to black

- The breakdown of animal bodies, products and manure provide a secondary source of organic matter to the soil
- Bodies of soil organisms such as bacteria; fungi , battles ,ants and earthworms fall under this group

- Organic matter such as paper, sewage, industrial effluent can be recycled as organic waste to provide organic matter.

Alcohol soluble fractions

- This is a fraction of organic matter which is usually derived from seeds, animal skins, and exoskeletons of soil organisms.
- These include cellulose, lignin, waxes chitins and lipids

Water soluble fractions

- This fraction consist of sugars, starch.
- The fraction is characterized by quick decomposition and is quickly decomposed by enzymes from different organisms.

Proteins

- The fraction is characterized by quick decomposition and is quickly decomposed by enzymes from different organisms

Describe 5 characteristics of a good soil structure from an agricultural point of view. (5)

- good penetration of plant roots and water
- fairly easy to cultivate/friable
- moderate to high levels of organic matter
- forms water stable aggrigates/resistance to erosion
- less prone to surface silling/capping
- less prone to compaction

Why are we talking about organic matter?

- SOM contributes to soil aggregation, drainage, aeration, structure
- SOM is the major substrate for microbial growth in the soil
- SOM is key for good “soil quality”
- SOM is the major reservoir of N in the soil
- Soil SOM is the major storage reservoir of C in the environment.

Decomposition of organic residues

- Describe the role of soil organisms in organic matter decomposition
- Identify organisms involved in different stages of decomposition process
- Describe the carbon: nitrogen (C: N) ratio
- Describe how the C:N ratio
- Mineralization and Immobilization

Role of organisms in organic matter decomposition

1. Mineralization of Organic matter

- Mineralization- organic (unavailable) nutrients are broken down into inorganic (available) forms. E.g. degradation of proteins, amino sugars and nucleic acids to NH_4^+ (ammonium).
- Immobilization on the other hand is whereby nutrients are converted from inorganic to organic.
- **N- Mineralisation** Occurs in a number of steps:

Ammonification - organic nitrogen is converted to ammonium- nitrogen

Organic N----- NH_4^+

- Reaction carried out by bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes and hydrolytic enzyme are involved e.g. Proteases which breakdown proteins into peptides

Peptidases which decompose peptides into amino acids

Deaminases – these convert amino acids to ammonia

Ammonia can also be lost as a gaseous form (volatilization)

- Surplus ammonia produced during decomposition of organic nitrogen compounds is the available ammonia in the soil and can be adsorbed onto clay lattices.

2. Nitrification

During nitrification, ammonium is converted into nitrate. The process occurs under aerobic conditions and the process is carried out by chemoautotrophic nitrifying bacteria.

NH_4^+ ----- NO_2^- ----- NO_3^-

- Nitrification occurs in two stages. The first stage is carried out by Nitrosomonas which derive their energy solely from CO_2 and their energy from the oxidation of NH_4^+ to NO_2^- .

Nitrobacter converts NO_2^- to NO_3^- (plus energy)

Nitrogen fixation

- Considerable atmospheric N is converted to organic N by a process called biological fixation. Nitrogen fixation is carried out by microorganisms many of which form symbiotic relationships with the plants.
- Free living (non-symbiotic) forms of N-fixers includes aerobic bacteria (Azobacteri, Pseudomonas, Aerobacter and many blue green algae) and anaerobic bacteria (Clostridium).
- Symbiotic associations occur in trees and shrubs, and in the actinomycetes Frankia and most importantly between rhizobia and legumes.

3. Legume-rhizobia symbiosis

- Establishment of legume –rhizobium symbiosis involves interaction of both symbionts. Rhizobia are attracted to root surfaces, where they proliferate and attach to root cells.
- The initial response of the root hair to rhizobium involves the tight curling of the root-hair tip. Then an infection thread is formed.
- The host plant benefits by obtaining fixed nitrogen and the plants supplies the bacteria with carbohydrates.
- A given species of bacteria only nodulates a specific legume, unless in promiscuous species.

- Factors affecting N fixation include, temperature, aeration, pH (neutral) and high levels of available N tend to depress nodulation and fixation.

4. Mycorrhizae of fungus roots.

- Plants supplies the fungi with carbohydrates and the mycorrhizae increases the area (upto 10 times) of adsorption of roots for nutrients (esp P, Zn and Cu), mycorrhizae are thought to increase drought tolerance and improve disease resistance of plants.
- **Types of mycorrhizae**

Endotrophic (Vesicular-Arbuscular Mycorrhiza VAM) Ectotrophic mycorrhizae (ECM),

Explain the role of C: N ratio in decomposition

- High C:N ratio > 25% - slow rate of decomposition
 - high immobilisation
 - add nitrogen for faster decomposition.
- Low C:N ratio <25% -high rate of decomposition
 - high mineralization

Factors affecting soil organic matter levels

- Describe factors affecting soil organic matter levels
 - Original organic matter composition
 - Soil nitrogen levels
 - Climate conditions
 - Soil drainage conditions
 - pH of organic matter
 - organic matter form/size fraction
 - soil texture
- discuss the benefits of soil organic matter

Describe the role played by the following organisms in organic matter decomposition.

i) bacteria

ii) earth worm

Bacteria- decomposes organic matter

- mineralizes organic matter/nutrients to inorganic forms
- denitrify soil nitrates, fix nitrate into the soil

Earthworms- provide earation/ drainage

- mix organic matter with soil
- secrete nutritious worm cast
- promotes chemical and physical properties

Why are legumes used as green manuring plants?

- high amounts of foliage increase manure.
- legumes grow fast and produce residues.
- They are hardly under moisture or diseases stress.
- They have soft stems for quick decomposition.
- Long roots for absorption of water.
- They withstand drought.

Explain 2 ways in which Organic matter content of a soil influences: -

(i) Soil temperature [2]

(ii) Bulky density [2]

(i)

- Organic matter darkens the soil;
- Dark soil absorbs radiation;
- Decomposition process releases heat
- O.M imparts temperature rise;
- Moderates soil temperature

(ii)

- O.M aerates the soil;
- Encourages aggregation;
- Increases volume of soil;
- Lowers bulky density.

TOPIC 4: PRINCIPLES OF CROP BREEDING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

SUB TOPIC: GENETICS

Principles of genetics

- describe the structure of a chromosome
- describe the structure of DNA
- explain DNA replication
- describe protein synthesis starting from DNA

Chromosomes

- A composed of deoxyribonucleic acid [DNA] and protein with small amount of chromosomal RNA .
- DNA has a negative charge distributed along it's length and positively charged protein molecule called histones and bond to it .
- Between division of the nucleus each chromosome contain one DNA molecule .
- Before the nucleus divides the DNA replicates such that at nuclear division the chromosomes is a double structure, containing two identical DNA molecules.
- The two parts of the chromosomes are referred to as chromatids.
- Each chromatids one of the two identical molecules.
- Species in which there are two sets of chromosomes are referred to as **diploid** given symbol **2n** . A few simple organisms have only one set of chromosomes and are referred to as **hyploid** symbol **n**
- Garments either sex are haploid.

Diagram of Chromosome

- There are two types of nuclear division: meiosis and mitosis.
- Mitosis is a process by which a cell nucleus divides to produce daughter nuclei containing identical sets of chromosomes of parent cell.
- Usually it is followed by division of whole cell to form two daughter cells a process known as cell division.
- Mitosis with cell division results in increase in cell number and is the method by which growth replacement and repair of cell occurs in eukaryotes.
- In unicellular eukaryotes, mitosis results in asexual reproduction.

Structure of DNA

- DNA is double-stranded, so there are two polynucleotide strands alongside each other. The strands are antiparallel, i.e. they run in opposite directions.
- The two strands are wound round each other to form a double helix
- The two strands are joined together by hydrogen bonds between the bases. The bases therefore form base pairs, which are like rungs of a ladder.
- The base pairs are specific. A only binds to T (and T with A), and C only binds to G (and G with C). These are called complementary base pairs
- This means that whatever the sequence of bases along one strand, the sequence of bases on the other strand must be complementary to it. (Incidentally, complementary, which means matching, is different from complimentary.)

DNA showing the complementary base pairing between antiparallel strands

DNA showing the double helix

spacefilling model of the double helix

DNA Replication /DNA Synthesis

- DNA is copied, or replicated, before every cell division, so that one identical copy can go to each daughter cell.
- The method of DNA replication is obvious from its structure: the double helix unzips and two new strands are built up by complementary base-pairing onto the two old strands.

- Replication starts at a specific sequence on the DNA molecule called the replication origin.
- The enzyme helicase unwinds and unzips DNA, breaking the hydrogen bonds that join the base pairs, and forming two separate strands.
- The new DNA is built up from the four nucleotides (A, C, G and T) that are abundant in the nucleoplasm.
- These nucleotides attach themselves to the bases on the old strands by complementary base pairing. Where there is a T base, only an A nucleotide will bind, and so on.
- The enzyme DNA polymerase joins the new nucleotides to each other by strong covalent phosphodiester bonds, forming the sugar-phosphate backbone. This enzyme is enormously complex and contains 18 subunits.
- A winding enzyme winds the new strands up to form double helices.
- The two new molecules are identical to the old molecule.

Protein synthesis

- Involves the following stages:

1. Transcription - RNA Synthesis

- DNA never leaves the nucleus, but proteins are synthesised in the cytoplasm, so a copy of each gene is made to carry the “message” from the nucleus to the cytoplasm.
- This copy is mRNA, and the process of copying is called transcription.

- The start of each gene on DNA is marked by a special sequence of bases called the promoter.
- The RNA molecule is built up from the four ribose nucleotides (A, C, G and U) in the nucleoplasm.
- The nucleotides attach themselves to the bases on the DNA by complementary base pairing, just as in DNA replication. However, only one strand of RNA is made.
- The DNA strand that is copied is called the template or sense strand because it contains the sequence of bases that codes for a protein. The other strand is just a complementary copy, and is called the non-template or antisense strand.
- The new nucleotides are joined to each other by strong covalent phosphodiester bonds by the enzyme RNA polymerase.

- Only about 8 base pairs remain attached at a time, since the mRNA molecule peels off from the DNA as it is made. A winding enzyme rewinds the DNA.
- The initial mRNA, or primary transcript, contains many regions that are not needed as part of the protein code. These are called introns (for interruption sequences), while the parts that are needed are called exons (for expressed sequences). All eukaryotic genes have introns, and they are usually longer than the exons.
- The introns are cut out and the exons are spliced together by enzymes. Some of this splicing is done by the RNA intron itself, acting as an RNA enzyme. The recent discovery of these RNA enzymes, or ribozymes, illustrates what a diverse and important molecule RNA is. Other splicing is performed by RNA/protein complexes called snurps.
- The result is a shorter mature RNA containing only exons. The introns are broken down.
- The mRNA diffuses out of the nucleus through a nuclear pore into the cytoplasm.

2. Translation.

- messenger / mRNA attaches to ribosome (small unit);
- many ribosome/polyribosomes bind to same mRNA;
- carries codons / triplet of bases each coding for one amino acid;
- transfer / tRNA each have specific anticodon;
- triplet of bases for specific amino acid;
- tRNA carries specific amino acid;
- tRNA binds to ribosomes;
- to corresponding triplet base / codon;
- a second tRNA binds to next codon;
- two amino acids bind together;
- in a peptide linkage;
- first tRNA detaches;
- ribosome moves along mRNA;
- another tRNA binds to next codon;
- continues until polypeptide / protein formed to stop codon;
- stop codon has no corresponding tRNA/amino acid / causes release of polypeptide;

Translation - Protein Synthesis

1. A ribosome attaches to the mRNA at an initiation codon (AUG). The ribosome encloses two codons.
2. met-tRNA diffuses to the ribosome and attaches to the mRNA initiation codon by complementary base pairing.
3. The next amino acid-tRNA attaches to the adjacent mRNA codon (leu in this case).
4. The bond between the amino acid and the tRNA is cut and a peptide bond is formed between the two amino acids. This operation is catalysed by an rRNA-protein complex called a ribozyme.
5. The ribosome moves along one codon so that a new amino acid-tRNA can attach. The free tRNA molecule leaves to collect another amino acid. The cycle repeats from step 3.
6. The polypeptide chain elongates one amino acid at a time, and peels away from the ribosome, folding up into a protein as it goes. This continues for hundreds

of amino acids until a stop codon is reached, when the ribosome falls apart, releasing the finished protein.

3. Post-Translational Modification

- In eukaryotes, proteins often need to be altered before they become fully functional. Because this happens after translation, it is called post-translational modification.
- Modifications are carried out by other enzymes and include: chain cutting, adding methyl or phosphate groups to amino acids, or adding sugars (to make glycoproteins) or lipids (to make lipoproteins).

- Outline Mendelian laws of inheritance
 - Determine genotype and phenotype ratios
 - Outline types of gene expressions
 - Describe effects of environment on gene expression
 - Describe the importance of gene expression
 - Describe types of mutations
-
- Inheritance is a process in which the material is passed from the parents to the off-springs.
 - In sexual reproduction the fusion of male and female gametes results in transfer of DNA from parents
 - A **gene** is a sequence of nucleotide on the DNA strand which codes for a certain peptide chain. It's also referred as a unit of inheritance.
 - An **allele** is an alternative form of the same gene responsible for determining, construction of characteristics. e.g. an allele for black skin color and an allele for white skin color.
 - A **dominant allele** is an allele which influences the appearance of the phenotype presence of an alternative allele. It suppose of expression of a recessive allele. It is represented by capital letters.
 - A **recessive allele** which influence the appearance of the phenotype only in the presence of the other identical allele. It will not express itself in the presence of the alternative allele of the same gene.
 - A **phenotype** is the outward appearance of an organism or the external expression of a gene or genotype e.g. black white etc.
 - A **genotype** is the genetic constitution of an organism with respect to alleles under consideration e.g. BB, Bb, bb.
 - A **locus** is the position of an allele in the DNA molecule.
 - **Homozygous** is a diploid condition in which the alleles at a given locus are identical e.g. BB or bb.
 - **Heterozygous** is a diploid condition in which the alleles at a given locus are different e.g. Bb.
 - A **first filial** generation (**F1**) these are off-springs produced by crossing parental genotypes of organism.
 - A **second filial** generation (**F2**) these are produced by crossing the parents from the **F1** generation.

MANDALIAN FIRST LAW OF SEGREGATION

- In one of Gregor Mandel's experiments he crossed pure breeding pea plants which are tall and short. Cross pollination was presented and the F1 were all tall and no short plants were produced. He intercrossed the F1 ones to produce the F2 generation. On counting these 787 were tall plants, 277 were short.
- This is a ratio of 3:1 Mandel made the following conclusions:
- There were no intermediate plants in F1 and F2 generation, this indicated that inheritance is not a process in which parental features are blended. It is a process in which definite features which may show themselves in F2 generation only, this implied that the F1 were carrying the allele

for shortness were being suppressed. All the F1 were tall and this indicated that the allele for tallness was dominant and the allele for shortness was recessive.

THE GENETIC DIAGRAM

Let **T** represent the allele for dominant tallness. And **t** represents the recessive allele for shortness.

Back cross test or **test cross** is then done by intercrossing the parents from F1 generation.

TEST 1 BACK CROSS TECHNIQUE

- An organism showing dominant characteristics can have two possible genotypes, A tall plant can have either homozygous or heterozygous tall. The phenotype will be the same but the genotype is different and is determined by crossing the plant with the recessive organism.
- By crossing this organism with the unknown genotype with homozygous recessive it is possible to determine the unknown or dominant characteristics genotype e.g. tall pea plant

- If half the off-springs are tall and the other half is short this implies that the unknown genotype is heterozygous tall.

MANDEL'S LAW OF SEGREGATION

- It states *that the characteristics of organisms are determined by internal factors which occur in pairs and only one of the pair of such a pair is represented in a single gamete.* The internal factors are the genes.
- This law's explanation is obtained from meiosis, the alleles are located on one of the two homologous chromosomes and during meiosis the homologous chromosomes come together and they segregate into different gametes. Each gamete only receives one of each type of chromosome and it also receives one of the pair of alleles.

CODOMINANCE

- It is a condition in which two or more alleles fail to show complete dominance or recessiveness to each other. This causes the alleles to show equally their effects on the phenotype.
- This is due to the failure of one of the alleles to be dominant in the heterozygous condition. Co dominance is found in both plants and animals.

- The heterozygous has a phenotype which is intermediate between homozygous dominant and recessive condition produced by crossing pure breeding black and splashed white fowls.
- A cross between pure breeds of **red** and **white** cows produces an intermediate color called **ROAN**.
- The presence of the black plumage is the result of possession of an allele for black pigment melanin. Splashed white fowls also lack this melanin. Heterozygous show a partial development of this melanin which produces a blue sheen in the plumage.

- If the F1 generation intercrossed, the F2 generation shows the modification of the Normal Mendelian F2 phenotypic monohybrid ratios of **3:1**
- A phenotypic ratio of **1:2:1** is product of alleles which are **codominant**.

DIHYBRID INHERITANCE

- Is concerned with the inheritance of two pairs of alleles consider the following example;
- Pea plants can produce the seeds which are round and wrinkled, Also they can be green and yellow. One pure breed produce seeds that are round and yellow seeds while one pure breed produces round and yellow seeds while the other pure breed wrinkled and green seeds.

Let **R** the dominant allele for round seeds and **r** for wrinkled.

Let **Y** be the dominant allele for yellow seeds and **y** for green.

Parental phenotype: Round and Yellow x Wrinkled and green

Parental genotype:

Meiosis:

Gametes :

Using PANNET'S square

	Ry	Ry	Ry	Ry
ry	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy
ry	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy
ry	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy
ry	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy	RrYy

Genotypic ratio:

1: 2 : 2 : 4

Phenotypic ratio:

9:3:3:1

- Basing on the results of the dihybrid cross therefore the presence of new combinations of characteristics. **Mandel postulated his second law** known as “**the principle of independent assortment**”. *On one pair of characteristics may combine with either one.* The typical dihybrid ratio of **9:3:3:1** only apply to characteristics controlled by genes and different chromosome are said to be **linked**, they form a **linkage group**.

THE SUMMARY OF MENDEL'S 2nd LAW.

- *Orientations on the equatorial spindle of bivalents during metaphase 1 and of chromosome in metaphase 2 are random. The subsequent separation of these chromosomes during anaphase 1 and 2 respectively produces new alleles recombination in gamete cells.*
- *Alignment of chromosome B on the equator is independent of chromosome A; BB is above bb and therefore moves together with AA; resultant cell AABB; BB is below therefore moves with aa. resultant cell BBaa.*
- This is called **independent assortment** and results in the random assortment of maternal and paternal chromosomes between daughter nuclei.
- **This is the basis of Mendel's second law.**

TRY TO CARRY OUT THIS CROSS

Pure-breeding pea plants with round, yellow seeds were crossed with pure-breeding pea plants with wrinkled, green seeds. The offspring all had round, yellow seeds. These seeds were grown and the resultant plants allowed to self-pollinate.

This produced 1112 offspring with the following characteristics.

630 round, yellow seeds
202 round, green seeds
216 wrinkled, yellow seeds
64 wrinkled, green seeds

(a) Using the symbols **R** for round, **r** for wrinkled, **B** for yellow and **b** for green, draw a genetic diagram to explain these results.

Gene expressions/ interaction

- Refers to the manner in which genes control the phenotypic expression of various characters in an organism. Alleles of the gene may interact with one another in a number of ways to produce variability in their phenotypic expression
- Gene interaction can be based on dominance relations such as
 - Complete dominance
 - Co-dominance
 - Partial incomplete dominance
 - Over dominance

Complete dominance

- This is when allele completely masks the effects of the other allele at the same gene locus so that heterozygote has the same phenotype as the dominant homozygote
- E.g in a garden pea, round seed shape is completely dominant over wrinkled

Incomplete dominance

- Heterozygote exhibits a phenotype intermediate to the homozygote
- E.g in *Mirabilis jalapa* (four 'O' clock plant) a partially dominant allele 'R' produces red flower in homozygous state, while its recessive allele 'r' produced white flower in homozygous state. When a red (RR) flower type plant is crossed with a white (rr) flower type plant, the hybrid (Rr) has pink flowers.

Red x White

Co-dominance

- Both the alleles of a gene are expressed in the phenotype and the heterozygote has the characters of both parents. The coat colour of short horned breed of cattle presents an example of co-dominance.

- Roan colour is that which has patches of red and white colours.

Over dominance

- A phenotype relation in which the phenotypic expression of the heterozygote is greater than that of either homozygote.
Aa > AA or aa
- In many cross-pollinated species, crossing of inbred lines produced progeny far superior to their inbred parents. This is heterosis or hybrid vigour.

Interaction of genes with the environment and impact on gene expression

- Genes interact with the environment to produce the final phenotypic expression. The environment can either be external environment or internal environment (hereditary)

External environment

1. Light

- Light provides energy for plant growth. Seedlings grown in the dark will appear as albinos because they do not develop chlorophyll. The gene for chlorophyll production are present but cannot be expressed in the absence of light.

2. Temperature

- Influence rates of chemical reactions in living organisms. In primrose plants, red flower colour is produced at room temperature (25°C) but white flowers are produced at temperatures above 33°C. There are genes whose phenotype expression depends on the temperature.

3. Moisture

- Water is required for all metabolic processes. Shortage of water affects the growth of both plants and animals

4. Diseases

- As a result of diseases only the strongest individuals survive. These animals or plant develop partial or complete immunity to diseases.

5. Nutrition

- Sufficient food enables the animal to grow properly while insufficient food or an unbalanced diet causes underdevelopment.

Internal environment

1. Age

- Plays an important role on the expression of genes. In plants, flowering takes place at a certain time in the growth of a plant. The genes for flowering are there at the beginning of the plant's life. The internal environment created by the plant at a certain age induces flowering.

2. Sex

3. Hormones

TOPIC 5: PRINCIPLES OF CROP PROTECTION

SUB TOPIC: WEED, PEST AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT

Weeds

- Outline the socio- economic importance of weeds
- Identify weeds
- Classify weeds
- Describe mechanisms that make weeds persistent
- Explain the mechanisms of crop-weed competition

Weed is a plant that grows where it is not wanted, includes whatever plant. It can be a broad leaved or narrow leaved or poisonous

Socio-economic importance of weeds (Disadvantages of weeds)

- **Reduction in crop yield:** Weeds compete for water, nutrients & light. Being hardy & vigorous in growth habit, they soon outgrow the crops & consume large amounts of water & nutrients, thus causing heavy losses in yield. e.g.: 40% reduction in yield of groundnut & 66% reduction in yield of chilli. The loss of N through weeds is about 150 kg/ha.
- **Increase in the cost of cultivation and control:** One of the objects of tillage is to control weed on which 30% expenditure is incurred and this may increase more in heavy infested areas & also cost on weed control by weeding or chemical control. Hence, reduce margin of net profit.
- **Reduction in the quality of field produce:** Weed seeds get harvested & threshed along the crop produce which lowers the quality. Such produce fetches fewer prices in the market. e.g.: Leafy vegetables, grain crop.
- **Reduction in quality of livestock produce:** Weeds impart an undesirable flavor to the milk (Ghaneri), impair quality of wool of sheep (Gokhuru, Aghada), and cause death of animals due to poisonous nature of seed (Dhatura).
- **Harbour insect-pests & disease pathogens:** Weeds either give shelter to various insect pests & disease pathogens or serve as alternate hosts & thus helps in perpetuating the menace from pests & diseases. e.g.: Gall fly of paddy, midge fly of Jowar, leaf minor of soybean & Groundnut, rust of Wheat, tikka of Groundnut, Black rust of wheat, Downey mildew (*Saccharum spontaneum*).
- **Check the flow of water in irrigation channels:** Weeds block drainage & check the flow of water in irrigation canals & field channels thereby increasing the seepage losses as well as losses through over flowing, so reduce the irrigation efficiency.
- **Secretions are harmful:** Heavy growth of certain weeds like quack grass (*Agropyron repens*) or lavalala lowers the germination & reduce the growth of many crop plants due to presence of certain phytotoxins secreted by weeds.

- **Harmful to human beings and animals:** Weeds cause irritation of skin allergy & poisoning to human beings, also death of castles.
- **Cause quicker wear & tear of farm implements:** Being hardy & deep rooted; the tillage implements get worn out early & cannot work efficiently unless they are properly sharpened or mended.
- **Reduce value of the lands:** Heavily infested lands with perennial weeds fetch less price as require heavy expenditure to bring under cultivation.

Benefits aspects of weeds / advantages derived from weeds

- Weeds when ploughed under, add nutrients, organic matter.
- Weeds check winds or water erosion by soil binding effect of their roots (undirkani). **iii.** Useful as fodder for castles (Hariyali) & vegetable by human beings (Ghol, Tandulja).
- Have medicinal value, *Leucas aspera* is used against snake bite, oil of satyanashi seed is useful against skin diseases, nuts of lavalala are used in making scents (Udabattis/Incense sticks).
- Have economic importance e.g.: *saccharum spp* used for making thatches.
- Reclamation of alkali lands (Satyanashi). **vii.** Serve as ornamental plants (Ghaneri). **viii.** Used for fencing (Cactus, Nagphana).
- Used as mulch to check the evaporation losses of water from soil. **x.** Used as green manuring & composting.
- Fix atmospheric Nitrogen (Blue green algae, Tarota, Unhali, etc.)

Classification of weeds

Weeds are classified

1. **Based on morphology**
2. **Based on life cycle**
3. **Based on habitat**
4. **Based on origin**
5. **Based on nature of stem**

Classification based on morphology/ cotyledon characters

- During 1940 2,4-D was discovered and it was a selective translocated herbicide. After the discovery of the herbicide, classification based on morphology has got strong recognition as it controlled broad leaved weeds.
- The morphological classification is most important and useful in weed control. Morphological characters of plant are closely related to herbicidal absorption, retention, & translocation.
- The weeds belonging to the same group are likely to have same kind of response to specific herbicides or cultural or mechanical methods.
- This is the most widely used classification by the weed scientists. So, weeds are generally divided into three groups
 - 1) **Grasses**
 - 2) **Sedges**
 - 3) **Broad leaved weeds**

Based on cotyledon characters they are classified into

Monocots

1. Narrow and upright leaves
2. Parallel venation
3. Retention of herbicide is less
4. Adventitious root system
5. Growing point is open
6. Cambium (conductive tissue) is scattered

Eg Grasses or narrow leaved weeds

Dicots

1. Broad & horizontal leaves
2. Reticulate venation
3. Retention of herbicide is more
4. Tap root system.
5. Growing point is open
6. Conductive tissue intact

Eg: Dicots

Amaranthus spp.
Chenopodium album
Convolvulus arvensis
Phyllanthus niruri
Parthenium hysterophorus
Xanthium strumarium

Classification based on habitat / situation

- Depending upon the place of their occurrence they are classified into **terrestrial** and **aquatic weeds**. Terrestrial weeds are again classified into
 1. Crop land weeds: weeds in field. Eg. Echinochloa in rice.
 2. Non-crop land weeds: weeds in waste lands Eg. Tribulus terrestris, Xanthium strumarium.
 3. Grass land weeds: Eg. Vernonia and Rumex spp.
 - 1) 3. Weeds of lawns & public parks Eg Lippia nodiflora and Eleusine indica.
 3. Orchard or garden weeds Eg. Euphorbia geniculata, Imperata Cylindrica , Acalypha indica.
 5. Weeds of plantation crops Eg. Eupatorium spp. Makania micrantha
 6. Parasitic weeds Eg. Loranthus.
 7. Road side weeds Eg. Euphorbia , Lantana camera , Hyptis and Prosopis juliflora
- **Aquatic weeds**; They are classified into
 - 1) Sub merged weeds Eg Hydrilla Verticillata, Utricularia stellaris.
 - 2) Emerged weeds Eg Typha Spp Nelambium speciosum.
 - 3) Floating weeds Eg Eichhornia crassipes, Pistia stratiotes .

Classification based on origin

- **Indigenous weeds**: All the native weeds of the country are coming under this group and most of the weeds are indigenous. Eg. Acalypha indica, Abutilon indicum, Sorghum halepense, Cynodon dactylon and Echinochloa colonum
- **Introduced or Exotic weeds or Alein**: These are the weeds introduced from other countries. These weeds are normally troublesome and control becomes difficult. Eg. Parthenium hysterophorus, Acanthospermum hispidum, Eichhornia crassipes, Argemone mexicana, Lantana camara and Croton bonplandianus When man aids in its introduction such Weeds are called as anthropytes.

Classification based on nature of stem

- Depending upon development of bark tissue on their stems and branches weeds are classified into woody, semi-woody and herbaceous weeds.

- **Woody weeds:** Weeds include shrubs and under shrubs and are collectively called brush weeds. *Lantana camera*, *Prosopis juliflora* (mesquite) *Zizyphus rotundifolia* (wild plum) are examples for brush weeds.

Semi-woody weeds: *Croton sparsiflorus* is semi woody weed.

Herbaceous weeds: Weeds have green, succulent stems are of most common occurrence around us. Eg. *Amaranthus viridis* and *Chenopodium album*.

Classification based on life cycle / ontogeny

- Based on life span (ontogeny), weeds are classified as annual, biennial and perennial weeds.
 1. **Annuals-** Completes its life cycle within one year or one season and propagate by seeds. They may be Kharif annuals, winter annuals and summer annuals
 2. **Biennials** - Complete their life cycle within two years/ two seasons, 1st year vegetative growth – Rosette stage. 2nd year produced inflorescence called bolting. They may propagate either by seeds or vegetative parts or by both. Biennials generally do not come up in annual crop fields but they infest perennial crop fields, pastures, lawns and orchards. Eg. *Daucus carota*, *Cirsium vulgare*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Taraxacum stricta*, *Alternanthera echinata* but *Cichorium intybus* bolts every year
 3. **Perennials**
 1. They have an indefinite life period ranging from a few years to many years. They do not die after reproduction.
 2. Some have herbaceous stems which die back to the soil surface every year in winter so that they resume growth from the crown or taproot in spring.
 3. Trees and shrubs are other examples of perennials which add new growth every year from woody stems. Some plants are perennials in climate and annual in another.
 4. Examples of such crops are castor beans, sorghum and cotton. These can grow for several years in tropical regions but tend to be killed by frost. Other perennials include sugar cane and forage crops.

Describe mechanisms that make weeds persistent (Characteristics of weeds)

- The weed seeds germinate early and the seedlings grow faster. They being hardy, compete for light, moisture and nutrients.
- They flower earlier, run to seed in profusion and mature ahead of the crop. They are difficult to control and it may be even impossible to eradicate some weeds completely.
- They are non-useful, unwanted & undesirable.
- They are harmful to crops, cattle and human beings.
- They can thrive even under adverse conditions of soil, climate, etc.
- They are prolific and have a very high reproduction capacity. e.g.: A plant of satyanashi (*Argemone mexicana*) produces over 5000 seeds while a plant of striga produces over half a million seeds.
- Viability of weed seeds remains intact, even if they are buried deep in the soil. In some cases, the seeds may remain viable even after passing through the digestive tract of the animals.
- The seeds may have special structures like wings, spines, hooks, sticky hair, etc. on account of which they can be easily disseminated over long distances.
- Many weeds like *Cynodon dactylon* are vegetatively propagated and spread rapidly all over the field even under adverse conditions.

Crop-weed competition

- **Competition** is struggle between two organisms for a limited resource that is essential for growth. Water, nutrient, light and space are the major factors for which usually competition occurs. Competition between crop plants and weeds is most severe when they have similar vegetative habit and common demand for available growth factors.
- Weeds appear much more adapted to agro-ecosystems than our crop plants. Without interference by man, weeds would easily wipe out the crop plants. Generally, an increase in one kilogram of weed growth will decrease one kilogram of crop growth.

Principles of crop weed competition are

1.Competition for nutrients

- It is an important aspect of crop weed competition. Weeds usually absorb mineral nutrients faster than crop plants.
- Usually weeds accumulate relatively larger amounts of nutrients than crop plant Nutrient removal by weeds leads to huge loss of nutrients in each crop season, which is often twice that of crop plants.
- Amaranthus accumulate over 3 % nitrogen in their dry matter and this fall under category of nitrophylls. Digetaria spp accumulates more phosphorous content of over 3.36%. Chenopodium and *Portulaca* are potassium lovers, with over 4.0% K₂O in their dry matter.
- *Setaria lutescens* accumulates as high as 585 ppm of zinc in its dry matter. This is about three times more than by cereal crop.

2.Competition for moisture

- Crop weed competition becomes critical with increasing soil moisture stress. In general for producing equal amount of dry matter weeds transpire more water than field crops.
- Therefore, the actual evapotranspiration from the weedy crop fields is much more than the evapotranspiration from a weed free crop field.
- Consumptive use of Chenopodium album is 550mm as against 479mm for wheat crop. Further it was noted that weeds remove moisture evenly from up to 90 cm soil depth. While the major uptake of moisture by wheat was limited to top 15 cm of soil depth.
- Weeds growing in fallow land are found to consume as much as 70- 120 ha mm of soil moisture and this moisture is capable of producing 15 -20 q of grain per ha in the following season.

3.Competition for light (Solar energy)

- Plant height and vertical leaf area distribution are the important elements of crop weed competition.
- When moisture and nutrients in soil are plentiful, weeds have an edge over crop plants and grow taller.
- Competition for light occurs during early crop growth season if a dense weed growth smothers the crop seedlings.
- Crop plants suffer badly due to shading effect of weeds. Cotton, potato several vegetables and sugarcane are subjected to heavy weed growth during seedling stage.
- Unlike competition for nutrients and moisture once weeds shade a crop plant, increased light intensity cannot benefit it.

4.Competition for space (CO₂)

- Crop-weed competition for space is the requirement for CO₂ and the competition may occur under extremely crowded plant community condition.
- A more efficient utilization of CO₂ by C₄ type weeds may contribute to their rapid growth over C₃ type of crops.

Critical period of crop-weed competition

- The period at which maximum crop weed competition occurs called critical period.
- It is the shortest time span in the ontogeny of crop when weeding results in highest economic returns.
- **Factors affecting weed-crop interference or critical period of crop weed competition:**
 1. Period of weed growth.
 2. Weeds / crop density.
 3. Plant species effects. a) Weed species b) Crop species and Varieties.
 4. Soil and climatic influence.
 - a) Soil fertility
 - b) Soil moisture status
 - c) Soil reaction:
 - d) Climatic influences.
 5. Cropping practices.
 - a) Time and method of planting crops
 - b) Method of planting of Crops
 - c) Crop density and rectangularity.

Pest

- Outline the socio-economic importance of pests
- Identify pests
- Classify pests according to feeding habits
- Describe the life cycle of pests
 - Complete and incomplete metamorphosis
 - vivipary

Pest damage

- Pests can cause plant damage in different ways. This can be through biting and chewing, piecing and sucking and can be vectors of pathogens.

Classification of Pests

1. Biting and chewing Pests

- These are insects which feed by biting pieces of plant material and chewing. Very good examples of such pests are: locusts, crickets, caterpillars and beetles.

Damage caused by biting and chewing pests

Losses in plant yield can be brought about in different ways by biting and chewing pests as indicated below:

- During feeding some pests produce substances which irritate the host plant leading to proliferation and gall formation.
- Loss of photosynthesis tissue due to the eating away of the leaf lamina of the plant and leaf drop, e.g. by leaf worm
- There is destruction of seedlings and young plants, e.g. vegetable seedlings can be destroyed by cutworm.
- Feeding of pests from the growing points lead to the destruction of buds and shoots e.g. the bud worm in tobacco.
- Some pests feed by boring and tunneling the stems interfering with the movement of sap up and down the plant and weakening of the plant, e.g. maize stalk borer in maize.
- During feeding the pests destroy flowers, seed and fruits there by significantly reducing fruit production, e.g. cape mounted rifle beetle in sugar bean.
- Tubers and roots can be bored or eaten by pests in the soil leading to reduced yields, e.g. potato tuber moth in potatoes.

2. Piercing and sucking Pests

- Pests in this category have part or all of the mouthparts modified into piercing proboscis.
- They suck sap from the xylem or phloem tissues of the plant.
- Examples of such pests are from the order Acarina, homoptera and thrips.

Pests that are vectors of pathogens

- These are insects that transmit diseases to plants making them important to agriculture.
- Examples are fruit fly which transmits tobacco and cotton leaf curl viruses, aphids transmits groundnut mosaic virus, and leaf hopper which transmits maize streak virus.
- It is important to note that very low populations of disease vectors can lead to serious crop damage.

Pests life cycles

- Pests go through different developmental stages during their life. Some go through complete metamorphosis and some incomplete metamorphosis.
- With most insects growth is limited to immature stages.
- Insects develop from stage to stage and the change from one stage to the next is through moulting (ecdysis).
- The change in appearance of the insect due to moulting is referred to as **metamorphosis**.

Complete metamorphosis

- In complete metamorphosis insects go through the four stages of development which are as in the figure 4 below.

Fig 4 Complete metamorphosis

- (Reproduction dispersal and Sometimes feeding)
- The four stages are mostly exhibited by holometabola insects like the American boll worm (*Heliothis armigera*), maize stalk borer (*Bassiola fusca*).
- In the complete metamorphosis group of pests there are four instars, a modified larval or pupal instar and the adult phase.

Incomplete metamorphosis

- In this case insects go through three stages of development which are: as illustrated in the in the figure 5 below.

Fig 5 Incomplete metamorphosis

- Insects falling under this group belong to the Homimetabola.
- In incomplete metamorphosis group of pests, wings appear as external wing pads in the second instar and they are fully formed after the fifth moult e.g. grass hoppers and locusts.

Diseases

- Outline the socio-economic importance of diseases
- Classify diseases into bacterial; fungal and viral
- Describe signs and symptoms of diseases
- Describe mode of transmission of diseases

Powdery mildew of field beans (FUNGUS)

- Caused by fungus
- E.g *Erysiphine pisi*

Signs and symptoms

- Infected plants are covered with a white powdery film;
- Severely affected foliage turns blue-white in colour;
- Tissue below these infected areas may turn purple;

- Stunted growth / death of plant may occur.
- Severe pod infection can cause a grey brown discolouration of the seeds

Transmission

- Spores from the pathogen are carried by wind to other plants
- Seed-borne

Disease management

- Varietal selection
- Crop rotation
- Seed treatment
- Foliar fungicides with fungicides

Maize Streak Virus (MSV)

- Caused by a virus.

Transmission

- It is mainly transmitted by *Cicadulina mbila* (maize leaf hopper) vector.
- The leaf hopper have sucking mouth parts that enable them penetrate the plant cells by use of salivary and gut enzymes.

Signs and symptoms

- Stunting of severely infected maize plants
- Pale spots form on leaf that become longer streaks that eventually coalesce.
- Fully elongated leaves develop a chlorosis with broken yellow streaks along the vein, contrasting with dark green colour of normal foliage.

Control strategy

- Remove previous crop residues
- Avoid downwind planting of the crop
- Plant maize in an open area to avoid shade as leafhoppers prefer shade
- Plant early to avoid the optimal temperature for vector multiplication and subsequent transmission of the virus.
- Chemical insecticides can be effective in control of the vector e.g imidacloprid
- Use of certified seed.

Bacterial Blight

- Caused by a bacteria
- E.g *Pseudomonas savastanoi*

Symptoms

- Brown spots on the margins of the cotyledons
- Young plants may be stunted and if the infection reaches the growing point, they may die.
- The centers of the spot will turn a dark reddish-brown and dry out,
- Lesions can also occur on the pods causing the seeds to become shriveled and discoloured.

Transmission

- Wind / splashing water droplets

Disease control

- Genetic resistance
- Crop rotation
- Limit cultivation to times when the foliage is dry

TOPIC 6: CROP PRODUCTION

SUB TOPIC: AGRONOMIC PRINCIPLES

Agro- ecological zones

- Explain the basis of dividing Zimbabwe into agro-ecological zones.
- Drawing and identifying agro-ecological zones on the map of Zimbabwe
- Design suitable cropping programmes for each agro-ecological zones.

Natural region – a relatively large area where land use is common throughout and the agricultural activities are conditioned by one or a few natural characteristics.

Diversified farming – a system with several lines of production not directly interlinked

The basis of dividing Zimbabwe into agro-ecological zones

- Decide on a broader system of farming best suited to the section of the region
- Match the existing conditions (soil, climate, socio-economic) to specific crops.
- Assess potential arable land suitable for production of various crops
- Assess the stock carrying capacity of natural pastures
- Classify soils and assess their potential for crop production
- Evaluate farming patterns that exist, and the economic factors that affect them

KEY FEATURES OF ZIMBABWE

- High watershed area; 1200 -1500m above sea level this provides the main catchment area for the major tributaries of Zambezi, Limpopo and Save Valley it also divides the country into 2 lowlands the main river valleys; the Zambezi, Limpopo, Save and Mazowe
- the low lying areas of the Zambezi and Limpopo valleys have a tropical climate but the uplands have sub tropical climate the Eastern Highlands
- altitude 2200 – 2600 above sea level highest parts in the country
- the different altitudes and relief features determine their climate and agricultural activities

Natural Farming Regions of Zimbabwe

Natural Region I – Specialised and Diversified Farming

- Characterised by specialised and diversified farming under intensive systems
- Specialised products e.g timber (wattle), silviculture, plantation crops (tea and coffee), seed potato
- Diversified – several farming activities are undertaken – crop production (potato, apples, tea, coffee) ,dairying, timber.
- Mean annual rainfall - >1000mm
- Mean annual temperature (T0C) – 180C

- Region has more than 18 wet (rainy) pentads per year
- Covers 1.6% of the country area
- Located in Manicaland, Eastern Border areas.

Natural Region II – Intensive Farming

- Intensive farming due to high and reliable rainfall
- Irrigation is only supplementary e.g on early planted tobacco
- Sub-divided into IIa and IIb basing on rainfall reliability (rainfall more reliable in IIa)
- Farming activities not as diversified as in NRI
- Characterized by cash and food crop production
- Mean annual rainfall – 700 to 1000mm
- Region has more than 16 - 18 wet (rainy) pentads per year
- Covers 18.8% of the country area

Natural Region III – Semi-intensive Farming

- Characterized by mid-season dry spells
- Production of drought tolerant crops
- Supplementary irrigation in summer is common practice
- Production of short season varieties or drought tolerant varieties advised
- Mean annual rainfall – 650 to 800mm
- Less reliable rainfall than NRII
- Region has more than 14 - 16 wet (rainy) pentads per year
- Covers 17.6% of the country area

Natural Region IV – Semi-extensive Farming

- Semi-extensive beef production is recommended
- Characterized by mid-season dry spells
- Production of drought tolerant crops also recommended
- Fodder crop production
- Unreliable rainfall
- Mean annual rainfall – 450 to 650mm
- Region has less than 14 wet (rainy) pentads per year
- Covers 33% of the country area

Natural Region V – Extensive Farming

- Extensive beef production and wildlife management
- Ranching based on veld alone
- Characterised by ‘sweet veld’
- Very unreliable rainfall, erratic
- Production of drought tolerant crops, fodder crops under irrigation is recommended
- Mean annual rainfall – <400mm
- Region has less than 10 wet (rainy) pentads per year
- Covers 29% of the country area

A new farmer allocated land in natural farming region 3 has approached you for advice [a] describe the climatic characteristics of the location {5}

- high summer temperatures
- temperature range between 25-35C
- summer mostly experience dry spells especially January
- summer is the rain season
- rainfall amount 650 to 800mm
- 14 to 15 pentads
- It experience winter from May to August
- august is wind and cold
- frost occurrence in winter
- Frequencies of drought.

Discuss the factor to consider when choosing suitable maize or sorghum varieties for different agro-ecological zones of Zimbabwe

- Amount of rainfall
- rainfall distribution and reliability
- effectiveness of rainfall
- the occurrence of mid-season droughts
- days to maturity of the cultivar
- temperature
- drought
- relief
- soil type
- disease consideration
- Season length, season quality
- season onset
- plant stature
- canopy or leaf characteristics
- root density or root to shoot ratio
- pest prevalence
- target plant population
- yield potential of variety

discuss why yield of soyabeans or ground nuts is lower in small holder farming areas [10]

- do not practice soil analysis
- lack of skilled labour
- practise mixed farming/cultivation (do not focus on one enterprise at a time)
- lack knowledge ploughing depth of soya beans
- raw spacing 50-90cm. usually plant at greater plant population
- rarely practice crop rotations
- lack funds to buy pesticides & herbicides

Outline the problems faced by small holder independent farmers in maize production.(10)

- lack of capital for inputs e.g fertilizer , seeds , pesticides ,etc
- poor technology and inadequate equipment .
- Lack of skill in diseases identification and control (pest and diseases)
- Low prices at the market.

- losses during temporary storage.
- Incorrect fertilizer type, rates and application.
- Early or late harvesting.
- Lack of irrigation schemes to supplement rainfall in times of drought or in areas which receive inadequate water supply e.g region 3 .
- There is late land preparation due to lack of drought power.

Discuss factors that affect population densities in maize. (6)

- Rainfall distribution
- nutrient availability
- available space
- variety/ cultivar
- soil structure
- availability of inputs
- type of labour used

What problems would you associate with high plant densities? (3)

- Competition for nutrients, water, sunlight, space.
- There is spread of pests and diseases.
- Working will be difficult in the field.
- They discourage the use of machinery.

A new farmer allocated land in natural farming region 3 has approached you for advice.

(i). Describe the characteristics of the location of the farm. (5)

- It receives rainfall between 650 to 800 mm per year with 14-16 pentads.
- Higher summer temperatures between 25-35 degrees.
- Frost occurrence in winter .
- There is also wind in August to September and there is frequent drought.

(ii). Suggest a suitable cropping program for one calendar year. (10)

Summer

- Grow long season varieties when early rains are expected /under irrigation.
- Medium to early season varieties /short season varieties are usually recommended.
- Crops like Rapoko, Sorghum, Sunflower and Maize and sunflower are usually recommended
- beans/potatoes can be grown under irrigation

Winter

- winter wheat under irrigation/ also maize under irrigation
- field beans, flowering should not coincide with frost
- potatoes can be grown under irrigation
- pasture crop can be grown under irrigation
- dry land preparation for the next summer
- winter ploughing, clearing of land and drought resistance

Environmental factors affecting irrigation

- rainfall
- temperature
- wind
- relative humidity

- cloud cover
- soil type

Explain how agro-ecological zones influence farmers choice of

- (i) cultivar [3]**
- (ii) time of planting [3]**
- (iii) plant population [3]**

Discuss how agro-ecological zones influence crop production management in Zimbabwe. [20]

Tillage practices

- Distinguish primary from secondary tillage
- Explain the significance of primary and secondary tillage in crop production.

Definitions

- The physical manipulation of soil with tools and implements to result in good tilth for better germination and subsequent growth of crop (Reddy and Reddi, 1992).
- Tillage refers to mechanical manipulations of the soil that provide necessary conditions favourable for the growth of crops. It includes operations and practices that are used for the purpose of modifying the physical character of the soil (Balasubramaniyan and Palaniappan, 2004)
- Those mechanical, soil-stirring actions carried on the soil for the purpose of nurturing crops
- Manual or mechanical soil-stirring actions necessary for the proper establishment and growth of crops.
 - o **Tilth** the physical condition brought about by a tillage operation.

Types of tillage

- **Primary and Secondary tillage** are the two general categories of tillage referring to/ based on depth of tillage, type of implement and goals in preparing a seedbed
- *Two types of tillage can also be identified, based on time (with respect to crop) at which they carried out viz;*
 - i. Preparatory cultivation (seedbed prep): consists of primary tillage, secondary tillage and lay-out of seedbed
 - ii. After cultivation –tillage operations are carried out in the standing crop e.g drilling or side dressing of fertilizers.

Primary tillage:

- It is tillage which cuts, inverts and /or shatters the soil to a depth 15-36 cm. It may bury trash by the inversion and it usually leaves the surface rough.
- It is a more aggressive, relatively deeper operation and implements tend to be heavier and more strongly constructed than for secondary tillage.
- The aims of primary tillage may include:
 1. loosening and aerating the soil surface layer;
 2. incorporating fertilizer

3. covering plant residue from previous crop or mixing the residue into the surface layer of the soil

- Examples of primary tillage implements:
 - Mouldboard ploughs, chisel ploughs
 - Disc ploughs
 - Sub-soilers
 - Chisels
 - Rippers
 - Offset and heavy tandem disc harrows and ploughing discs
 - Rotary tillers

Ploughs:

- These can be classified according to four criteria:
 1. type of plough body (disc or mouldboard)
 2. type of operation (conventional or reversible)
 3. hitching system (trailed, mounted, semi-mounted)
 4. number of plough bodies
- Thus a plough may be called for example; a mounted conventional two-disc plough.or a semi mounted reversible three disc plough.
- Disc or mould board ploughs are used according to the required tilth (soil inversion, uniformity, water conservation and growing conditions are the 4 aspects to be considered), the existing field conditions (two aspects are considered namely obstacles and soil moisture)and the draft and maintenance requirements (these are related to the type of operations of the disc and mouldboard ploughs).
- *Note:* Under normal conditions farmers use a mounted conventional or reversible three disc plough, but in hard conditions(e.g.....), the three disc plough may be changed for a two-disc plough.
- For very powerful tractors, a semi-mounted five or six disc plough can be used.
- Disc ploughs are basically tractor drawn because of their weight and size.

Mould plough (action):

- Cuts slices of soil and inverts them. A layer of soil is separated from the underlying sub-soil and is inverted.. Degree of cover of trash on surface layer depends on depth of ploughing, setting of plough and amount of plant residue.

Chisel plough:

- *It does not plough.* The desired action of the chisel plough is to break and shatter the soil while leaving enough residue on the surface to help control soil erosion.
- *It is a heavy cultivating implement*
- It is also used to breakdown plough pans or *plough soles* caused by mouldboard ploughing at the same depth for years
- Useful in hard conditions and in reclaiming rough lands and orchards
- It is heavy structured

Stubble mulch tiller

- Combines the operations of chiselling and disking. It consists of disk blades and in front to cut and loosen trash and a chisel plough in the rear section to break and shatter the soil

Powered rotary tiller

- Require engine power to rotate the blades for cutting/lifting and loosening the soil. Depth of cut is up to 12-15 cm.
- Effective in chopping and incorporating trash and preparing a fine tilth bed. They are often used for secondary tillage at shallower depths
- Note: excessive use may lead to soil pulverization- limiting water infiltration and increasing the erosion hazard.
- Rotary tillers are suitable for light soils

Sub soilers:

- Used to penetrate the soil deeper than with conventional cultivation machinery.
- There is no soil inversion and this differentiates the practice/process from deep ploughing (where depth of tillage can go beyond that considered adequate for primary tillage. Deep ploughing can be done to invert soil in special circumstances such as sanitation, improvement of soil structure and control of some perennial weeds. It should be done when the soil is completely dry. Depth of ploughing is generally deeper than 50cm).
- Break up relatively impervious layers of soil which have arisen as a result of compaction from tillage operations (movement of heavy machinery or as a result of ploughing at the same depth for a long time). Impervious layers can also form naturally. The impervious layers can limit root growth and nutrient and water holding capacities of soil.
- May have one or more heavy tines which break the through the impervious layer causing a shatter.
- Sub-soiling refers to pulling a chisel type implement through the soil to a depth of 30cm or deeper to shatter impervious layers (Depth of work is approximately 50 cm)
- Sub-soiling should be carried out under very dry conditions or when internal drainage beneath the impervious layer should be good. Sub-soiling is not effective when subsequent tillage operations re-compact the soil

Secondary tillage

- It refers to tillage operations that follow primary tillage and are for the purpose of preparing a final seedbed suitable for planting, seed germination seedling establishment and weed control
- It works the soil to shallower depths -5-15 cm

Aims include:

1. Levelling and firming the soil
2. Further pulverising of the to ensure good seed –soil contact
3. Control

Note: excessive secondary tillage may increase the evaporation of water from the surface layers of soil resulting in sub-optimum moisture levels for proper germination.

Examples of secondary tillage equipment:

Disk harrow

- e.g. tandem disk harrow(can be used for primary tillage depending on size)
- Action: pulverize soil clods, levels and firms soil

Field cultivators (usually have conditioners).

- Resembles chisel plough except that it is lighter constructed and designed for shallower tillage.
- They are widely used for seedbed preparation and weed control.

Spring, spike and tine-tooth harrows

- These implements vary in design but they have similar purpose of levelling, pulverising, firming soil and sometimes weed control.
- They may be operated separately or pulled behind ploughs, disc harrows or field cultivators

Roller packers and roller harrows?

- Can be made from stone, iron or wood
- Implement consists of heavy rollers designed to crush soil clods and the soil surface- good for small-seeded grasses and legumes
- General principle involved is the rotation of massive material round the axle
- It should not be used on wet soils otherwise severe crusting results

Row-crop cultivators

Factors affecting selection of farm machinery

- Maintenance requirement: if not locally available the spares will need to be imported.
- Labour requirement for subsequent operations
- Availability of results from international recognized test methods
- Proof testing
- Potential detrimental /benefits
- Power requirement and compatibility of implements with available tractor.

Plant population

- Calculate plant population per unit area
- Discuss factors that influence plant population
- Discuss implications of plant population in crop production

PLANT POPULATION

- It is correlated with more yields and should be based on soil type.
- However soils have higher water and nutrient holding capacity than sand soils and have high yield potential.
- **The plant population per hectare of a maize crop with a spacing of 90cm × 30cm can be calculated as follows :**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Plant population} &= \frac{\text{Area (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{inrow(m)} \times \text{inter-row(m)}} \\
 &= \frac{10\,000\text{m}^2}{0,3 \times 0,9\text{ m}} \\
 &= 37\,037,04 \\
 &= \underline{\underline{31\,037\text{ plants}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

- General Plant spacing for Maize:

Short season cultivars : 900mm×230mm
 Long season cultivars: 900mm× 300mm

Problem 1. Calculate number of maize plants in one ha area if inter and intra spacing is 60cm and 20 cm, respectively.

$$\text{Number of plants in a given area} = \frac{\text{Given area (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Area required by single plant (m}^2\text{)}}$$

1 ha = 10000 m²

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area required by single plant (m}^2\text{)} &= \text{inter spacing}/100 \times \text{intra spacing}/100 \\ &= 60/100 \times 20/100 \text{ or } 0.6 \times 0.2 \text{ or } 1.2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of plants/ha} &= 10000/1.2 \\ &= 8333.33 \text{ or } 8333 \end{aligned}$$

Problem 2. Calculate number of wheat plants in 400m² area if inter and intra spacing is 22cm and 10cm, respectively.

$$\text{Number of plants in a given area} = \frac{\text{Given area (m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Area required by single plant (m}^2\text{)}}$$

$$\text{Area required by single plant (m}^2\text{)} = \text{inter spacing}/100 \times \text{intra spacing}/100$$

$$\text{Area required by single plant (m}^2\text{)} = \text{inter spacing}/100 \times \text{intra spacing}/100$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of plants} &= 400/0.022 \\ &= 18181.81 \text{ or } 18182 \end{aligned}$$

Calculation of seed rates

$$\text{Seed required (kg)} = \frac{\text{Recommended quantity of crop seed (kg) per ha or square meters}}{\text{Given area in ha or square meters}} \text{ for the area}$$

Crop rotation

- Explain the principles of crop rotation;
 - Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of crop rotation;
 - Design a 4-crop rotation cycle.
- **Crop rotation** refers to recurrent succession of crop on the same piece of land either in a year or over a longer period of time.
 - **The practice of growing different crops one at a time in planned succession on the same piece of land.**
 - Component crops are so chosen so that soil health is not impaired. or it means growing a set of crop in a regular succession on a piece of land in a specific period of time, with an object to get maximum profit least investment without impairing soil fertility.

Characteristics of good crop rotation

- It should be adaptable to the existing soil, climatic and economic factors.

- It should be based on proper land utilization or it should be so arranged in relation to fields that crop yields can be maintained and also build up organic matter content of the soil.
- It should contain sufficient area under soil improving crops (legumes) to maintain and also build up organic matter content of the soil.
- It should provide food grains, pulses, oilseed etc. to family and roughages, fodder to cattle.
- It should help in control of pests, diseases, and weeds.
- It should provide maximum area under the most profitable crops adapted to the area.

Principles of crop rotation

- The crops with tap-root should be followed by those, which have a fibrous root system. This helps in proper and uniform use of nutrients from the soil and roots do not compete with each other for uptake of nutrients.
- A shallow rooted grain crop, deep rooted cash crop and restorative crop (legume crop) should be included in the rotation for providing food, fodder, cash and maintaining the fertility and productivity of soil.
- The leguminous crops should be grown after non-leguminous crops because leguminous fix atmospheric N into soil and more organic matter to soil. Apart from this, legumes need more phosphate and less nitrogen while non- legumes need more of nitrogen and relatively low phosphorus. So nutrient requirements of these crops are different and such combination helps farmers in reducing cost of cultivation.
- More exhaustive crops should be followed by less exhaustive crops because crops like potato, sugarcane, maize, etc. need more inputs such as better tillage, more fertilizer higher number of irrigations, more insecticides, better care than crops like oil seeds, pulses, etc. which need little less care or little less inputs.
- Two or three crops are taken in a year on same land under irrigated conditions. However, a dry crop should be included in the rotation to avoid damage to the soil due to continuous irrigation.
- In case of rainfed farming on moisture retentive soils after harvest of Kharif crop some minor crop requiring less moisture like pulses or cereals may be grown. e.g. Rice (Kharif)-Gram/Wal (Rabi), Green gram or black gram-Rabi sorghum, sorghum, sorghum-gram.
- The selection of crops should be problem based e.g. on sloppy lands which are prone to soil erosion, an alternate cropping of erosion promoting (erect growing crops like millet etc) and erosion resisting crops like legumes, should be adopted. Selection of crops should suit the farmer's financial conditions.
- Both wide spaced crop and thickly planted crops should be included in rotation for control of weeds. e.g. wide spaced crops like tobacco controls weeds due to frequent inter culturing and dense (thick) forage or legume crops control weeds and soil erosion e.g. soybean.
- Crops with different botanical relationship should be altered for control of weeds, pests and diseases.
- Effect of previous crop on succeeding crop should be considered for obtaining maximum yield and harvest quality of produce.
- Enough elasticity may be kept in rotation so that if pest or diseases destroy a crop, another crop can be substituted.
- Fertile and well-drained land should be utilized for important good rotation, less fertile land for soil improving crops (legumes) and salt tolerant crops on acidic, saline or alkali soils.
- The ideal crop rotation should be built up around a hub crop for which the greatest comparative advantages exist. e.g. in areas of dairy industry oil seeds like groundnut or pulses will supply

cattle feed (oil cakes and roughages) or in irrigated areas near cities, growing of vegetables or floriculture will be profitable.

- Selection of crops should be demand based, i.e. the crops, which are needed by the people or area. So that produce can be sold at a higher price. The area devoted to each crop should be constant from year to year.

Advantages of crop rotation

- It increases overall yield of crops mainly due to maintaining physical- chemical properties of soil. Soil fertility is restored by fixing atmospheric nitrogen, encouraging microbial activity (more organic matter) and protecting soil from erosion, salinity and acidity.
- It helps in controlling insects, pests and soil borne diseases.
- It also controls weeds. e.g. repeated wheat culture increases wild oats and phalaris infestation. Similarly growing berseem continuously encourages chicory (kasani) infestation, but an alternate cropping of berseem and wheat helps in controlling kasani as well as oats and phalaris.
- It prevents or limits periods of peak requirements of irrigation water. Crops requiring high irrigation if followed by light irrigation, this will not affect or deteriorate the soil physical condition.
- It facilitates even distribution of labour and crop make proper utilization of all resources and inputs. Family and farm labour, power, equipment and machines are well employed through out the year.
- Farmers get a better price for their produce due to higher demand in local market. So there is regular flow of income over year.
- Inclusion of crops of different feeding zones (root system) and nutrient requirement maintains the better balance of nutrient in soil. Growing crops of different root depths avoids continuous depletion of nutrients from the same depth. e.g. deep rooted crops take nutrients from deeper zone and during that period upper zone get enriched. Similarly, surface feeding roots take nutrients from upper zone when lower zone get enriched. So growing same crop without rotation results in loss of soil productivity.
- Diversification of crops reduces risk of financial loss due to unfavorable conditions. Diversification of crops means variety of crops can be grown for meeting the domestic needs of farmers and livestock, to reduce risk of market fluctuations, mechanism of farming, growing expensive crops. So all variety of crops are grown in rotation for more benefit. ix. It improves soil structure, percolation and reduces changes of creation of hard- pan in sub soil and also reduces soil erosion.
- The family needs of feed, food, fuel, fiber, spices, sugar etc. are fulfilled and also fulfill needs of livestock.
- Advantages of raising short duration crops (catch crop/vegetables) when long season crops cannot be raised due to some reasons.

Disadvantages of crop rotation

Design a 4-crop rotation cycle

Soya bean – Wheat – Cotton - fallow

- This rotation is typical/popular in the middle-veld.

- Requires high level of management
- Provides short period between wheat harvesting and cotton planting
- Individual Crop Characteristics important for consideration in rotations

Cotton – due to slow early growth and (type?) of root system may cause extensive erosion and thus can be grown year after year on the same field.
- long season crop

Sunflower - poor soil/crop cover and thus may also cause soil erosion.
- a good extractor/user of nutrients. Thus, after growing it, an extra supply of nutrients is required.
- a drought tolerant crop and thus may exhaust soil water

Maize - grows rapidly and thus avoids or reduces the amount of soil erosion. It also has a good root system.
- requires high levels of Nitrogen as opposed to tobacco, soya and groundnuts and because of this, it may cause soil acidification.

Groundnuts - requires less nitrogen
- may exhaust soil water since it is regarded as a drought tolerant crop.
- fixes nitrogen
- to be grown once in every 4 years

Tobacco - susceptible to root-knot-nematode
- does not require much nitrogen as maize
- to be grown once in 4 years
- encourages soil losses – poor ground cover

Soya bean - Nitrogen fixation, requires less nitrogen
- Potash is required in high amount
- Generally short season crop

Fallow period

- Improve soil fertility
- Improve soil physical properties
- Reduce soil erosion
- Break life cycles of pests and diseases

discuss the importance of including a legume in a crop rotation [10]

- deep rooted crop; that makes effective use of nutrients. It also absorbs water from different horizons within the soil profile.
- it possess nodules, which are a sign of symbiotic relationship with bacteria that fix nitrogen.
- Thus improves soil fertility. The leaves of the plant have nutrients residues, which make them important as a green manuring crop.
- Legumes have a short live cycle, giving the farmer enough time to prepare land for next crop.
- the plant have large leaf canopy which will in turn leave leaf residues on surface of the soil.
- these increase organic matter of the soil.
- legumes belong to different botanical class with wheat/maize which are most common grown in Zimbabwe

- crop rotation which changes the botanical class of crops avoid diseases and pest build up.
- legumes are a cheap source of protein diet.

SUB TOPIC: CEREAL AND LEGUME CROP PRODUCTION

Crop origins; soil and climate requirements

- Discuss the origin of a named legume and cereal crop
- Explain the uses of the named legume and cereal crop
- Describe critical growth stages of a named cereal and a legume crop in relation to moisture stress.
- Describe the soil and climate requirements of a named legume and cereal crop.

Growth stages of Maize

- Maize growth involves about five stages.
- The stages have different moisture requirements.
- These stages are germination and emergence, vegetative, flowering, pollination and grain filling and maturity.

1. Germination and emergence

- Germination starts in about 2-3 days with the radical emerging.
- In 6-10 days, the coleoptile that encloses the plumule emerges above the ground (emergence).
- Primary and seminal roots would have started to develop.
- The first and second leaves appear. Soil capping affects emergence to a great extent.

2. Vegetative growth

- Permanent adventitious roots develop within one and three weeks after emergence.
- At around four weeks the plants reaches knee height.
- All the leaves will have formed although a limited number will be visible.
- At this point the plant will have cut its link with the seed.
- During this stage the plant will be fairly resistant to moisture stress.

3. Reproductive stages

I. Flowering (tassel and ear initiation)

- This period ranges from 46-63 days.
- After 6 weeks the tassel begins to form but will not actually emerge for another four weeks.
- The ovule and the ear size are determined during this period.
- Any moisture stress at this stage will affect yield.
- Under extreme drought condition the tassel is not affected as it gets first preference over the ear due to apical dominance.

- Moisture stress may delay the ear and ovule developments causing a lag between the times of pollen shedding.

II. Pollination

- Moisture and nutritional stress at this stage will affect the final yield.
- It is at this stage that one can determine the failure of fertilisation.
- If fertilization fails to occur the obvious sign is the extension of the silk excessively.
- Tassel emerges 7-10 days before the first silk but the pollen is not shed until 2-3 days before silk emerges to facilitate synchronisation.
- Synchronisation is the timing of pollen shedding to the receptive silk.
- Pollen is shed from the spike downwards and about 2-5 millions of pollen grains are produced by each tassel.
- Moisture stress at flowering can result in the silks being withheld by the ear while pollen is shed normally.
- If stress causes the silk to be withheld for duration of the pollen shedding period, yield can be drastically reduced to almost nothing.
- Once the silk receives the pollen, they usually dry in 48 hours. The silk that remains moist may continue to elongate and one can inspect the crop for such a sign.

4. Grain filling and drying

- This stage takes place at about 81-150 days depending with the maize variety.
- The moment fertilisation occurs, grain filling commences.
- Moisture stress interferes with photosynthesis.
- This reduces manufactured sugars and a reduction in yield.
- At about three week post pollination, the kernels are milky and contain mostly sugars.
- As time progresses sugars are converted to starch.
- It takes only 200-220 days for a maize crop to dry naturally.
- Moisture content should be 12.5% but can be harvested at 25% and artificially dried.

Crop management

- Discuss factors to consider when choosing appropriate legume and cereal crop cultivar.
 - Describe the planting of a named cereal and legume crop
 - Discuss the management of a named legume and cereal crop
 - Identify weeds; pests and diseases of a named cereal crop and legume crop
 - Discuss ways of controlling weeds; pests and diseases in a named cereal and legume crop.
- The timing of planting or sowing is influenced by the type of crop to be planted and the environmental conditions of the area.
 - **Factors to consider in timing planting:**
 - The rainfall pattern/moisture condition of the soil.
 - Type of crop to be planted.
 - Soil type.

- Market demand.
- Prevalence of pests and diseases.
- Weed control.
- Timely planting is necessary and should be done at the onset of rains. In some areas where rainfall is scarce dry
- planting is recommended.

Methods of planting

- Direct seeding
- Transplanting
- Machine planting
- Hand planting
- Row planting vs broadcasting

Advantages of timely planting:

- Crops make maximum use of rainfall and suitable soil temperature, leading to vigorous growth.
- Crops usually escape serious pests and diseases attack.
- Crops benefit from nitrogen flush which is available at the beginning of the rain.
- For horticultural crops, proper timing ensures that the produce is marketed when prices are high.
- Crops establish earlier than the weeds, hence smothering them.

Planting methods based on water availability

- **Planting with the rains.** The farmer plants seed after receiving adequate rains or after the first effective rains. Normally 50mm is adequate.
- **Dry planting.** The farmer sows seed 2-3 weeks before effective rains are received. The soil is dry and planting depth should be deeper than normal planting depth (as used under 1). This is done to ensure that, in the case of light showers, the planted seed is not wetted. If light showers wet the seed, the moisture will not be adequate for germination, and all the light rains will do is to cause rotting of the seeds. Lighter soils are more suitable for dry planting than the heavier ones because the former soils can easily/quickly dry off if light showers are received and the danger of seed rotting is reduced. For maize seeds may be planted at about 7.5 cm instead of the usual 5.0cm depth.
- **Water planting with water.** In this case, the soil is initially dry. The farmer artificially supplies water to the planting stations or rows. A hole is dug (planting station). Soaking water is administered to the hole until it subsides. The hole is slightly covered with dry soil and seed is then placed. The hole is then covered with dry soil (soil mulch)
- **Water planting without water.** The farmer relies/uses residual soil moisture. Seed is planted on a wet (from residual moisture) soil. The crop is established before the start of the rain season. Common practice in dambos/ wet lands/vleis.

Sowing depth

- Depth at which seed is placed = f (seed size; type of germination; moisture status of the soil and soil type)
- The larger the seed, the greater the depth from which it can emerge, the deeper it can safely be placed/planted. Rule of thumb is place seed at depth 2-3 times its diameter. Large seeds have enough

quantities of stored food reserves for the germination and emergence processes. Small seeds deplete their stored food in a short time

- Seeds with epigeal germination have to push the cotyledons to the surface and therefore have limited ability to emerge from great depths.
- Under dry conditions, seeds should be placed/sown deeper in order to place them in contact with moist soil
- Seeds can emerge from greater depths in sandy soil than in clay soil, all other factors remaining constant. Thus planting depth can be adjusted according to soil texture

Seed rate

- Can be expressed as weight of seed per hectare or number of seeds per hectare. For the same crop variety, the larger the seed the more weight of seed will be required per unit area.
- Maize = approximately 25-30kg/ha; small grains (5-7kg/ha); soyabean and groundnuts (90-120 kg/ha). The desired plant population depends the seeding rate.

Maize cultivars

Factors considered when selecting suitable Maize variety.

- Potential yield of the variety.
- Standability- resistance to lodging as it reduces harvesting losses and damage.
- Insect pest resistance
- Drought tolerance
- Number of days to reach maturity
- End use value such as milling, stock feed and silage.
- Cob height- is related to maturity. Excessive height may contribute to plant lodging in wind and rain situations.
- Husk cover- they function to prevent damage caused by larvae, and protect the grain from weather.

Common Maize varieties: -

Very early maturity e.g. SC403

- ❖ Very tolerant to maize streak virus and mofle viruses.
- ❖ A relatively short, flinty ear and excellent yields.
- ❖ Stability over a range of environments.
- ❖ Outstanding drought tolerant.
- ❖ High potential yields.
- ❖ Tolerant to diploid ear rot.

Early maturity- e.g. SC513

- ❖ Average tolerance to both Maize streak xims (MSV) and grey leaf spot (GLS).
- ❖ Takes about 137 days to mature.
- ❖ High yielding potential.
- ❖ White dent variety.

Medium maturity- e.g. SC602

- ❖ Moderately susceptible to GLS and MSV.
- ❖ Takes about 144 days to mature.
- ❖ Yellow dent varieties.

- ❖ Has excellent yield potential.

Late maturity – e.g. SC709

- ❖ Susceptible to MSV.
- ❖ Very tolerant to GLS.
- ❖ Takes 151 days to mature.
- ❖ Excellent yield potential.

TOPIC 7: CONSERVATION FARMING

SUB TOPIC: PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES

Conservation farming

- Explain the importance of conservation farming
- Outline the components and practices of conservation farming
- Describe different conservation farming practices

Tillage practices/systems

- There are three main tillage systems/practices. These include:
 - a) Conventional tillage;
 - b) Conservation tillage;
 - c) Minimum /reduced tillage.
- **Conventional tillage** includes both primary tillage and secondary tillage. A number of operations are performed systematically depending on the requirements of the crop and area for example:
 - a) shredding or disking crop residues (preliminary operation)
 - b) primary tillage(ploughing)
 - c) secondary tillage –may involve disc harrowing followed by spike-, spring- or tine-tooth harrowing, one or two times
 - d) planting
 - e) cultivating/weeding
- Several passes of different operations leave the soil with a fine tilth that is ideal for planting. It also eliminates the risk of trash interfering with the planting operation, but may have the disadvantage of rendering the soil highly erodible.
- **Conservation tillage** is broadly defined as any practice [trash farming, mulch farming, stubble farming as opposed to clean tillage] that leaves at least 30% of crop residue over the soil surface after planting (Oliver, 1989; Vowles,1989 cited by Nyakanda, 2000).
- The main objectives of conservation tillage (*and mulch tillage*) are:
 - a) Soil and moisture conservation;
 - b) Energy conservation.
- Conservation tillage has a number of advantages. Some of the advantages include:
 - a) Reduced soil erosion;
 - b) Increased water availability;
 - c) Moderation of temperature;
 - d) Timeliness of operations;
 - e) Improved soil structure;

- a. A better root system develops closer to the surface;
 - b. This is a cheaper system.
- These advantages are generally on long term.
- The disadvantages of conservation tillage are:
 - a) It is difficult to rectify compaction layers:
 - b) The mulch created may reduce temperatures
 - c) High C/N ratio of the common crop residues may depress nitrification.

Minimum tillage (reduced /optimum/economy tillage).

- This system concentrates on the minimum disturbance of the soil, mostly introducing the seed into the soil. There are several methods of introducing seed into the soil used in this case. They include:
 - a) Strip tillage; normally, the farmer works on strip/row of previous crop
 - b) Direct planting in stations.
 - c) The system has been made possible of late, by the use of special equipment and the use of herbicides
- Tillage can be reduced in two ways –
 - a) omitting less beneficial operations
 - b) combining operations
- *These systems involve principles rather than well-defined practices.*
- System objectives include:
 - a. Reducing energy input and labour requirement for crop production
 - b. Conserving soil moisture and reducing erosion
 - c. Providing optimum seedbed and root bed growth area, rather than homogenizing the entire soil surface
 - d. Keeping trips over the field to minimum

Limitations of the system:

- Weed infestation especially early weed infestation: more of a problem for the smallholder farmers. Weed pressure under reduced tillage can be reduced by controlling the late weeds in the previous crop.
- Pests and diseases are likely to be a problem especially where residues remain in the field (*what is the situation with smallholder farmers. How do they manage crop residues? – grazing in situ; removal and storage at cattle kraals etc*)
- Use of resistant varieties and good crop rotations will reduce pest and disease problems.

Other tillage terms/practices

- Clean tillage: Cultivation of a field so as to cover all plant residues and to prevent the growth of all vegetation except the particular crop desired, e.g. conventional tillage.
- Mulch tillage: Soil tillage that employs plant residues or other material to cover the ground surface.
- Combined tillage: Reduces number of secondary tillage operations by combining secondary tillage and planting into one operation. Several secondary tillage implements may be hooked together and used in conjunction with a planter

Zero tillage (No-till)

- An extreme form of minimum tillage. Primary tillage is done away with and secondary tillage is restricted to seedbed preparation in the row zone only.

- It is recommended in high erosion prone areas and in multiple cropping systems/areas where there is inadequate time for any tillage operations
- Weed control is a problem
- Practice reduces loss of soil moisture through evaporation which would result from conventional tillage of stubble.

Tillage for weed control

1. Tillage before planting

-Most tillage operations prior to planting provide some measure of weed control especially secondary tillage operations immediately before planting. Delayed seedbed preparation utilizes delayed secondary tillage to kill weeds on previously ploughed land.

2. Tillage after planting and before crop emergence

-Tillage of large seeded crops e.g. maize and soyabean can be done before emergence to i) weed control ii) break soil crust for better crop emergence.

-Ten (10%) crop stand can be destroyed, but loss in stand is usually less severe than loss of stand resulting from soil crusting. One can use rotary hoe soon after crop emergence.

3. Cultivation after crop emergence.

-Although chemicals provide some weed control, cultivation of row crops often provides the most economical and surest method for controlling troublesome weeds. Cultivation should be shallow to minimize root injury otherwise it can lower yields compared to other methods of weed control if roots are severely pruned.

Agronomic considerations in adopting tillage practices

When deciding to use a tillage practice we have to consider several factors. These considerations are:

a) Seed and fertilizer placement;

- Although surface crop residues prevent soil erosion, they present problems in seed and fertilizer placement. Heavy trash can interfere with proper seed placement, covering of seed with soil and seed-to-soil contact.
- In no-plough systems, cooler soil temperatures under mulch and relative immobility of P, K and micro-nutrients in soils can reduce nutrient uptake efficiency of plants growing in low fertility soils.

b) Pest control;

- Weeds accumulate near soil surface in reduced tillage systems. Crop residues also interfere with weed control equipment.
- Need for chemical weed control at increased herbicide rates, but limiting the use of pre-plant, soil-incorporated herbicides.
- Surface residues may harbour pest organisms which can become major problems compared to clean tillage systems.

Soil conservation-Crop residues save loss of top soil.

FORM 6

TOPIC 1: PLANT MORPHOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY

SUB TOPIC: PLANT GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT

Plant growth regulators

- Describe the effects of growth regulators on plant growth and development
 - Gibberellins
 - Cytokinins
 - Ethylene
 - Auxins
 - Absciic acid
- Demonstrating the effects of growth regulators such as on rooting; growth and ripening.

Plant growth regulators

- Plant regulators are hormones that control plant growth and development.
- A plant hormone is an organic substance produced in one part of the plant and translocated to a target part, where it evokes a physiological response.
- Growth regulators can be placed into five groups:
 - i. Abscisic Acid,
 - ii. Auxins,
 - iii. Cytokinins,
 - iv. Ethylene,
 - v. Gibberellins.

Abscisic Acid (ABA):

- These are growth inhibiting substances whose site of synthesis is not clear.
- They move in all directions within plants.

Developmental and Physiological Effects of ABA

- Regulates seed maturation.

- ABA inhibits **precocious** (early germination of seed before maturity) germination and **viviparity** (germination of seeds before they are shed from the parent plant).
- Promotes seed storage reserve accumulation and desiccation tolerance.
- Induces bud and seed dormancy that requires scarification.
- Inhibits GA-induced enzyme production.
- Promotes root growth and inhibits shoot growth at low water potentials.
- Promotes leaf senescence independently of ethylene.
- ABA accumulates in dormant buds.
- Closes stomata in response to water stress.
- Promote fruit abscission.
- Regulates ion channels and the plasma membrane ATPase in guard cells.

Auxins:

- Auxins are synthesised in meristemic tissues, and their transport is polarised in aerial organs.
- They are transported along the longitudinal axis of the plant more rapidly in one direction than in the opposite direction. Examples of auxins are indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and 4-chloro-indoleacetic acid.

Actions of Auxin: Cell Elongation

- Auxins promote growth in stems and coleoptiles, while inhibiting growth in roots.
- The outer tissues of dicot stems are the targets of auxin action.
- The minimum lag time for auxin-induced elongation is ten minutes.
- Rapidly increases the extensibility of the cell wall.
- Auxin-induced proton extrusion increases cell extension.
- Auxin-induced proton extrusion involves activation and protein mobilization.

Actions of Auxin: Plant Tropisms

- Phototropism is mediated by the lateral redistribution of auxin.
- Gravitropism involves lateral redistribution of auxin.
- Auxin application on one side of coleoptile cause the coleoptile to bend in opposite direction.

Developmental Effects of Auxin

- Regulates apical dominance.
- Auxin transport regulates floral bud development and **phyllotaxy** (arrangement of leaves on a stem).
- Promotes the formation of lateral and adventitious roots.
- Increase fruit set and influence the sex of unisexual flowers.
- Induces vascular differentiation.
- Promote rooting of cuttings.
- Promotes **parthenocarpic** (development of fruit without fertilization) fruit development in some species.
- Delays the onset of leaf abscission and leaf senescence.

Promotes fruit development, and stimulate synthesis of ethylene.

Cytokinins:

- Regulators of Cell Division

- They stimulate cell division in plant tissues.
- They are synthesised in the roots, and there is evidence of upward movement in the stem.

Cell Division and Plant Development

- Differentiated plant cells can resume division.
- Diffusible factors control cell division.
- Plant tissues and organs can be cultured.

The Biological Roles of Cytokinins

- Promote fruit set, parthenocarpy and flowering.
- Control apical dominance.
- Delay senescence in leaves.
- Inhibit root growth by promoting the exit of cells from the root apical meristem.
- Regulate specific components of the cell cycle.
- The auxin/cytokinin ratio regulates morphogenesis in cultured tissues.
- Modify apical dominance and promote lateral bud growth.
- Promote movement of nutrients and delay leaf senescence.
- Affect light signalling via phytochrome. □ Regulate vascular development.
- They are involved in the formation of nitrogen-fixing nodules in legumes.

Ethylene:

The Gaseous Hormone

- Ethylene is a gas produced by any plant tissue.
- It does not move between different parts of the plant in significant amounts.

Developmental and Physiological Effects of Ethylene

- Ethylene promotes the ripening of some fruits.
- Fruits that respond to ethylene exhibit a **climacteric** (fruit ripening stage).
- The receptors of never-ripe mutants of tomato fail to bind ethylene.
- Stimulates leaf epinasty that results when ACC (1-aminocyclopane-1-carboxylic acid) from the root is transported to the shoot.
- Ethylene induces lateral cell expansion, thus reducing stem elongation.
- Inhibit polar transport of auxin.
- Stimulates flowering in pineapples.
- Breaks seed and bud dormancy in some species.
- Promotes the elongation growth of submerged aquatic species.
- Induces the formation of adventitious roots and root hairs.
- Accelerates leaf senescence and abscission.
- Ethylene mediates some defence responses, and acts on the abscission layer.

Gibberellins (GA):

Regulators of Plant Height and Seed Germination

- They are mainly synthesised in young leaves.

- They are transported through the circulatory system of the xylem and phloem tissues.
- The gas do not exhibit the polarity of transport exhibited by auxins.

Effects of Gibberellins on Growth and Development

- Break dormancy or promote seed germination and early seed development.
- Can stimulate stem elongation and root growth.
- Regulate the transition from juvenile to adult phases.
- Influence floral initiation and sex determination.
- Promote pollen development and tube growth.
- Promote fruit set and **parthenocarpy** (without fertilization) in some species.
- Delay leaf senescence and inhibit leaf abscission. □ Stimulate flowering in short night plants (vernalisation).

Gibberellin Responses: Stem Growth

- Gibberellins stimulate cell elongation and cell division.
- GAs regulate the transcription of cell cycle kinases.
- Reducing GA sensitivity may prevent crop losses.

The uses of plant regulators in agriculture

Growth regulators are used to:

- Increase the rate of growth or as “growth triggers”.
- Break dormancy, and initiate floral induction and rooting induction in cuttings.
- Increase or decrease fruit set, and control fruit ripening.
- Modify apical dominance to encourage lateral growth.
- Reduce crop loss by lodging through interfering with internode elongation. o Accelerate senescence and abscission of leaves and fruits.

Use of growth regulators in field crops

- A plant regulator such as *Chlormaquat chloride* is used to prevent lodging in wheat, maize and barley by internode shortening. This reduces yield loss through lodging.
- Spraying an indeterminate soyabean variety, such as Impala, with an antigrowth substance, retards vegetative growth. More nutrients are available for pod and bean development and thus increases seed yield.
- Indole Acetic Acid (IAA) is used to initiate root growth in cuttings of woody species.
- Defoliant such as Sodium chlorate and Magnesium chlorate, are used to remove leaves from the cotton plant.
- Antitranspirants, e.g. ABA and Phenyl mercuric acid (PMA) are applied to the transpiring plant surfaces so as to reduce water loss. They induce stomatal closure.

SUB TOPIC: SEED AND SEED GERMINATION

Seed dormancy

- Test seed viability
- Discuss the different types of seed dormancy
- Describe methods of overcoming dormancy
- Design and carryout experiments on seed dormancy

SEED VIABILITY

- Seed viability is a *measure of how many seeds are alive and could develop into plants which will reproduce themselves, given the appropriate conditions.*
- A **viabile seed** is a seed which is able to live and develop. Viable seeds that do not germinate are said to be **dormant**.
- A **non-viable** seed, is either metabolically dead or has suffered irreparable damage and cannot germinate under any conditions.

Test for seed viability

a) Tetrazolium chloride (TTC) test

Method:

Seeds are soaked in water overnight.

Remove seed coat of legumes.

Add 2.3.5 triphenenyl-tetrazolium to water to form a colourless solution.

Place seeds in 1% solution of 2.3.5 triphenenyl-tetrazolium chloride.

Results:

Embryos of living seeds are stained deep red, purple or orange.

Dead embryo of non-viable seed will remain white or unstained.

b) Soaking seed in distilled water

Viable seeds will sink because they are denser.

Dead seeds will float.

c) Excised embryo test.

- The embryos in the seeds of many woody plant species have profound dormancy conditions and do not respond in a direct germination test.

- In this test the embryo is excised from the seed and germinated alone, by placing them for example on moist paper in a petri-dish.
- The time required for the test varies from 3 days to 3 weeks. Non viable embryos remain white at first but become soft, turn brown and decay within 2 to 10 days.
- Viable embryos remain firm and will show some activity like greening and separation of the cotyledons, growth of radicle and plumule.
- The rapidity and degree of development also gives some indication of the vigor of the seed.

Seed dormancy

- **Dormancy can be described as the condition in which viable seeds fail to germinate when favourable germination conditions are provided.** This may be a result of internal or external factors or a combination of both.
- Harger in 1977 described dormancy thus:

“Some seeds are born dormant (innate dormancy); some acquire dormancy (induced dormancy); and some have dormancy thrust upon them (enforced dormancy)”.

The types of dormancy found in seed

- **Innate dormancy** is failure of a viable seed to germinate when it is shed from the plant. It IS genetically controlled.
- **Induced dormancy** occurs when the seed fails to germinate due to exposure of some after-ripening experience i.e. the seed was germinable when it was shed from the plant but because of some after-ripening experience it has become dormant.
- **Enforced dormancy** is when a seed fails to germinate due to unfavourable environmental conditions such as shortage of water, low temperature or poor aeration e.t.c.
- Dormancy can be broadly divided into two main classes namely **primary dormancy** and **secondary dormancy**.
- In turn secondary dormancy can be further divided into induced dormancy and enforced dormancy.

Significance of dormancy

- Dormancy is often assumed to be important in relation to the prevention of viviparity and precocious germination i.e. germination while still on the mother plant (Bewley and Black, 1982).
- Helps seed shed from the same plant to germinate at different times during the season.
- Gives seed ample time to be dispersed to new habitats.

- Allows seeds to pass through drought, cold and other unfavourable conditions.
- Enable grains, pulses and other edibles to be stored, making them available throughout the year and transport to the areas of deficiency.

Mechanisms of dormancy

Innate dormancy mechanisms

- Innate dormancy may be associated with either embryo dormancy or coat-imposed dormancy or both.
 - Embryo dormancy**
 - A viable mature embryo in a seed fails to germinate when the seed is shed from the plant or even when the embryo is excised and exposed to conditions favourable for germination.

Reasons :

a) Cotyledons may produce inhibitors that prevent germination

- Remedy- Remove the cotyledons. E.g. in barley (*Hordeum vulgare*)
- Several inhibitors have been isolated from dormant embryos and prominent among them has been abscissic acid (ABA).

b) Embryo immaturity/ rudimentary embryos

- Embryos of several species are morphologically immature when the seed is shed from the plant e.g. pine (*Pinus sylvestris*), black ash (*Fraxinus nigra*)
- Remedy- Allow the embryo some time to mature before planting the seeds.

ii) Coat-imposed dormancy

- In many species seed dormancy is often imposed by the structures surrounding the seed. Such structures include the seed coat or testa, pericarp, perisperm, endosperm and glumes, palea and lemma (cereals).
- Remedy: Coat-imposed dormancy is often broken by physically or chemically abrasion of the coat.
- The mechanisms by which the seed coat structures prevent embryo germination include:
 - Interfere with water uptake
 - Interfere with gas exchange
 - Presence of chemical inhibitors in the seed covers
 - Prevention of escape of inhibitors from seed by seed covers
 - Modification of light reaching the embryo by the seed covers
 - The seed cover physically or mechanically constrains the embryo from expanding
- Seeds with coat-imposed dormancy are sometimes termed “hard seeds” (Berrie, 1984 in Mashingaidze).

Induced dormancy

- This implies that the seed was not dormant when it was shed from the plant but rather acquired dormancy because of exposure to certain adverse conditions in the environment in which it was shed.
- Such seeds will not germinate even when favourable germination conditions are provided but will require another set of conditions to break dormancy.
- Conditions that may induce dormancy include high temperatures, absence of light for seeds that are positively photoblastic seeds, exposure to high concentrations of carbon dioxide e.t.c.

Enforced dormancy

- Seeds fail to germinate because of lack of favourable germination conditions. Enforced dormancy is therefore not of physiological origin but is a manifestation of the inadequacies in conditions required for the seed to germinate.
- Remedy: Provide the necessary conditions

The major categories of dormancy include **exogenous**; **endogenous**; **double**; and **secondary dormancy**. **Exogenous dormancy** is imposed by factors outside the embryo. These include maternal tissues in the seed or fruit (like the seed coat or pericarp); or mechanical resistance imposed on the radicle. **Endogenous dormancy** is related to dormancy factors within the embryo itself. **Double dormancy** includes any combination of exogenous and endogenous dormancy. The first three categories are examples of primary dormancy. **Secondary dormancy** occurs in certain seeds when the germination environment does not permit germination and induces dormancy in seeds that were previously nondormant.

Exogenous dormancy

- The tissues enclosing the embryo can impact germination by inhibiting water uptake, providing mechanical restraint to embryo expansion and radicle emergence, modifying gas exchange (i.e. limit oxygen to the embryo), preventing leaching of inhibitors from the embryo and supplying inhibitors to the embryo.

Physical dormancy (seed coat dormancy)

- Physical exogenous dormancy is produced by seed coverings that are impervious to water.
- This type of dormancy can preserve the dry seed for many years, and germination can be induced by any method that can soften or scarify the covering.
- This type of dormancy is a genetic characteristic of certain plant families, including Leguminosae, Malvaceae, Canaceae. Among cultivated crops, hardseededness is found chiefly in the herbaceous legumes, including clover and alfalfa, as well as many woody legumes (*Robinia*, *Acacia*).

Methods of overcoming dormancy

- Some seed-enclosing structures, such as shells of walnut, pits of stone fruits, and stones of olive are too strong to allow the dormant embryo to expand during germination.
- This has been shown in both herbaceous (lettuce, pepper and tomato)and woody (redbud and lilac) plants.
- In nature, impervious seed coats and hard seed coats are softened by action of micro-organisms in the soil during warm periods of the season or by passage through the digestive tracts of birds and mammals.
- They may be broken through mechanical abrasion, alternate freezing and thawing, and in some species by fire. In cultivation, scarification is used to overcome dormancy.
- **Scarification** is any process of breaking, scratching, mechanically altering, or softening the seed coverings to make them permeable to water and gases.
- Three types of treatments are commonly used as scarification treatments. These include: mechanical, chemical and hot water treatments.

Mechanical scarification:

- This involves chipping hard seed coats by rubbing with sandpaper, cutting with a file, or cracking with a hammer or a vise are simple methods useful for small amounts of relatively large seed. For large-scale mechanical operations, special scarifiers are used.
- Small seeds of legumes, such as alfalfa and clover, are often treated in this manner to increase germination. Seeds may be tumbled in drums lined with sandpaper or in concrete mixers containing coarse sand or gravel.
- The sand or gravel should be of a different size than the seed to facilitate subsequent separation. Scarification should not proceed to the point at which the seeds are injured.
- To determine the optimum time, a test lot can be germinated, the seeds may be soaked to observe swelling, or the seed coats may be observed with a hand lens.

Acid scarification:

- Dry seeds are placed in containers and covered with concentrated sulfuric acid in a ratio of about one part seed to two parts acid.
- The mixture should be stirred cautiously at intervals during the treatment to produce uniform results and to prevent accumulation of the dark, resinous material from the seed coats that is sometimes present.
- At the end of the treatment period the acid is poured off, and the seeds are washed to remove the acid. The acid-treated seeds can either be planted immediately when wet, or dried and stored for later planting.

Hot water treatment:

- Seeds are dropped into four to five times their volume of hot water to C).
- The heat source is immediately removed, and the seeds soaked in the gradually cooling water for 12 to 24 hours
- . The seeds should usually be planted immediately after the hot-water treatment.

Stratification:

- Stratification in the process of pretreating seed to simulate natural conditions that seed must endure before germination, e.g. exposing the seeds to cold temperatures in the refrigerator, simulates a short winter. When brought back to room temperature, they germinate readily.
- Seeds are spread between layers of moist substrate under cold temperatures (1-10°C) for a period of 1-6 months.

Water:

- Soaking seeds in water over night softens a hard seed coat enough to allow moisture inside so that the seed can germinate.
- For quicker results, pour boiling water over the seeds and let them soak until the water cools.
- Many types of legumes benefit from this treatment, including the garden pea (*Pisum sativum*).

Chemical dormancy

- Chemicals that accumulate in fruit and seed-covering tissues during development and remain with the seed after harvest can be shown to act as germination inhibitors.
- Some of the substances associated with inhibition are various phenols, coumarin and abscisic acid. Germination can sometimes be improved by prolonged leaching with water, removing the seed coverings, or application of growth promoters like gibberellins/cytokinins to overcome the effect of the growth inhibitors.

- Chemical dormancy occurs in citrus, cucurbits, stone fruits, apples, pears, grapes, and tomatoes.

Endogenous dormancy

- Endogenous dormancy is related to dormancy factors within the embryo itself. It includes the following:

Morphological dormancy

- Dormancy occurs in some seeds in which the embryo is not fully developed at the time of seed dissemination.
- Enlargement of the embryo occurs after the seeds have imbibed water and before germination begins.
- The process of embryo enlargement is usually favoured by a period of warm temperatures and treatment with chemical additives such as gibberellic acid. Examples are cyclamen, primula, anemone, carrot, gentian.

Physiological dormancy

- **After-ripening:** is a type of dormancy in which the embryos, although apparently fully formed and viable, remain dormant even when the seed coats are removed and conditions are suitable for growth. Germination in these cases takes place only after a series of little-understood changes, collectively called after-ripening, has taken place in the embryo as it lies dormant in the soil or is kept in storage. In some species, 1 year is sufficient for after-ripening to occur, but in others the process is drawn out over several years. This can be regarded as an insurance by the species against sudden catastrophes that might completely wipe out all the seedlings of any one age group. The period of after-ripening is usually shortened by exposure to high temperature.
- **Light-related dormancy:** seeds that either require light or dark conditions to germinate are termed **photo dormant**. Seeds of maize and many legumes such as cowpea germinate equally well in light and in darkness. Germination of onion and four-o'clock is inhibited by exposure to light, whereas the germination of lettuce, many weed species and many grasses is stimulated by light.
- **Temperature related dormancy:** many seeds require a period of one to three months of chilling before germination will start. This is most common in seeds of trees and shrubs and some herbaceous plants of the temperate zone. Seeds of this type ripen in the fall, overwinter on the ground, and germinate in the spring.

Double or combinational dormancy

- This type of dormancy combines two or more kinds of dormancy. To induce germination all blocking conditions must be eliminated in proper sequence.

Secondary dormancy

- In nature, primary dormancy is an adaptation to control the time and conditions for seed germination. **Secondary dormancy** is a further adaptation to prevent germination of an imbibed seed if other environmental conditions are not favourable.

- These conditions can include unfavourably high temperatures, temperatures too low, prolonged darkness, water stress, Release from secondary dormancy can be induced by chilling, sometimes by light, and in various cases, treatment with germination-stimulating hormones, particularly gibberellic acid.

Photosynthesis

- Explain the factors affecting photosynthesis
 - Light intensity
 - Water
 - Carbon dioxide
 - Oxygen concentration
- Describe light-dependent and light independent reactions
- Describe the photosynthetic electron transport
- Describe the structure and synthesis of ATP
- Explain the role of ATP as energy 'currency'

Factors Affecting Photosynthesis

1. Light intensity

- As for CO₂ concentration light tends to be the rate limiting at low intensities but not at high intensities.
- Rate of photosynthesis is measured by the rate of O₂ production.
- Plants respire as well as photosynthesis. At low light intensities the plants tend to respire .As light intensities increase the rate of photosynthesis.
- This is called the light compensation point. Above this light intensity the rate of photosynthesis exceeds the rate of respiration and so O₂ is released from the plant.

Agronomic Practices to Improve Light Interception:

- Now that we have seen those factors that limit photosynthesis, and one factor is light (*recall the light dependent reactions of photosynthesis*). We want now to look at agronomic practises that will improve light trapping the crop. Below are some of the practices: -
- ❖ Breed crops with quick establishment and those with fast growth rate so as to introduce leaf area fast.
- ❖ Breed crops with upright leaf angle that will reduce shading. This will enable more leaves at the bottom or lower canopy to receive light and fix carbon dioxide.
- ❖ Also breed for efficiency. In general, C₄ plants have a higher level of light utilization than C₃ plants.
- ❖ Use narrower interrows as these will enable ground area coverage faster. This is a function of genotype and cultivar.
- ❖ For crops like maize, grow them well in time (*summer*) when they can receive enough light and under ideal temperatures.

2. Concentration of carbon dioxide

- Photosynthesis is limited by the concentration of carbon dioxide in the air.
- If there is plenty of light, a plant cannot photosynthesise if there is insufficient carbon dioxide.
- The atmosphere contains only 0.03% of the gas by volume. Increase in CO₂ concentration from 0.03% to 0.3-1% raises rate of photosynthesis. Higher concentrations have an inhibitory effect on photosynthesis.

CO₂ compensation point

- Compensation point is the point reached in a plant when the rate of photosynthesis is equal to the rate of respiration.
- This means that the Carbon dioxide released from respiration is equivalent to that which is taken up during photosynthesis.
- The compensation point is reached as light intensity increases.
- If light intensity is increased beyond the compensation point, the rate of photosynthesis increases proportionally until the point of light saturation is reached, beyond which the rate of photosynthesis is no longer affected by sunlight intensity. What does the CO₂ compensation point indicate?
- At this point, the uptake of CO₂ through photosynthetic pathways is equal to the respiratory release of carbon dioxide, and the uptake of O₂ by respiration is equal to the photosynthetic release of oxygen.
- In assimilation terms, at the compensation point, the net carbon dioxide assimilation is zero. (Ref. graph below)

- At very low carbon concentration rates the rate of CO₂ evolution due to dark respiration exceeds the rate of net carbon dioxide assimilation. This results in a negative CO₂ uptake, or net CO₂ evolution.
- As fluence rate increases, photosynthesis also increases and so does CO₂ uptake until the rate of CO₂ exchange equals zero.
- This is the fluence rate, known as the light compensation point, at which the competing processes of photosynthesis and respiration are balanced. The light compensation point for most plants falls somewhere in the range of 10 to 40 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, roughly equivalent to the light level found in a well-lighted office, laboratory, or classroom.
- At fluence rates above the compensation point, the rate of photosynthesis continues to increase until, at least in C₃ plants, it reaches light saturation.
- When the rate of photosynthesis equals the rate of respiration or photo respiration, the compensation point occurs.

Oxygen

- Photosynthesis does not take place in cells which lack oxygen because of the following reasons:
 - The energy produced in oxygen respiration is necessary for photosynthesis.
 - Oxygen is required for the production and maintenance of some substance, essential for photosynthesis.
- High concentrations of oxygen inhibit the rate of photosynthesis in C₃ plants, and promotes photorespiration in C₄ plants.

Water

- Water is one of the raw materials of photosynthesis.
- Only 1% water is absorbed by the plant, therefore, it cannot be a limiting factor directly.
- Water content of the leaf acts as a limiting factor indirectly. It maintains the turgor of the assimilatory cells.
- The rate of photosynthesis decreases in the cells which have lost their turgor.
- The loss of turgor of guard cells closes the stomata.
- This reduces the rate of photosynthesis.

Structure of ATP

- ATP is a energy carrier molecule made up of organic base adenine ,a pentose sugar ribose and three phosphate groups.
- The third phosphate can be debouched from ATP by the release producing ADP plus a inorganic phosphate .

Condensation

- Adding Pi to ADP is known as phosphorylation. The enzyme ATPASE has catalyzed the reaction.
- All cells in every living organism use ATP as their energy source
- ATP is known as the universal energy carrier molecule.

Describe the structure and synthesis of ATP and its universal role as the energy currency in all living organisms. [8]

- nucleotide;
- adenine + ribose / pentose + three phosphates;
- loss of phosphate leads to energy release / hydrolysis releases
- 30.5 kJ;
- $ADP + P_i \leftrightarrow ATP$ (reversible reaction) ;
- synthesised during, glycolysis / Krebs cycle / substrate level
- phosphorylation ;
- synthesised, using electron carriers / oxidative phosphorylation /
- photophosphorylation ;
- in, mitochondria / chloroplasts ;
- ATP synthase / ATP synthetase ;
- chemiosmosis / description;
- used by cells as immediate energy donor ;
- link between energy yielding and energy requiring reactions / AW ;
- active transport / muscle contraction / Calvin cycle / protein synthesis

LIGHT DEPENDENT STAGE: THE Z SCHEME / PHOTOPHOSPHORYLATION

Describe the transfer of energy to ATP during photosynthesis [6]

- light absorbed by chlorophyll
- An electron from P700 or P680 is boosted to a higher energy level when light strikes the photosystem;
- the electron which acquires excitation is accepted by electron acceptor x or y .
- The electron acceptor x or y become reduced and chlorophylls become oxidized with positive change.
- The electrons with the excess energy of oxidation are very unstable tend to fall down to their ground state .
- The electrons then in terms of energy via a series of electron acceptors.
- The excess energy lost when they fall back to the ground state is coupled in the production of ATP.
- The positive charge left in the p680 contribute to the photochemical lysis of water which releases electrons which lost from electron acceptor X .
- Electrons flow X along a chain of electron carriers losing energy [used to phosphorylate ADP to ATP] FILLING THE HOLE LEFT IN p700 ,electrons also pass down from Y to NADP along a chain a chain of electron carries to and combine with hydrogen ions from water to form reduced NADP.
- This is called non cyclic photophosphorylation.

- In cycle photophosphorylation electrons from Y are recycled to P700 via a electron chain carries results in ATP being formed

Describe the roles of the following substances in the light-independent stage of photosynthesis:

(i) RuBP [2]

- carbon dioxide fixation;
- production of GP;
- Ref. to rubisco;

(ii) reduced NADP [2]

- reduction (of GP) / donates hydrogen;
- GP to TP;

(iii) ATP. [2]

- supplies, energy / phosphate;
- (to convert) GP to TP;
- (to) regenerate of RuBP;

Outline the process of the photolysis of water and describe what happens to the products of photolysis. [10]

- PII absorbs light;
- enzyme (in PII) involved;
- to break down water / AW;
- $2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{e}^- + \text{O}_2$;
- oxygen is produced;
- used by cells for (aerobic) respiration;
- or released (out of plant) through stomata;
- protons used to reduce NADP;
- with electrons from PI;
- reduced NADP used in, light independent stage / Calvin cycle;
- to convert GP to TP;
- electrons also used in ETC;
- to release energy for photophosphorylation;
- to produce ATP;
- electrons (from PII) go to PI;
- ref. re-stabilise PI;

Light independent stage; The Calvin cycle

- The light independent (or dark) reactions takes place in stroma and do not require light .
- they make use of the ATP (energy) and NADPH₂ from from the light dependent stage of photosynthesis .
- The biochemistry of these reactions take place where promulgated by Calvin ,Benson and Basham , hence they are known as Calvin –Benson cycle .

1. Carbon dioxide fixation

- The first stage is carbon dioxide fixation or acceptance.
- The carbon dioxide acceptor RuBP a5C compound combines with CO₂ to form a highly unstable 6C compound which quickly breaks down to form to 3C compound to glycerate phosphate.
- The enzyme Ribulose biphoshate carboxylase oxyfenal (Rubisco) catalyse the reaction .

2. Reduction phase

- The glycerate phosphate a 3C acid contains the carboxylic group (COOH) which is reduced to an aldehyde group (-CHO).
- Energy from ATP and hydrogen from NADPH₂ are used to remove oxgen from GP.
- TP is produced a sugar phosphate, the first carbohydrate made in photosynthesis.

3. Regeration of RuBP – the CO₂ Acceptor

- Some of the TP is used to generate the RuBP consumed in the first reaction.
- The regeneration of RuBP involves a complex cycle containing 4,5,6. And 7C sugar phosphates.

Outline/ describe the main features/reactions of the Calvin Cycle.

[9]

- RuBP 5C;
- combines with carbon dioxide;
- rubisco;
- to form an unstable 6C compound;
- which forms 2 X GP (PGA);
- ATP;
- energy source
- and reduced NADP;
- forms TP (GALP);
- TP used to form glucose / carbohydrates 1 lipids / amino acids;
- TP used in regeneration of RuBP
- requires ATP;
- as source of phosphate;

- light independent;
- Grana increase surface area for light absorption

OXIDATIVE PHOSPHORYLATION [ETC]

- ATP is made by addition of inorganic phosphate to ADP are phosphorylation reaction.
- In the respiration process it requires oxygen and is known as oxidative phosphorylation.
- The Krebs cycle takes place in the matrix of the mitochondrion.
- Reduced NAD and FAD provide energy for ATP synthesis as they are passed in the ETC .
- The electrons are passed along ATP is made.
- At the end of the ETC oxygen is used to combine with electrons as they off the chain with hydrogen ions to form water.
- If there's no enough O₂ the ETC wont work and hence resulting in the occurrence of anaerobic respiration .

Describe how ATP is synthesized by oxidative phosphorylation. [8]

- reduced, NAD / FAD ;
- passed to ETC ;
- inner membrane / cristae ;
- hydrogen released (from reduced, NAD / FAD) ; R H₂
- split into electrons and protons ;
- electrons pass along, carriers / cytochromes ;
- ref. energy gradient ;
- energy released pumps protons into intermembrane space ;
- proton gradient ;
- protons pass through (protein) channels ;
- ATP synthase / stalked particles ;
- (ATP produced from) ADP and inorganic phosphate ;
- electron transferred to oxygen ;
- addition of proton (to oxygen) to form water / (oxygen) reduced to water ;

Photosynthetic pathways

- Describe the structural differences between C₃ and C₄ biochemical pathways
- Describe and illustrating C₃ and C₄ pathways
- Discuss Crassulacean acid metabolism (CAM) pathways

Differences between C₄ and C₃ Plants

- Leaves of C₄ plants can be distinguished by having small intercellular spaces, frequent veins, and large bundle-sheath cells which contain abundant chloroplasts. In C₃ plants chloroplasts are present in all the mesophyll cells.
- In C₄ plants there are two types of photosynthetic cells, the large bundle sheath cells around the veins, and the mesophyll cells around the bundle sheath cells.

- The C₄-system also operates efficiently at high temperatures, which makes it adapted for tropical plants.
- C₄-plants show no or little photorespiration and this is another reason why C₄ photosynthesis is highly efficient

Below are brief explanations for reduced photorespiration in C₄ plants

- PEP-carboxylase does not accept oxygen and hence does not contribute to photorespiration.
- The concentration of carbon dioxide is always very high in the bundle sheath cells as a result of their special CO₂-fixing system, so O₂ loses out in the competition for RuBP.
- Because the bundle-sheath cells are completely surrounded by mesophyll cells, carbon dioxide released by the photo-respiration of the bundle-sheath cells is immediately recovered by the carbon dioxide fixing mechanism of the mesophyll cells

The C₄ pathway

- Certain plants (C₄ plants) possess a characteristic leaf anatomy in which two rings of cells are found around each of vascular bundles.
- The inner ring the bundle sheath cells contain chloroplast which differ in form from those in mesophyll cells these are referred to as the kranz anatomy

Hatch slack pathway

- The hatch slack pathway is a pathway for transporting CO₂ from the mesophyll , it's a pumping mechanism for CO₂ .
- The carbon dioxide acceptor is PEP and the reaction is catalysed by PEP carboxylase an efficient enzyme with high affinity for CO₂ and not inhibited by O₂.

Oxaloacetate is then reduced by NADPH₂ to MALATE .

- Malate is then shunted through plasmodesm into the bundle sheath cells where they accepted by RUBP in the normal C₃ pathway .

C₃ and C₄ plants

- C₃ plants have GP and C₄ have a four carbon compound oxaloacetate.
- The enzyme Rubisco is also able to catalyzes the combination of Rubp with oxygen .
- This results in the lose of RuBP which can be used only in the presents of CO₂ from the plant. As this process has the overall effect of taking in O₂ and giving out CO₂ and this is called photorespiration.
- However C₄ prevent photorespiration by keeping Rubp and Rubisco away from O₂. The cells containing these two compounds are arranged around the vascular bundle called bundle sheath.
- They have no direct contact with the air CO₂ is absorbed by the mesophyll cells which are in contact with air space .
- The mesophyll cells contain an enzyme called PEP CARBOXYLASE which catalyses the combination of CO₂ with the three carbon molecule phosphopyruvate.
- The opd made from the reaction is oxaloasetate .

- Still inside the mesophyll cell oxaloacetate is converted to malate and this malate is shunted into the bundle sheath.
- Here CO₂ is removed from the malate and delivered to RuBP by Rubisco in the usual way. The Calvin cycle then proceeds normally.
- Some of the most productive crops are C₄ plants. Sugar cane is especially efficient converting around 8 percent sunlight to energy in carbohydrates.
- *Explain how the anatomy of a C₄ plant is adapted to make it efficient in photosynthesis? [3]*
- *State any 3 ways which a farmer can modify the environment to enhance the photosynthetic efficiency of a C₃ plant. [3]*

CAM-Plants

- A variation of the Hatch-Slack (C₄) pathway is found in several types of succulent plants of hot arid climates. Examples are members of the cactus (Cactaceae) family.
- The stomata of these plants open during the night and close during the day.
- These plants accumulate malate and other organic acids causing an increase in acidity. The phenomenon was called Crassulacean Acid Metabolism (CAM).

Let us now look at how photosynthesis takes place in CAM plants:-

- During the night, when conditions are no longer conducive to transpiration, the stomata of CAM-plants open,
- Carbon dioxide diffuses into the leaf and is fixed by the PEP-carboxylation system to form oxaloacetate (OAA) and malate as in C₄-plants,
- These products are stored in the vacuoles of the mesophyll cells.
- During the day, the stomata are closed to reduce water loss.
- Again, during the day the accumulated malate and other organic acids are de-carboxylated to release CO₂.
- The CO₂ released is supplied to cells that immediately re-fix it via the Calvin cycle using RuBP (remember the Calvin cycle).

We want to conclude that:-

- the biochemical events of the CAM-pathway are similar to those of the Hatch-Slack pathway
- But the PEP and Calvin systems are separated by time rather than by different cells as in the Hatch-Slack pathway.

Cellular respiration

- Describe the process of respiration
- Describe the two distinct pathways for breakdown of starch
 - Glycolysis
 - Krebs's cycle
- Starch mobilization
 - Hydrolytic pathway

- Phospholytic pathway

The Respiration Process

- Respiration in plant cells is basically the oxidation of organic molecules by oxygen from the atmosphere to form CO₂ and water.
- The organic molecules are gradually broken down by a series of enzyme-controlled reactions. Each reaction releases a small amount of energy, some of which is transferred to ATP. The rest of the energy is lost as heat.
- The energy in the ATP can then be used for several energy requiring reactions in the cell.
- The general overall reaction for respiration is:-

- You will notice that this reaction is basically the opposite of photosynthesis. Respiration converts some of the energy captured in photosynthesis into a form that can be used by the cell.
- Respiration is a complex metabolic process of over 70 reactions. During these reactions chemical energy is released, some of which is used to synthesise ATP. These may be conveniently divided into four main stages:
 - I. Glycolysis,
 - II. Link reaction,
 - III. Krebs cycle and,
 - IV. Oxidative phosphorylation.

Glycolysis

Describe the process of glycolysis. [7]

- glucose is phosphorylated by ATP, this raises energy level / overcomes activation energy to form hexose biphosphate ;
- lysis / splitting, of, glucose / hexose
- breaks down to two TP ; A GALP / GADP / G3P / PGAL
- 6C → 2 x 3C ;
- dehydrogenation / description ;
- 2 NAD reduced formed (from each TP to pyruvate formed) ;
- 4 ATP produced / net gain of 2 ATP ;
- pyruvate produced ;
- reduced NAD → oxidative phosphorylation / redox ;

Krebs Cycle

Describe the main features of the Krebs Cycle. [9]

- Occurs in the matrix of mitochondrion;
- acetyl CoA combines with oxaloacetate to form citrate;
- 4C to 6C;
- decarboxylation/produce CO₂;
- dehydrogenation/oxidation;
- 2CO₂ released;
- reduced NAD produced; accept reduced coenzyme for one mark - annotate 9/10
- reduced FAD produced;
- ATP produced;
- series of steps/intermediates;
- enzyme catalysed reactions;
- oxaloacetate regenerated;

Explain the role of NAD in aerobic respiration.

- NAD is coenzyme for dehydrogenase;
- when NAD is reduced carries electrons and protons/H⁺/H/hydrogen from Krebs cycle and from glycolysis to cytochromes/electron transfer chain;
- when NAD is reoxidised/regenerated ATP produced;
- 3/2.5 (molecules of ATP) per reduced NAD;

Starch mobilization:

- The two distinct pathways for the breakdown of starch are hydrolytic and phospholytic pathways.

Hydrolytic pathway

- Starch degradation is initiated by the addition of phosphate group at C6-position and C3-position of individual glucosyl residues.
- these disrupt the packing of the glucan at the granule surface.
- Phosphate additions are catalysed by two enzymes: glucan water dikinase (GWD) and phosphoglucan water dikinase (PWD).
- The hydrolysis of the resulting glucan and phosphoglucan chain is carried out by a suite enzymes, including phosphoglucan phosphatase(SEX4/LSF2), -amylases (BAM3/LDA), -amylase (AMY3), glucan phosphorylase, and the disproportionating enzyme 1(DPE1, an glucanotransferase).
- The product of hydrolytic pathway are maltose and Glutamic acid.
- These are exported to the cytosol by glucase transporter (pGlcT) and maltose transporter (MEX1), to make Sucrose.

Phospholytic pathway

- The product of phospholytic pathway is Glc-1-P (G1P), which is converted to Glc-6-P (G6P), which is used by the pentose phosphate pathway at night and may be used to regenerate the Calvin cycle intermediates during the day.

TOPIC 3: SOIL FERTILITY AND PLANT NUTRITION

SUBTOPIC: SOIL CHARACTERISTICS

Soil chemical properties

- describe the formation of clay and humus colloids.
- describe the basic structure of clays.
- explain the source of negative charges on clay and humus colloids.
- explain the origins and significance of cation exchange and anion exchange capacity (CEC and AEC).
- determine cation exchange capacity (CEC) and base saturation percentage.
- discuss the significance of base saturation and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP).
- discuss the causes of soil acidity and salinity.
- discuss the effects of soil acidity and salinity on crop growth.
- explain methods of correcting soil acidity and salinity

Formation of clay and humus colloids

- clay fraction and humus are referred to collectively as the colloidal fraction, because of their small size and colloid-like properties.
- A **colloid** is a mixture where at least two types of substances (particles) are placed together. The particles do not change, do not settle out of the mixture, and cannot be seen.
- The important functional properties of these colloids may include high specific surface area, electrostatic charges (cations and anions) and adsorption of water.
- Mineral colloids came from various stages of weathering of primary materials or inherited from sediments of old clay formation.
- Humus came from various stages of organic residue decomposition.

Types of Colloids

- Any given soil contains a mixture of both crystalline and amorphous state.
- A crystal is a piece of homogenous substance having natural geometrically regular form with symmetrical arranged plane faces.
- An amorphous material is non crystalline, with no regular geometric form, such as allophane and humus.

Basic structure of clays

Clay minerals can be classified as 1:1 or 2:1, because they are fundamentally built of tetrahedral silicate sheets and octahedral hydroxide sheets.

1:1 Clay (kaolinite group)

- Consists of one tetrahedral layer bonded to one octahedral layer (figure 2.1) eg kaolinite.
- Has strong hydrogen bonds between layers.
- These soils do not allow water to penetrate between layers (non swelling).
- Deprotonation or dissociation of H^+ from OH^- groups at the broken edges of clay particles is the prime source of negative charge in the 1:1 clay minerals.
- High pH values favor this deprotonation of exposed hydroxyl groups.

Properties of 1:1 clays

- Stable and non expanding clay
- Low total charges
- Relative low specific surface area
- pH dependant charges
- Good physical properties
- Limiting holding capacity for nutrients
- Good for roads, buildings, ceramic and bricks.
- Hexagonal shape

2:1 Expanding Clay minerals (smectite group)

- These are formed when an octahedral sheet is sandwiched between two tetrahedral layers .
- The layers are not bonded hence allow water to penetrate between layers eg montmorillonite.
- There is isomorphous substitution with 2:1 clays.
- The more the negative charge created the greater the capacity to retain positively charged nutrients eg K, Na, Ca.

Properties of 2:1 clays eg montmorillonite

- Expanding clays

- Shrinking and swelling constantly
- Poor physical characteristics
- Abundant charges and surface
- Rich in nutrients
- Good soils for crops if managed properly
- Not affected much by pH

Sources of negative charges on clays

1. Isomorphous substitution (IS).

- Isomorphous substitution is defined as the replacement of one atom by another of similar size in the clay lattice, e.g. magnesium (Mg²⁺) replacing aluminium (Al³⁺).
- The magnesium is a divalent (Mg²⁺) while aluminium (Al³⁺) is trivalent. This produces a negative charge in a clay lattice.
- This can be balanced by clay adsorbing (to gather on the surface) a positively charged ion called cation, from the soil solution. If it has a negative charge it is called an anion.
- Ions are atoms or molecules which have gained or lost, one or more valence electron, giving the ion a net positive charge.
- Cations and anions attract one another. Conversely cations repel one another, as do anions.
- However, 2:1 clays have more substitution than 1:1.

An example of isomorphous substitution (IS) and subsequent cation adsorption:

Al³⁺ can be replaced by Fe³⁺ or Mg²⁺

2. Exposed crystal edges.

- The second source of charge involves unsatisfied valencies found at the broken ends or edges of the silicon tetrahedral and aluminium octahedral layers.
- **Exposed crystal edges- positive charge development** -The hydrogen ions may dissociate from the OH groups in the lattice in alkaline solutions and H^+ reacts with the free OH^- ions on solution to form water.
- **Protonation** is the addition of H^+ ion to a hydroxyl group at an exposed crystal edge. When positive charges develop on clays, the clays then adsorb negatively charged ion (anions) to neutralise the charge. The process is therefore called anion adsorption. Anions such as chlorine (Cl^-), sulphate (SO_4^{2-}) and phosphate ($H_2PO_4^-$) can be held on these clays as shown below in Figure 6.5.

Figure 6.5 Positive Charge Developments on Crystal Edge
(Source: Module 1 CSDL 101 Hussein, J. First edition n/d)

- **Exposed crystal edges- negative charge development** - forms the second source of charge that involves unsatisfied valences at the broken ends or edges of the silicon tetrahedral and aluminium octahedral layers.
- The hydrogen ions may dissociate from the OH groups in the lattice in alkaline solutions and the H^+ reacts with free OH^- ions in solution to form water. A net negative charge is then left at the crystal edge.
- This negative charge then attracts cations such as for example (K^+) from solution to neutralise the charge.
- This type of charge is called pH dependent charge because it depends on the dissociation of the OH^- groups, which occurs in response to pH changes in the soil solution.
- This type of charge occurs in all clays, but is responsible for most of the cation adsorption in 1:1 clays, as they have little permanent charge.
- Cations such as calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), potassium (K^+) sodium (Na^+), aluminium (Al^{3+}) and hydrogen (H^+) are commonly adsorbed as shown in below in Figure 6.4.

Figure 6.4: Negative Charge Developments at Crystal Edges
 (Source: Module 1 CSDL 101 Hussein, J. First edition. n/d.)

Importance of isomorphous substitution in soils

- Source of negative charge.
- Increase in attraction of cations or nutrients.
- Reducing leaching of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and K^+ .
- Source of positive charge.
- Al substitute Mg in tetrahedral sheet in vermiculite or chlorite.

Cation exchange

- Cation exchange refers to the interchange between a cation in solution and another cation on the surface of the soil.
- Cation exchange occurs on the surfaces of colloidal sized clay and humus (micelles). Many different cations may be adsorbed on clay colloid.

Figure 6.6: Cation Adsorption on a Clay Colloid
 (Source: Module CSDL 101 Hussein, J. First edition. n/d.)

- However the preferential order of adsorption is:

- Clay will adsorb Al^{3+} in preference to Ca^{2+} if equal concentrations of the cations are present.

- However if a clay micelle with Ca²⁺ is exposed to a increase concentration of K⁺ from fertilizer, then the Ca²⁺ ions can be exchanged for K⁺

- This would occur even if Ca²⁺ is usually preferentially adsorbed compared to K⁺.
- Another example of cation exchange is liming

Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC)

CEC can be defined as:

- The sum total of the exchangeable cations (basic + acidic) that a soil can adsorb.
- The quantity of readily exchangeable cations neutralizing negative charge in the soil.
- Soils capacity to adsorb cations from an aqueous solution of the same pH, ionic strength, dielectric constant and composition as that encountered in the field.

Cation Exchange Capacity is expressed in terms of mmoles of the positive charge per unit mass of soil (mmolescKg-1soil).

- Therefore if a soil has a CEC of 100 mmolescKg-1 this soil is capable of adsorbing 100mmoles of H⁺ and of exchanging with another 100 mmoles of univalent ion (K, Na) or 50mmoles of divalent ion (Ca, Mg). In this case the 100mmoles of negative charge on 1kg of clay is attracting 100mmoles of positive charge. Cations are adsorbed on a chemically equivalent basis ie 1 mmole is satisfied by 1mmole of univalent ions and by ½ of divalent and 1/3 of trivalent ions.
- That is 1mmole of H⁺ (1mg) is exchanged by ½ of Ca²⁺(40mg/2 = 20mg). The CEC values of a soil therefore depends on the amount and type of clay present.

Kaolinite	20- 50mmolescKg-1
Illite	150 - 400 mmolescKg-1
Monmorillonite	800 - 1200 mmolescKg-1

Factors affecting CEC of a soil

- Organic matter
- Clay content
- surface Area ratio
- leaching
- soil texture

What causes variation in CEC of a soil

- amount of organic matter
- clay content of the soil
- amount of surface area ratio; large surface area has high CEC, while those with low surface area ratio have low CEC.
- Leaching levels of the soil
- Soil Texture: fine soils have high CEC, while coarse textured soils have low CEC.

explain the relationship between colloidal and cation exchange capacity (CEC).

- Colloid is negatively charged
- Different cations adsorbed around the colloid
- Amount of cations depend on negative charge.
- Cations are adsorbed in preferential order.
- One cation of higher preferential order may displace one of lower preferential order if concentration are the same/ lyotropic series:

Anion Exchange

- Anion exchange is a chemical process in which anions, in the form of acids, are adsorbed by a basic substitution.
- They undergo exchange on the positively charged sites.
- Anion exchange is less common, but may occur in acid solutions. The diagram below illustrates an example of an anion exchange reaction.

- The reaction is balanced and reversible but proceeds to the right due to excess of nitrate ions.

Humus

- Humus refers to fully decayed organic matter.
- Humus exists as fine colloidal material with large surface area and also has many enolic, carboxylic and phenolic groups which can adsorb cations.
- H^+ dissolves/dissociates from these groups (as the solution becomes alkaline) leaving net negative charge. This charge is pH dependant.

- The CEC value of humus can be as large as 2000mmolescKg-1
- If humus is only 1% of the soil, then the humus will not contribute substantially to the CEC of the soil.

Basic and acidic cations

- Basic cations include Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , and acidic cations include Al^{3+} and H^+
- Cation Exchange Capacity therefore is the sum of all exchangeable basic plus acidic cations.

Base saturation

- The proportions of basic versus acidic cations are important as they give an indication of the degree of weathering and leaching. It also indicates the likely supply of some basic plant nutrients (Ca, Mg, K).
- If the basic cation concentration is low, and acidic cation concentration is high, this indicates, high degree of weathering and leaching and that the soil is likely to be acidic.

$$1. \quad \text{Total Exchangeable Bases (TEB)} \rightleftharpoons \text{exchangeable } Ca^{2+}, Mg^{2+}, Na^+, K^+ \text{ mmolesckg-1}$$

$$TEB \rightleftharpoons Ca + Mg + Na + K$$

$$2. \quad \text{Total Exchangeable Acids (TEA)} \rightleftharpoons \text{Exchangeable } H^+ + Al \text{ mmolesckg-1}$$

$$TEA \rightleftharpoons H + Al$$

$$3. \quad CEC \rightleftharpoons TEB + TEA$$

$$4. \quad \text{Total Exchangeable Bases(\%BS)} \rightleftharpoons \frac{\text{Total Exchangeable Bases}}{\text{Cation Exchange capacity}} * 100$$

Crops grow best when % BS is around 80%

$$5. \quad \text{Percentage Acid saturation (\%AS)} \rightleftharpoons \frac{TEA}{CEC} * 100$$

Soil pH

- The pH gives a measure of soil acidity or alkalinity. It is simply a measure of the hydrogen ion concentration of any given soil. It is therefore driven from the ionization of water that contains both the hydrogen and hydroxide ions.

$$\text{pH} = -\log_{10} [\text{H}^+] \text{ or } \log_{10} \frac{1}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

- Soil pH is an important soil property which affects the availability and uptake of plant nutrients as well as the microbial activity in the soil.
- Soil pH is influenced by % base saturation, addition of fertilizers, liming, type of exchangeable cation, type of clay mineral and concentration of dissolved salts in the soil solution.
- As previously discussed in the first chapter, soil pH is measured by the concentration of H⁺ in the soil solution.
- The exchangeable H⁺ provide the principal source of H⁺ until the pH of the soil decreases below 6. At this point Al ions in the clay lattice may become unstable and dissolve in solution.
- When in solution the Al ions are hydrolysed to produce hydrogen ions.

Therefore Al³⁺ ions are a source of acidity, called Al toxicity in soil.

Factors affecting soil pH / Factors increasing soil acidity

1. Addition of acidifying materials ie addition of ammonium containing fertilizers. Fertilizer containing (NH₄)SO₄ is oxidized in the soil to produce nitrate ions and release H⁺

2. Organic matter decomposition may release acids which increases soil acidity. We have already learnt about this in Unit 3 when we looked at biotic factors affecting soil formation. An example is when organic acids are ionised.

3. Leaching of bases- in sandy soils, bases are leached causing acidity

4. Pollution – rainfall may dissolve gases from industries such as CO₂, nitric oxide and Sulphur dioxide. this forms acid rain which infiltrates soil and lowers pH

5. Root respiration - releases hydrogen ions, providing a natural source of acidity in soils. This takes place when plant roots absorb oxygen root respiration and release carbon dioxide which dissolves in soil water to form weak carbonic acid. Weak carbonic acids dissociates into bicarbonate and hydrogen ions causing an increase in soil acidity.

Factors causing alkalinity

1. Weathering- of basic minerals in soils provide slow release of bases. Base accumulation (low leaching) pH rises. Alkaline soils are likely to be found in low rainfall areas. Hydrolysis of basic parent material (eg limestone) give alkaline soils

2. Poor drainage and high evaporation-Bases accumulate in low lying poorly drained areas. Water evaporates leaving bases hence pH rises. Bases can then move to the surface by evaporation

3. Addition of liming materials

Effects of pH on nutrient availability

- pH affects the solubility of nutrients or their reaction of /fixation by other chemical elements. The release of nutrients from organic matter by microbe is also influenced by pH.
- N, P, S, Ca, Mg, and Mo are usually less available at low pH while Fe, Mn, Cu, and Zn are unavailable at high pH.

Liming

- Commonly soils become acidic with continuous cultivation, to raise the pH, lime, oxides, OH, CO₃ of Ca and Mg is added

Calcium oxide CaO

- Is also called unslaked lime, burnt lime or quick lime. It is a white powder manufactured by roasting calcitic limestone.
- The purity of the burned lime depends on the purity of the raw material. It reacts almost immediately when added to the soil, it should be mixed completely with soil as it rapidly cakes and becomes ineffective.

Ca(OH)₂

- Referred to as slaked lime, hydrated or builders lime. It is a white powdery substance, difficult and unpleasant to handle. It is prepared by hydrating CaO.

CaCO₃ and dolomitic lime MgCO₃

- Is made from mined deposits. Quality depends on impurities

Slags

- Are bi-products of industrial reactions. Eg blast furnace slag is a bi-product of the manufacture of pig iron.
- Liming material is selected on its neutralizing value, its degree of fines and its reactivity. Neutralizing values of all liming materials are determined by comparing them to the neutralizing value of value of pure CaCO₃ (100).

Using a calcium chloride solution for soil test

- ❖ CaCl₂ test method is considered to approximate average soil solution calcium and salinity levels.
- ❖ Measurements are carried out in 0.01Mol CaCl₂ solution with a soil/solution ratio of 1/5. A dilute CaCl₂ solution (0.01M) is used for pH measurements to stimulate actual field conditions in preference to distilled water.
- ❖ When soil is diluted with water, most of the H⁺ ions tend to remain attracted to the soil particles and are not released into the soil solution.
- ❖ Therefore, addition of small amounts of calcium chloride provides Ca²⁺ ions to replace some of the H⁺ ions on soil particles, forcing the hydrogen ions into the solution and making their concentration in the bulk solution closer to that found in the field.
- ❖ The pH measured in CaCl₂ is almost always lower than pH of the same soil measured in water due to the higher concentration of H⁺.

Explain ways of managing soil with low water holding capacity

- Use of drip irrigation
- Addition of organic matter
- Mulching
- Addition of anthill soil
- liming

Relative neutralizing values of different liming materials

Liming material	Relative Neutralising value
Calcium carbonate	100
Dolomitic lime	95- 108
Calcitic lime	95 – 100
Burned lime	150 – 175
Hydrated lime	120 – 135

- Reaction rate of the lime is greatly determined by particle size. Course lime particles react more slowly and less fully.
- Fine lime materials react more rapidly and much more fully. The cost of lime increases with fineness of grid.
- The initial pH, degree of mixing and chemical nature of the material also influences the reaction rate. Oxides and hydroxides react more quickly than carbonates. Over liming of soils result in deficiencies of Zn, Cu, Fe, Mn, and B and increases in Mo sufficient for toxicity.

Saline and Sodic Soils

- Soils may become naturally alkaline though weathering, lack of leaching and poor drainage.
- Exchangeable Sodium Percentage. – used to distinguish between sodic and non-sodic soils

$$\text{ESP} = \frac{\text{Exch Na}}{\text{CEC}} * 100$$

- Soils with an ESP of greater than 9 are classified as sodic in Zimbabwe, they have a very bad structure, poor drainage and hard to work.
- Sodium Adoption Ratio (SAR) is used to separate out sodic soils.

$$SAR = \frac{[Na^+]}{\sqrt{0.5([Ca^{2+}] + [Mg^{2+}])}} \text{ cmolesckg}^{-1}$$

- This shows the relative concentration of Na to Ca, and Mg

Electrical conductivity

- Electrical conductivity (EC) is measured in deciSiemens/m. The greater the quantity of salts the more the solution conducts the electrical current

Saline Soils

- These soils contain mainly Ca and Mg salts. There are enough salts in the soil to seriously impair plant growth. The soil solution has a high osmotic potential and cause plasmolysis of plant cells.
- Salts are brought up to the surface by evaporating water, and they are called white alkali soils. Salinity results in soil flocculation.
- Saline-sodic soils have appreciable quantities of Ca/Mg and enough Na to affect plants. These soils are more difficult to work.

Sodic soils

- Have very high Na concentrations. The soil pH is greater than 8.5 due to the hydrolysis of water by Na

- Conditions results in toxicity of nutrients ie too much availability of other nutrients
- The increase in pH cause fixation of many plant nutrients. The sodium destabilizes clay, causing its dispersion. Infiltration of rainfall is therefore reduced due to the dispersed clay which clogs pores. Sodic soils develop from granite or karoo formations in drier areas as these are rich in Na minerals. Sodium has the opposite effects of salinity on soils, that is, the forces that bind clay particles together get disrupted when too many large sodium ions come between them.

Chemical properties of normal, acid, and saline/sodic soils

Soil	pH	ESP	SAR	ECsat
Normal Zimbabwe	5.5 – 6.5	Less than 1	Less than 13	Less than 4
Acid Zimbabwe	Less than 5	Less than 1	Less than 13	Less than 4
Saline	Less than 8.5	Less than 15	Less than 13- 15	Greater than 4
Saline sodic	Less than 8.5	Greater than 15	Greater than 13- 15	Greater than 4
Sodic	Greater than 8.5	Greater than 15	Greater than 13- 15	Greater than 4
Sodic Zimbabwe	-	Greater than 9	-	-

The significance of base saturation and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP).

- Base saturation indicates the balance between acid and base cations adsorbed by the cation exchange complex (CEC) of soil.
- Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) is used to distinguish between sodic and nonsodic soils. Sodic soils have an ESP greater than 9, within the top 800mm of soil.
- Sodic soils have very high Na concentrations. The soil pH is greater than 8.5 due to the hydrolysis of water by sodium.

Problems that can be experienced in soils with high exchangeable sodium (ESP)

- High pH: o Soil pH is usually high, often greater than 8.4. o Carbonate become dominant form of alkalinity.
 - o *Cause injury or poor plant growth:*
- Salts at high concentrations, seriously impair plant growth or can kill plants.
 - o *Destroy soil structure:*
- Sodic soils tend to develop poor structure and drainage over time because sodium ions on clay particles cause the soil particles to deflocculate, or disperse (move apart from each other). o Sodium affected soils tend to swell when wet and to harden and crack when dry. When dry, sodic soil develops a hard dry crust on the surface.
 - o *Reduced water uptake:*
- The presence of salt in the soils reduces the availability of water to plants. Water and air movement through sodic soils is severely restricted due weakened
- aggregates in the clay soil, causing structural collapse and closing-off of soil pores.
 - o *Salinization:*
- In saline soils, the soil solution has a high osmotic potential and cause plasmolysis of plant cells.
 - o *Deficiency of other nutrients:*
- Salt affected soils are generally low in available nutrients.
 - o *Soil crusting:*
- Sodicity of the surface soil is likely to cause dispersion of surface aggregates, resulting in surface crusts.
- Hard crust restricts root growth and seed emergence.
 - o Subject to erosion:
- Soil erosion results in soil and nutrient loss.
- The runoff containing the nutrients and pesticides which are adsorbed on the clay particles, might reach drinking water sources and contaminate them.
 - Affect micro-organisms:*
- Poor soil aeration affects microbial activity.

SOIL SAMPLING

Soil sampling is a process of collecting quantities of soil from the various parts of the field for the purpose of analysing it in the laboratory.

Sample locations can be chosen using (a) haphazard or zigzag sampling pattern or (b) traversing pattern.

The importance of soil sampling

It provides information on the average nutrient status of the soil. This is important in determining the type and amount of fertilizer to apply.

It helps in knowing the soil pH number. This is important in determining whether nutrients are available or less available to plants.

What to consider when taking soil samples

To help ensure accurate recommendations, the sampler should avoid sampling areas such as:

- cultivated furrows, anthills, old roadways and yards,
- water channels, manure piles, and eroded knolls,
- depressions, terrace channels, saline areas, fence lines, and field edges.

Reasons why farmers would send soil sample for analysis

- To determine soil factors such as pH, structure, texture, organic matter and fertility.
- To establish type and amount of lime and fertilizer to apply.
- To produce high economic returns.

TOPIC 3: PRINCIPLES OF CROP BREEDING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

SUBTOPIC: PLANT BREEDING METHODS

Plant Introduction

- Explain plant introduction as a breeding method.
- Describe types of plant introduction.
- Discuss advantages and disadvantages of plant introduction.

Meaning of plant introduction.

- Plant introduction is the movement of new varieties from one environment into another of similar characteristics, within a country or from other regions.
- The process may involve new varieties of crop or the wild relatives of the crop species or totally new crop species for the area.
- These new varieties can be used as they are or can be used in breeding programmes to improve local varieties.

Types of plant introduction.

Based on adaptation

- **Primary introduction:** Variety is well adapted to the new environment, released for commercial cultivation without any alteration in the original genotype.
- **Secondary introduction:** Introduced variety may be subjected to selection and hybridization to isolate a superior variety.

Based on utilisation

- **Direct introduction:** New variety takes no time for establishment.
- **Indirect introduction:** New variety takes some time for establishment.

Objectives of plant introduction.

- To get new sources of resistance against both biotic and abiotic stresses.
- To enrich the germplasm (living genetic resources such as seed or another plant part) collecting e.g. groundnuts.
- To introduce high yielding varieties to increase food production.
- To introduce new plant species thereby creating ways to build up new industries.

Advantages of plant introduction.

- it protects the variability from genetic erosion by collecting germplasm.
- It provides superior crop by introducing into new disease free areas.

Disadvantages of plant introduction.

- Introduction of noxious weeds e.g. water hyacinth.
- Introduction of disease e.g. late blight of potatoes from Europe, and Bunchy top of Banana from Ceylon.
- introduction of pests, e.g. potato tuber moth from Italy.
- Ornamentals turned weeds, e.g. Lantana camara.
- Threat to ecological balance, e.g. Eucalyptus species introduced from Australia.

Plant selection

- Explain selection as a method of plant breeding.
- Describe types of selection in plant breeding.
- Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of plant selection.

Selection in plant breeding

- Selection is a process of allowing certain plants to be parents of future generations.
- The chosen plants are supposed to be carriers of desirable genes that make them produce better.
- The rejected ones are supposed to be carriers of undesirable genes that depress their productivity.

Types of plant selection

Natural selection

- It is a process that operates in nature without human interference. Plants that survive through the adversities of nature are preferred and the weaker are wiped out (Survival of the fittest).
- natural selection has given the cultivated crops and “ecotype” in plants.

Artificial selection

- Eye is the powerful tool in artificial selection.
- Man decides on which crop individuals to use in the next generation.
- Farmer looks at characteristics like yield, quality, disease tolerance, and height.
- An understanding of botanical characteristics is needed.

Methods of artificial selection

Mass selection.

- This is a selection of a number of phenotypically superior plant heads or seed from the field population.
- It is based on phenotype (external character) and the harvested seeds are composited with progeny testing.
- Most vigorous plants from the mixed population of a crop are selected.

Progeny selection.

- This is commonly used in cross pollination, and often cross pollinated crops.

- Progeny (offspring) is a new individual organism that results from the process of sexual or asexual reproduction.

Pure-line selection.

- Pure-line selection is a process of selecting a desirable homozygous individual from the mixed population and multiply the same without contamination to release a new individual.

Clonal selection.

- A clone is a variety propagated vegetative from a single plant.
- Clonal selection is the selection and propagation of the desirable variations between the clones as well as within the clone.
- It is practical with non-flowering plants and those species which produce seed poorly.

Hybridization

- Explain methods of hybridization
- Describe advantages and disadvantages of hybridization.
- Describe hybrid seed production.
- Compare hybrid seed and, traditional and commercial open- pollinated varieties (OPVs) performances.

- **Hybridization** refers to the natural or artificial process of combining varieties or species of crops to create a hybrid.
- A **hybrid** is an offspring of two plants of different varieties, with characteristics that are better than either of their parents.
- **Heterosis or hybrid vigour** is the increase in growth, size, fecundity, or yield in the offspring.

Objectives of hybridisation

- To combine the desired characters into a single individual.
- To exploit and utilize the hybrid varieties.
- To artificially create a variable population for the selection of types with desired combination characters.

Types of hybridization

- Intraspecific or inter-variatal hybridization:** -The crosses are made between the plants belonging to two different varieties.
- Intra-variatal hybridization:** - The crosses are made between the plants of the same variety.
- Interspecific or intragenric hybridization:** - The crosses are made between two different species of the same genus.
- Introgressive hybridization:** -The transfer of some genes from one species into the genome of the other species.

Advantages and disadvantages of hybridization.

Advantages

- Crossing two parental individuals gives chance for formation of new genetic recombinants and increase viability.
- Widened selection base exploits hybrid vigour or heterosis.
- Offspring with better characteristics are produced.
- The characteristics include, drought resistance, growth rate and improved yield.

Disadvantages

- Seed is expensive.
- Seed production requires expertise.
- Seed production takes a long time.
- New seed must be bought for each planting season, to maintain high yields.

Procedure of hybridisation

It involves the following steps:

Selection of parents.

Parental plants are selected from the local areas and are supposed to be best suited to the existing conditions.

Selfing of parents or artificial self-pollination.

It is essential for inducing homozygosity for eliminating the undesirable characters and obtaining inbreeds.

Emasculation.

Inbreeds are grown under normal conditions and are emasculated. Emasculation is the removal of stamens from female parent before they burst and shed their pollens. Emasculation is not essential for unisexual plants.

Bagging.

The emasculated flower or inflorescence is immediately bagged to avoid pollination by any foreign pollen. The bags are tied to the base of the inflorescence or to the stalk of the flower with the help of a thread.

Tagging.

Tags with information of the emasculated flower are attached at the base of the flower.

Crossing.

Mature, fertile and viable pollens from the male parent are placed on the receptive stigma of emasculated flowers to bring about fertilisation. Pollen grains are collected in paper bags (maize) or

petri dishes (wheat) and applied to the receptive stigmas with a camel hair brush, tooth pick or forceps.

Harvesting and storing the F1 seeds.

Crossed heads or pods of desirable plants are harvested. They are threshed or shelled after complete drying. Seed are stored with the original tags.

Raising the F1 generation.

Stored seeds are sown separately to raise the F1 generation. The plants of the F1 generation are hybrids.

Methods of improving of self-fertilized crops

1. Pedigree method

- Pedigree is a record of ancestry of an individual selected plant for various generations.
- Pedigree breeding is a selection method which is used to in segregating population of self-pollinated species and keeps proper record of plants and progeny selected in each generation.

2. Bulk method or Breeding

- Bulk method is a selection procedure which is used in segregating population of self-pollinated species in which material is grown in bulk plot from F1 to F5 with or without selection, next generation is grown from bulk seed and individual plant selection is practiced in in F6 or later generation.

3. Single seed descent method

- This is a breeding procedure used with segregating population of self-pollinated species in which plants are advanced by single seeds from one generations to the next.

4. Back cross method

- This is a method employed to in improvement of both self and cross- pollinated crops where varieties are deficient in one or two aspects.
- A single inheritance character like disease, frost or drought tolerance is transferred from an undesirable variety to good commercial variety.
- The desirable variety, called recurrent or recipient parent, is crossed to an undesirable variety called donor or non-recurrent parent.

5. Multiple cross or composite cross method

- This is a cross involving more than one inbred line.
- It is used to cross monogenic characters from different sources onto a single genotype.
- Several pure lines are crossed together, e.g. as A x B x C X D x E X F.
- F1 plants are mated together as [A x B] x [C x D] and [E x F] x [G x H]. The F1 plants are finally crossed with each other to produce hybrids, [A x B] x [C x D] x [E x F] x [G x H].

Hybridization Methods of Plant Breeding in Cross Pollinated crops

Principles of Hybrids

- Maize is normally cross-pollinated, and this maintains the plant vigour
- The principle of maize hybrids is based on the concept of hybrid vigour – achieved by crossing two unrelated and distinct parents, giving higher yields than the parents.
- The parents are normally developed by inbreeding maize to develop uniform but less vigorous inbred lines, and then crossing these to re-energize the hybrid plant
- Pollination of the maize must therefore be controlled
- For developing the inbred parents, the pollen from the plant is applied to the silks of the same plant
- For creating the hybrid, the pollen from the male must be applied to the silks of the female

TYPES OF HYBRID SEED

Single cross or single hybrid:

- hybrid obtained from a cross between two inbred-lines
- these are high yielding, but have limited adaptability

Double cross hybrids / double hybrids:

- obtained from a cross between two single crosses.

3- way hybrids/crosses

- obtained from a cross between a single cross and an inbred line
- have wide adaptability; medium level yields but can reach 10t/ha with optimum conditions and top management.

Top-cross hybrid: obtained from a cross between a single cross or an inbred line and an OPV

Varietal cross: obtained from a cross between two OPVs.

Open –Pollinated variety (OPV): A heterogeneous variety of a cross-pollinated crop that is allowed to inter-pollinate freely during seed production.

Inbred line: A relatively true-breeding strain obtained from at least five successive generations of regulated self-fertilization or back-crossing to a recurrent parent. (Singh, 1988). True breeding cvs that result from enforced self-pollination of selected parent plants followed by continued selection of to a desired type in succeeding generations. Once a desired cv of this type has been selected, it is maintained by growing plants in isolation and allowing them to cross-pollinate or self-pollinate naturally.

Pure line:

- Group of plants that have nearly the same homozygous genotype and that breed true.
- A strain which all members of have descended by self-pollination from a single homozygous individual
 - is genetically pure (homozygous) e.g inbred lines
 - inbred lines are maintained by self or sib pollinations
- A genetically pure strain in which all individuals have descended by self-fertilization, from a single homozygous individuals (Singh, 1988).

- A population of self-pollinated plants that have been selected to a standard by eliminating off-type plants and fixing the characters of the cultivar through consecutive generations of self-pollination.(All descendants are from a single homozygous plant).

Synthetic /composite line: Is composed of plants produced by combining a number of genetically distinct, but phenotypically similar lines which have been allowed to cross-pollinate at random.

Hybrid type	Model for crossing
Single cross hybrid (SC)	A x B
Three-way cross hybrid (3W)	(A x B) x C
Double cross hybrid (DC)	(A x B) x (C x D)
Top-cross hybrid (TC)	(A x B) x OPV or OPV x A

Hybrids

Advantages of growing hybrid maize are:

1. Hybrids are generally higher yielding than open pollinated varieties.
2. Hybrids are uniform in colour, maturity and other plant characteristics which enables the producer to carry out certain operations (for example fertilising, spraying and harvesting) at the same time.
3. The uniformity of the grain harvested can also have marketing advantages when sold to buyers with quality standards.
4. Hybrid yield on average 18% more than OPV.

Disadvantages of growing hybrids:

1. Seed is expensive.
2. The producer needs to yield more than two ton per hectare to justify the higher cost of seed.
3. New seed needs to be purchased every planting season.
4. The grain produced from hybrid seed may not be used as seed for the following planting seasons.
5. The producer might not be able to source seed timeously.
6. Hybrids are more susceptible to stress conditions (for example tasselling).
7. Under poor crop management and harsh environmental conditions, the yield advantage of hybrids over OPV's is diminished.

Open Pollinated Varieties (OPVs)

- an OPV variety is one whose seed is produced by random cross pollination (that is there is no pollination control).
- The pollination of the plants in the field is not controlled, which means the crop will not be uniform, for example the crop will vary in plant height, the colour of silks will vary, the cobs will not be the same size and shape and the plants will mature at different times.

Advantages of growing OPV:

1. Low or no seed cost. The producer can keep part of the crop for seed.
2. The cost of seed is a lot less than hybrid seed.
3. More money can be spent on buying fertiliser or pesticide.

4. Seed can be recycled. That is grain from this season can be planted next season.
5. Low potential areas cannot justify the high cost of hybrid seed.
6. OPV have a broader genetic base and are more variable in flowering dates. This results in a longer flowering period, which will enable an OPV to pollinate during short periods of high stress (for example moisture stress, temperature, etc.). This variation can at times, offer more stable yields than more uniformly flowering hybrids.
7. It is important to buy certified seed every three years to maintain genetic purity.

Disadvantages of OPV:

1. The yield potential is typically 10 - 25% less.
2. In high potential areas, OPV's will reduce profit margins.
3. They will not be uniform in colour, maturity and other plant characteristics.
4. Could impact on the price of the grain, i.e. quality.
5. Lack of uniformity may lead to difficulties in carrying out certain operations, such as spraying and harvesting, (especially when using a combine harvester).
6. To keep an OPV pure, it should be planted at least 300 m from other varieties.
7. Poor seed quality (seed kept for planting of the next crop is usually stored in poor conditions and is exposed to high temperature, pests and diseases) can result in poor germination and weak plants that cannot compete well with weeds.
8. OPV's are not genetically modified to exhibit insect or herbicide resistance.

Explain the advantages of using hybrid seed in groundnuts or soyabeans or soya beans production.

- hybrid seed can have up to 25% higher yields
- crop is physically uniform
- farmers can use machine to perform operation during production
- hybrid often show greater vigour and faster growth
- pest resistant
- quality of produce is improved
- Drought tolerance
- they also tend to easily adopt to the environment
- have long self-life.

discuss the principle used in hybrid seed production [10]

- distance isolation to prevent contamination through distance of 360m. Plant boarder rows prevent contamination.
- time isolation can also be used. This is achieved by preventing sulking of female when there is more pollen from unwanted plant.
- preventing of selfing of crop parent this can be achieved by timely detaselling of females
- removing of unwanted plants.
- optimisation of cross pollination by increasing number of males than females.

Genetic engineering

- Describe genetic engineering as a breeding method.
- Discuss advantages and disadvantages of genetically modified crops.

- **Genetic engineering** also known as **recombinant DNA technology**, is any technique that uses organisms or parts of living organisms to produce a Genetically Modified Organism (GMO) with a new genotype.
- Genetic modification of plants involves adding a specific stretch of DNA into the plant's genome, giving it new or different characteristics.
- Genetic engineering allows the direct transfer of one or just a few genes of interest, between either closely or distantly related organisms to obtain the desired agronomic trait.
- The new DNA becomes part of the GM plant's genome (complete set of DNA).
- Traits that have been modified in GM crops:
 - GM crops are engineered for insect resistance.
 - Herbicide tolerant soybean, maize and cotton.
 - Insect resistant maize, cotton, potato, and rice.
 - Virus resistant squash and papaya.
 - Slow ripening tomatoes and Freeze resistant potatoes.
- For example, insect resistant crops contain genes from the soil bacterium (*Bacillus thuringiensis*).
- The protein produced in the plant by the *Bacillus thuringiensis* gene is toxic to a target group of insects.
- Plants may be modified by removing or switching off their own particular genes.

Comparing conventional breeding and genetic engineering

Conventional Breeding	Genetic Engineering
-----------------------	---------------------

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited to exchanges between the same or very closely related species • Little or no guarantee of any particular gene combination from the millions of crosses generated • Undesirable genes can be transferred along with desirable genes • Takes a long time to achieve desired results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows the direct transfer of one or just a few genes, between either closely or distantly related organisms • Crop improvement can be achieved in a shorter time compared to conventional breeding • Allows plants to be modified by removing or switching off particular genes
--	--

The process of genetic engineering

- Identify a trait of interest from nature.
 - Isolate the genetic trait of interest from the DNA. N.B. Part of an organism's genetic makeup that contains the trait of interest must be decoded.
 - Insert the desired trait into a vector and clone to make multiple copies of gene of interest.
 - Incorporate the gene into plasmid (a small piece of DNA). The DNA or gene along with the plasmid is called recombinant DNA.
 - Grow the GMO.
- The most common methods used to introduce the gene package into plant cells include biolistic transformation (using a gene gun) or Agrobacterium-mediated transformation.

A) TISSUE CULTURE

- Plant tissue culture is a collection of techniques used to maintain or grow plant cells, tissue, or organism under sterile conditions on a nutrient culture medium of known composition.
- Types of tissue culture techniques are listed below.

1. Micro propagation

Micro propagation is the application of tissue culture techniques to propagation of plants starting with very small plant parts grown aseptically in a test tube or other container.

Advantages

- Plantlets produced are free from bacteria and fungi.
- Small pieces of plants (explants) are used to produce a large number of plants in a small space.
- Plantlets can be stored in vitro in small area and, less space and labour are required for the maintenance of stock plants.
- Nutrient levels, light, temperature and other factors can be more readily controlled to accelerate vegetative multiplication and regeneration.
- It is independent of seasons and requires minimal attention between subcultures.

Disadvantages

- Requires some advanced skills and specialised equipment and facilities.
- Propagules are very expensive because of the labour intensive methods used.
- Plantlets are very small initially.
- Each species requires its own specific methods in order to get optimum results.

2. Embryo culture

- Embryo culture is a technique that involves the removal of the embryo seed and subsequent growth in-vitro until the developing plant can be transferred to soil and grown to maturity.

Advantages

- The technique overcomes unviability problems from crosses between distantly related species.
- Prolonged seed dormancy is overcome.
- It can be used to develop important plant from embryos that are denied the chance to mature due to untimely death of parent.
- It can be used to produce plants from seeds of species that are normally propagated by vegetative means, like banana.

3. Somatic embryogenesis

- It is the development of embryo like structures from cells of non-sexual origin.
- Embryo formation can be artificially induced in cell cultures by manipulation of hormones, light intensity and other growth conditions.

4. Meristem culture

- Meristem culture involves the removal of a dome of actively dividing cells of about 0.1mm in diameter, and 0.25mm in length, and subsequent culture in-vitro.

5. Somaclonal variation

- Somaclonal variation is the use of tissue culture to produce variants that may be lacking or needed in breeding programme.
- Variation is exploited to create suitable varieties and hybrids.

6. In-vitro selection

- This technique is used in identifying plants which have some resistance or tolerance to stresses produced by phytotoxins from pathogens, herbicides, cold temperatures and aluminium, manganese and salt toxicity.

7. Anther culture

- It is a technique of producing haploid plants through the removal of anthers and/or immature pollen from a plant and placing them on suitable culture medium which will induce regeneration from the haploid tissue of microspore or pollen.

8. Protoplast culture

- These are cells from which the cell wall has been removed, but they possess membrane and all other cellular components.
- The technique creates new plant cultivars through fusion of protoplasts from unrelated species.
- This process is also referred to as somatic hybridisation or protoplast fusion.
- Protoplasts are isolated by two techniques: mechanical and enzymatic.
- **Mechanical method:** A small piece of epidermis from a plant is selected. They are subjected to plasmolysis, causing the protoplasts to shrink away from the cell wall.
- **Enzymatic method:** Protoplasts can be isolated from leaves, roots, shoot apices, fruits and microspores. Enzymes that digest the cell wall are required.

b) GENE TRANSFER.

- Vectors containing the genes we want must be incorporated into living cells so that they can be replicated or expressed.
- The cells receiving the vector are called host cells, and once they have successfully incorporated the vector they are said to be transformed.
- Vectors are large molecules which do not readily cross cell membranes, so the membranes must be made permeable in some way.
- There are different ways of doing this depending on the type of host cell. An example is plant tumours.

Benefits of genetic engineering in crop improvement

- Growth rate is improved.
- Modifying plants to introduce disease or insect resistance.
- Improving nutritional quality and yield in crops.
- Producing herbicide and drought tolerant crop.

Disadvantages of genetically modified crops

- Loss of genetic pool.
- Contamination of local varieties.
- Need to buy seed every season.
- Loss of desirable recombinants after independent assortment.
- Destabilization of ecological balance.
- Narrows genetic base and is expensive.

TOPIC 4: PRINCIPLES OF CROP PROTECTION

SUBTOPIC: WEEDS, INSECT PEST AND DISEASE MANAGEMENT

Safety precautions

- Describe safe handling of agro-chemicals.
- Outline safe storage procedures for agro-chemicals.
- Outline safe disposal of agro-chemicals.

Precautions to be followed when using pesticides

- Avoid contact with the skin.
- Wear protective clothing such as respirator, rubber gloves, rubber boots, goggles and overall.
- Read instructions for correct dilution and mixing.
- Do not drink, eat or smoke.
- Use on correct crop or situation.
- Spray down wind.
- Avoid spraying on very windy conditions.

Protective clothing

Precautions to be followed when storing pesticides

- Store in original container to retain the label, and reduce risk of wrong use.
- Keep container tightly closed to prevent spillage.
- Store in secure places, out of reach by children.

- Keep apart from food and foodstuffs.

Avoidance of pollution during use and disposal

- Avoid spraying on very windy conditions.
- Destroy empty containers. Do not use for any other purpose.
- Do not contaminate ponds and waterways.
- Avoid working in spray mist.
- Empty container completely, and dispose of safely.

Toxicity levels of agro-chemicals

Coloured triangles are used to show the degree of toxicity of a chemical.

Weed management

- Outline the importance of weed management.
 - Determine effective timing of weeding.
 - Describe the methods of weed management.
 - Evaluate weed management methods.
- **Weed Management** refers to how weeds are manipulated so that do not interfere with the growth, development and economic yield of crops and animals.
 - It encompasses all aspects of weed control, prevention and modification in the crop habitat that interfere with weed ability to adapt to its environment.

Weed control:

- Weed control refers to those actions that seek to restrict the spread of weeds and destroy or reduce their population in a given location. The effectiveness of weed control is affected by:
 - Type of crop grown
 - Timing of weeding operation
 - Nature of the weed problem
 - Methods of weed control available to the farmer
 - Type of weeds to be controlled
 - Cost of the operation
 - Available labour or cash resources

- Environmental
- condition before during and after the time of operation.

Weed prevention:

- Weed prevention refers to the exclusion of a particular weed problem from the system that has not experienced that weed problem. It involves those measures necessary to prevent the introduction of new weed species into a given geographical area as well as the multiplication and spread of existing weed species. It includes the following:
 - Fallowing.
 - Preventing weeds from setting seeds.
 - Use of clean crop seed for planting.
 - Use of clean machinery.
 - Controlling the movement of livestock.
 - Quarantine laws services.

Weed eradication:

- This involves complete removal of all weeds and their propagules from a habitat.
- Eradication is difficult to achieve in crop production and uneconomical. However in situations where weed problem becomes so overwhelming, eradication may be desirable in long term goal. E.g. *Striga asiatica*, *S. hermonthica*. Eradication may be considered if:
 - other weed control methods are ineffective,
 - Weeds have many buried seeds that cannot be controlled by conventional practice.
 - The infested field is small.
 - Benefits from eradication outweigh those of the alternate methods for coping with weeds.

WEED CONTROL TECHNIQUES

1. Cultural method

- Cultural weed management is defined as any practice or effort adopted by the farmer in crop production which minimizes weed interference problem .
- Cultural weed methods include:
 - Hand weeding.
 - Mulching smother weeds by excluding light from them.
 - Crop Rotation.
 - Tillage.
 - Burning crop residues destroy weed seeds in the process.
 - Flooding.
 - Sowing/planting time and crop spatial management.
 - Crop genotype choice.
 - Cover crop (used as Living mulches).
 - Intercropping maize with cowpeas reduces *Striga asiatica*
 - Fertilization.

2. Mechanical method

- Animal or tractor drawn machinery, including hand hoe is used to control weeds. The implements are used after the crop has emerged.

3. Chemical method

- Chemicals that are used for killing weeds or suppress the plant growth are called herbicides. The practice of killing the undesirable vegetation (that is weeds) with herbicide is called chemical weed control.

Basis of herbicide classification

- Herbicides are classified based on the following:

Time of application (When applied).

- There are three groups:
 - **Pre-plant incorporated herbicides:** These are applied before planting.
 - **Pre-emergence herbicides:** They are herbicides applied before emergence of both the weed and the crop.
 - **Post emergence herbicides:** They are applied either when both the crop and the weed has emerged.

Points of application (Where applied).

- Point of application is either the foliage or the soil. Herbicides applied on foliage enter the plant through the foliage, e.g. Glyphosate.

Systemic and contact herbicides

- Contact herbicides destroy only the plant tissue they come in contact with. These are usually fast acting. Examples of contact herbicides are paraquat, diquat and buctril.
- Systemic herbicides are translocated throughout the plant either from leaves or stem to the roots or from the roots to the leaves. Systemic herbicides are usually slow acting but can control perennial weeds better than contact herbicides. • Examples of systemic herbicides are roundup or glyphosate.

Type of plants killed (Selectivity).

Herbicides can be divided into two groups depending on their selectivity.

- Selective herbicides, kill specific targets they come in contact with, while leaving the desired crop relatively unharmed.
- Non-selective herbicides, kill any plants they come in contact with. They may be translocated.

Chemical structure (Chemistry).

- Herbicides may be classified as (i) organic and (ii) inorganic herbicides,
- e.g. Diphenal ethers and sodium borate, respectively.

Physiological action.

The physiological actions affected by herbicides include:

- Photosynthetic inhibitors, e.g. atrazine.
 - ❖ inhibit biosynthesis pathways;
 - ❖ block xylem vessels;
 - ❖ degradation of cells;
 - ❖ closing stomata;
 - ❖ disturb the electron transport system;
 - ❖ interfere on light reactions;
 - ❖ interfere with structure and integrity of chloroplasts;
 - ❖ interfere with reproductive development;
- Seedling shoot inhibitors.
- Seedling root inhibitors.
- Nitrogen metabolism inhibitors, e.g. atrazine.
- Respiration inhibitors.
- Pigment inhibitors.
- Mitotic poisons.
- Growth regulators.

Herbicide formulation and Surfactants

- Formulation is combining the pure chemicals (the active ingredient) of a herbicide with appropriate solvents, diluents or surfactants. This is done to improve handling, storage, application, efficacy and safety.
- In order to produce a good commercial herbicide, the formulation, good chemical additives such as emulsifiers, wetting agents and inert materials to make a new herbicide formulation should be maintained.
- Surfactants are chemicals that enhance emulsifying, dispersing, wetting, spreading, and penetrating properties.

Reasons why herbicides are formulated:

- To reduce the concentration of the active ingredient through dilution in appropriate solvent.
- To make the pure chemical available in a form that will permit uniform distribution of target.
- To reduce the level of contamination and hazard during handling and application.
- To improve the efficacy of the herbicide through slow release of the active ingredient.
- Better protection from degradation.
- Greater uptake by the weed.
- To reduce cost of weed control with that particular herbicide. For example, the choice of wettable powder over emulsifiable concentrate and vice-versa may be, based to a large extent on which of the formulation is easy to produce and market.

Types of herbicide formulation

- Water soluble (WSC, SL)
- Oil soluble (OS)
- Emulsifiable concentrate (EC)
- Wettable powder (W or WP)
- Flowable formulation (FW, F)

- Granular Formulations (G)
- Water Dispersible Granules (EDG, SG, DG)
- Herbicide-coated pellets (P) or granules (G)
- Water Soluble Pellets (SP)

Advantages of using herbicides

- Can suppress weed germination.
- Can be used without loss of efficacy under wet conditions.
- More effective than other methods of weed control when properly used.
- Faster than manual and cultural weed control.
- Less labour is needed.
- Less likely to be adversely affected by erratic weather condition.
- Weed free, and improved yields are obtained.
- Pre-emergence application of herbicides protects crops from the adverse effects of early weed competition.
- More effective against perennial weeds.

Disadvantages

- Herbicides may be ineffective due to soil conditions.
- Weeds become resistant due to prolonged and constant use of a given herbicide.
- Crop injury as a result of poor sprayer calibration or wrong dosage calculation, faulty equipment or failure to follow label directions
- There could be side effect on the applicator.
- Required knowledge about the herbicide is needed.
- Adsorption by soil colloids.
- Has residual effect on subsequent crops.
- Expensive for poor resource farmer.
- Environmental hazard.
- Can be lost through volatilization.
- Proper calibration is needed.
- Can damage crops if over used.

Biological method

- Biological weed management refers to the use of biological agent – pest, predators, pathogen and parasites to control weeds.
- It involves the control or suppression of weeds through the action of one or more organisms by natural means, or by manipulation of the weeds, organism or environment. It involves:
 - ❖ Control of weeds with vertebrates and invertebrates (Macrobial weed control).
 - ❖ Use of micro-organisms such as plant pathogen (microbial weed control).
 - ❖ Live mulch: Live mulch is the crop production system in which a food crop is planted directly in the living cover of an established cover without destruction of the fallow (cover crop vegetation).
 - ❖ Perennial legumes such as *Psophocarpus palustris*, have been evaluated and found suitable as live mulch.

Reasons why biological methods of weed control are not widely used by farmers

- predators may not be available.
- needs time to study the pest natural enemy relationships.
- new predator-crop relationships.
- natural enemy takes time to establish.
- natural enemy may not establish/adapt to new climate.
- take time to multiply to effective levels of populations.
- it is a slow method.
- ineffective method.
- plant natural enemies may compete for nutrients. -lack of knowledge.

Integrated Weed Management (IWM)

- Integrated weed management (IWM) refers to the system of combining two or more weed management systems at low input level to keep weed interference in a given cropping system below economic threshold level.
- It combines two or more weed management systems at low inputs to obtain a level of weed suppression superior to that ordinarily obtained when one weed management system is used.
- IWM may involve combinations of cultural plus chemical, cultural plus biological, cultural plus preventive, biological plus chemical or combinations of three or more of these systems.

Factors that make IWM desirable

- Inability of any one method of weed control to completely solve the weed problem.
- Tendency of weeds to adapt to a given cropping system and thus escape control.
- Ability of weeds to develop resistance to a frequently used herbicide.
- Tendency of certain cropping systems to favour the dominance of specific weeds.
- Seasonal fluctuation in labour availability.
- Reduction in environmental degradation/hazards.

Types of Integrated Weed Management Practices

There are three main types of agronomic practices that you can use to develop your integrated weed management program:

- Practices that limit the introduction and spread of weeds (prevent weed problems before they start).
- Practices that help the crop compete with weeds (help "choke out" weeds).
- Practices that keep weeds "off balance" (make it difficult for weeds to adapt).

Pest management

- Explain the importance of pest management.
- Explain economic threshold and economic injury levels of pests.
- Describe methods of pest management.
- Compare and contrast pest management methods.

Economic injury levels (EIL) and Economic threshold (ET) of pests

- i. **Economic injury level** is the smallest number of insects (amount of injury) that will cause yield losses equal to the insect management costs.
- ii. **Economic threshold** refers to the pest density at which management action should be taken to prevent an increasing pest population from reaching the economic injury level.

Cultural methods

These are practices that break life cycles of pests when cultivating crops, for example,

- Crop rotation breaks pest life cycle and reduces their population,
- Weeding destroys pest habitat.
- Early planting allows pest to emerge when crop has fully established.
- Field hygiene such as burning or destruction of crop residues.
- Growing resistant varieties.
- Use of legislation that prevents introduction of new pests into the country.
- Hand collection and squashing under foot.
- Use of clean planting materials, such as seed, cuttings, buds and root stocks that are free from pests.

Chemical method

- It involves use of poisons that are harmful to a particular pest. They can be applied by dusting, spraying or fumigation of a crop.

The mode of action of the main groups of pesticides

Stomach poisons

- They kill when eaten by the target organism.

Contact poisons

- They are absorbed through the skin or cuticle of the pest.
- Pests are killed when they are sprayed directly or get in contact with the sprayed foliage.

Systemic pesticides

- These are absorbed into the plant and travel in sap or juice to other parts.

- They kill sucking pests when ingested, e.g. Dimethoate 40% E.C.

Fumigants

- They act in gaseous form and interfere with respiration.
- They destroy the pest by suffocation, e.g. Ethyl bromide.

Biological method

It involves the use of beneficial organisms, such as insects or vectors that feed on pest. For example,

- Use of predators, e.g. Ladybird beetle.
- Introduction of fungi or virus that feed on pest.

Integrated Pest Management methods (IPM)

- It involves use of a combination of all control methods
- It emphasizes on use of natural and low toxic methods, but minimises the use of chemicals.

Benefits of integrated pest management

- Reduces the environmental risks associated with pest management by encouraging the adoption of more environmentally benign control tactics.
- Reduces the potential for air and ground water contamination.
- Protects the non-target species through reduced impact of pest management activities.
- Promotes sustainable bio based pest management alternatives.
- Promotes sound structures and healthy plants.
- Reduces the need for pesticides by using several pest management methods.
- Reduces or eliminates issues related to pesticide residue.
- Reduces or eliminates re-entry interval restrictions.
- Decrease workers and public exposure to pesticides.
- Maintains or increases the cost effectiveness of pest management programmes.
- Alleviates concern of the public about pest and pesticide related practices.

Disease management

- Explain importance of disease management.
- Outline the different methods of disease management.
- Compare different methods of disease management.

Importance of disease management

- Reduces or excludes the initial inoculum.
- Reduces crop losses. And hence yield increases
- Improves quality of produce.

Methods of disease management

Cultural

- Refers to those growing methods that reduce pathogen levels or reduce the rate of diseases development. These include:
 - ❖ Crop rotation. It helps keep populations of pathogens from building up to damaging numbers.
 - ❖ Sanitation. This involves ploughing under, removing and properly disposing of infected leaves, washing hands and burning of crop residues.
 - ❖ Host eradication: It refers to the removal of undesirable plants that might serve as a host reservoir for diseases that attack cultivated crops.
 - ❖ Use of optimum plant populations.
 - ❖ Applying adequate fertilisers and use of vigorous growing crops.
 - ❖ Practicing intercropping and early planting.

Chemical

- Pesticide application method works by eliminating disease-causing organisms.

Biological

- Crop rotation may be an effective means to prevent a parasitic population from becoming well-established, as an organism affecting leaves would be starved when the leafy crop is replaced by a tuberous type.

Legislative

Avoid the introduction of harmful non-native organisms by controlling all human traffic and activity.

Integrated Disease Management (IPM)

This involves use of two or more of these methods in combination offers a higher chance of effectiveness.

Disadvantages of biological methods of disease management.

- ❖ Need careful study before implementation.
- ❖ It is slow to work/ineffective.
- ❖ Predator may fail to establish.
- ❖ Predator may be difficult to get.
- ❖ Lack of knowledge.

Sprayer calibration

- Calibrate a knapsack sprayer

Definition of terms:

- **Swath width:** - the width of the deposited spray cloud.
- **Application rate:** - the volume of the spray liquid distributed over a unit area (l/ha).
- **Dosage rate:** - the mass or volume of product of given percentage of active ingredient content to be distributed over a unit area (kg/ha).

Sprayer components

Tank: Carries and stores the chemical.

Agitator: Flat plate for mixing the chemical mechanically.

Strainers: Trap dirt which can clog the system.

Pump: Imparts correct pressure to the liquid carrier, and delivers the liquid, through the nozzle, at the required rate. Examples are centrifugal, roller, diaphragm, gear and piston pumps.

Pump handle/lever: Moves piston or plunger up and down, and pressure builds up.

Nozzles: Restricting device that breaks the sprayed liquid into fine droplets. This is called atomisation. Nozzles are of various types:

- Even flat fan nozzle.
- Hollow cone or disc and cone nozzle.
- Flooding flat fan nozzle.
- Solid cone nozzle.
- Offset nozzle.

The nozzle flow rate is calculated as given below:

$$Q_n = \frac{A * S * W}{60\ 000}$$

Where:

Q_n = nozzle flow rate, l/min.

A = application rate, l/ha.

S = travel speed, km/hr.

W = nozzle spacing, cm.

Sprayer calibration

Calibration is simply adjusting the sprayer to apply the proper volume of chemical on a given area. Factors affecting calibration are:

1. Nozzle flow rate,
2. Ground speed of the sprayer, and
3. Width sprayed per nozzle.

The amount of material flowing through a nozzle varies with, the orifice size, the viscosity of the fluid, and the pressure of the fluid. Flow rate is proportional to the square root of the pressure. Increase in ground speed decreases the application rate.

How to Calibrate a Knapsack Sprayer

- ❖ Determine flow rate or nozzle discharge rate.
- ❖ Carryout a trial run to determine ground speed.
- ❖ Maintain pump pressure.
- ❖ Take note of swath covered.
- ❖ Use water for calibration.
- ❖ Use a timer.

Example:

- Record time taken to spray 100m using water.
- Record amount of water sprayed into jug in 1 minute.

- Measure spray width with nozzle held at comfortable height.

Routine maintenance of sprayers

- Rinse nozzle with clean water.
- Drain and wash the tank twice with clean water and detergent, when changing from one chemical to another.
- Lubricate moving parts. This should be carried out with care as over-greasing may contaminate the spray liquid and block the filters.
- Concentrated chemicals should not be put into an empty tank, but the tank must be half-filled with water first, and then the chemical added to it.
- Remove and store nozzles separately, when not in use.

TOPIC 5: CROP PRODUCTION

.....

SUBTOPIC: CEREAL AND LEGUME CROP PRODUCTION

Crop management

- Describe harvesting indices and methods of a named cereal and legume crops.
- Describe post-harvest technology of a named legume and cereal crops.
- Discuss the marketing a named legume and cereal crops.
- Discuss the significance of record- keeping in the production of a named cereal and legume crop.
- Keep records of a named cereal and legume crop.

Cereal crop: Maize (Zea mays L.)

Harvesting indices (signs of maturity)

- Black layer at the top of mature kernel ,
- Grain moisture at onset of maturity occurs within the range of 25-350C,
- Number of days to reach maturity of the variety being grown ,
- Drying of maize cobs ,
- Kernels become hard to bite and glossing in color,
- Husks and leaves become brown and papery.

Harvesting methods

- Harvesting is the operations of gathering the useful part or parts of the plant.
- It is a voluntary intervention by man, carried out at the time when all the nutrients have been developed and the edible parts have reached maturity.
- Maize crops are first cut either as whole or partially (cobs) and then threshold and cleaned to separate the grain from the cobs and straw.
- Two methods can be used :

❖ Hand harvesting

- Cut the maize stalks with machetes or hoes and stack in the field for the cobs to dry.
- Pluck maize cobs from the stalks and remove them from the husks.
- Put cobs in bags or stationary cart to contain the cobs for later storage.
- Transport for storage.
- Harvested by hand and cobs are stored in traditional structures (granaries).
- This method does require specific tools, it simply involves removing cobs from stalks.

❖ **Machine harvesting**

- The mechanical harvester detaches the cob of the Maize from the stalks.
- Combine harvesters carry out several tasks in one operation.
- They remove cobs from stalks, dehusk, shell and pour grain in trailers or bags.
- A combine harvester is used.
- The combine harvester performs the gathering, snapping and removal of the trash.
- The rotating reel pushes or gathers the uncut stalks against the cutter-bar.
- Snapping is the breaking of the maize ears from the stalks.
- The crop is conveyed and fed into the machine.
- The material is moved into the cylinder and concave for threshing. Thus the grain is removed from the ears.
- Straw walkers separate the grain. Unshelled grain fall through the straw walker opening and returned for re-threshing.
- The cleaning shoe (chaffer sieve and blowing fan) separate the kernels from impurities.

Threshing methods

- Traditionally maize shelling is done as manual operation , maize kernels are separated from the cobs by pressing on the grain with the thumbs.
- Maize shellers, are hand operated machines.
- Threshing maize cobs which have been placed into bags and the beaten using sticks.
- Motonised threshing –small maize shellers, equipped with a rotating cylinder of the peg or bar type are available on the market.

Harvesting stages for maize

Maize storage

- Maize for marketing should be stored shelled in a closed stored with the use of pesticides.
- The spread of the grain borer in the region makes the use of good storage essential.
- Delayed harvesting of maize lead to higher losses because of attacks by termites , rodents and domestic animals.
- Crops can be infected by pests.
- Storage facilities should serve the following purposes
 - × provide protection –ground & water rain
 - insect pests
 - excessive heat.

Maize storage facilities

- Drying storage cribs – used normally when storing maize on the cobs, and can also be used to store shelled grain in bags.
- Mud or cement – plastered buckets.
- Brick bins -
- Ferro cement bins –

Preparing Maize for marketing

- GMB buys the maize soon after harvesting.
- The farmer can find milling buyers at a Marketing Board or Co-operative Depot.
- Maize is marketed through the GMB at a price gazette by the government.
- Also due to trade liberalization, maize processing companies like millers and breweries provide an alternative for maize growths.
- Farmers can market their grain through the open market like Mbare Musika at concessionary prices.

Harvesting losses

- **Pre-harvest losses:** Occurs before the crop is harvested due to over drying, weather, pests, and diseases.

- **Header losses:** Losses are caused by the reel operation, e.g. lodging.
- **Threshing losses:** Losses result from incomplete removal the seed from the seed head (under-threshing).
- **Separating losses:** These are losses of threshed grain over straw walker.
- **Cleaning shoe losses:** These are the losses of grain passing over the shoe.

Expected yield • Depends on cultivar and rainfall distribution. It ranges from 0-12t/ha.

Post-harvest technology:

Drying maize

- Drying is the systematic reduction of crop moisture down to safe levels for storage, usually 12%-15.5% moisture content.
- May be left to dry in the field for 4-7 weeks, either in stacks or heaps.
- Late harvesting can shorten drying duration.
- Wet grains and attract insects and mold.
- Drying the maize on the ground will make it absorb moisture and pick up dirt and insects.
- Shelled maize can be dried in layers on bare ground, mats or plastic sheets.
- Cob may be suspended from poles on free branches.
- Artificial driers and ventilated structures such as cribs, are modern methods.
- Proper drying results in increased storage life of the grains, prevention of deterioration in quality, reduction of biological respiration that leads to quality loss of grains, and optimum milling recovery.

Shelling and winnowing

- Shelling is the process of separating the seeds or grains from the cobs.
- To maintain the high quality of the harvested grains, it should be shelled immediately after harvesting.
- Maize shelling is difficult at moisture levels above 25%. This may lead to mechanical damage to the grain.
- Shelling is commonly done by beating maize cobs with stick in a sack or a confined floor space or by use of powered sheller. Beating maize will result in physical damage which makes it more vulnerable to pests and moulds
- Cleaners or winnowers separate kernels from impurities.

Milling

- Milling is the process wherein the maize grain is transformed into a form suitable for human consumption.

Dehulling

- Dehulling is the process of removing the pericarp or seed coat from the kernels. The methods include:
 - Hand pounding and
 - Use of mechanised dehullers.

Storage

- Store in bags, silos or granaries.
- Rooms must be moisture proof, dry and cool, tidy and clean.
- Store at 12-13% moisture content.
- Apply insecticides such as Malathion 1% dust. • Protect from vermin by putting rat baffles on granary pillars.

Losses due to poor storage

Mould

- Microbial infection in storage occurs due to inadequate drying of produce.
- Fungal infection results into rots and development of aflatoxins, which are poisonous compounds to live stock and cause cancer in human.
- Losses due to mould
 - ⊗ Loss of weight
 - ⊗ Loss of quality (smell, taste, colour, nutritional value, germination)

Spillage

- Careless handling of either maize cobs or grains can lead to spillage.
- This leads to loss in terms of quantity.
- Spillage can also lead to loss of quality in case contaminated grains or cobs are again mixed with the clean stuff.

Preparation for market

- Shelling to remove the kernels or grain or pips.
- Winnowing to remove chaff, weed seeds and small grains.
- Grading according to quality or size. The term “quality” as applied to food material refers to those attributes of the food which make it agreeable to those who consume it. Attributes of quality involve colour, flavour, texture, nutritional value and the absence of harmful substances.
- Weighing and packing in 50kg bags.
- Marketing through Grain Marketing Board or other merchants.

Outline the factors that a farmer of maize has to assess to determine the likelihood of making profits [20]

- demand
- if the product is inelastic
- check the present of substitute
- look at the habit farming factors
- income determination

- population
- real income per head
- free movement of global trade
- cost of production
- climate
- transport cost

Outline the problems that farmer face in marketing their products

- perishable nature of products
- season nature /gluts
- formal market channels too cumbersome
- distance from the market
- transport availability and costs
- poor road networks
- packaging material available and costs
- price controls & tax
- government policy
- storage facilities
- lack of information

List any 4 methods used to prevent and control insect pest infestation of stored grain,

- use of sealable containers
- clean seed
- storage hygiene
- pesticide treatment
- drying
- correctly designed (building) storeroom or silos
- cultural methods

Legume crop: Soya bean (Glycine max)

Harvesting methods

- Soybean matures within 3–4 months after planting; • At maturity, the pod is straw- coloured.
- Harvest when 80% and 85% of the pods have turned brown for shattering and nonshattering varieties, respectively.
- Crop can be harvested when the seeds are at the hard-dough stage, when the seed moisture content is between 12 and 16%.
- Harvesting can be carried out by hand or mechanical means, using a combine harvester.
- Stack them loosely on tarpaulin and allow them to dry in the open for 2 weeks before threshing.

Causes of losses in soya bean harvesting

Hand method:

- Incorrect stage of harvesting.

- Immature kernels are lost.
- Some kernels rot or even germinate.
- Long-time of harvesting.
- Shattering losses high due to inappropriate method.
- Hoes cause high losses.
- Temporary storage in the field lead to high termite damage.

Machine method:

- Incorrect adjustment of machine.
- Levelness of ground.
- Pod clearance and speed of harvesting.
- Blunt knife sections and cutter bar height.
- Shattering losses and lodging.
- Time of harvesting.
- Soil moisture.

How to minimise combine harvester losses

- Ensure level field.
- Operate cutter bar close to ground level.
- Operate slowly, about 5km/hr.
- Adjust knife sections and guard-wear plates accordingly.
- Use reel speed of about 25% faster than ground speed.
- Reel axle should be 150-300mm ahead of cutter bar.
- Observe the correct time of operation.

Expected yield: -3300kg/ha of seed yield can be expected.

Post-harvest technology

Threshing

- Threshing manually or mechanically may be done when the plants are properly dry.
- Manual threshing involves piling soybean plants on tarpaulin or putting dry soybean pods in sacks and beating them with a stick.
- Winnow to remove chaff, dust and other rubbish. Mechanical threshers are equipped with blowers that separate the grains from the chaff.

Storage

- Store at a moisture content of 10% or less.
- Dry in open-air, to 13% moisture for storage of 6–12 months and to 10–11% for longer storage.
- Open-air drying is the most practical way to protect soybean in storage.
- Stack the 50-kg or 100-kg grain bags on a raised platform or wooden pallet away from the wall.
- High moisture content in stored soybean encourages the development of insects and microorganisms.

- Exposure to high temperatures, will increase deterioration and reduce seed viability.
- Control storage pests, for example, by coating grain with Actellic Super.

Marketing

- Marketed at 11% moisture content.
- Pack in 50kg bags and market through GMB who grade the seed according to quality.

Causes of losses in soya-bean postharvest handling

- Poor storage structures.
- Poor storage practices (drying, insect control).
- Resistance to grain protectants by some pests such as Larger Grain Borer (LGB).
- High moisture content at storage.
- Poor shelling practices and poor drying structure.

Factors that lead to downgrading of kernels:

- Damaged kernels and broken shells.
- Diseased or moulded kernels.
- Dirty or shrivelled kernels, including foreign objects.
- Discoloured kernels and pest damage.
- High moisture content.
- Mixed varieties.

With reference to soya beans or groundnuts

[a] describe the climatic requirements for the crop {10}

- sub-tropical crops
- warm condition
- with an optimum growing temperature of 22 to 28C
- Lower temp- cause low growth rate and delay maturity, can cause slow germination as well as reduced pollen viability and fertility
- High temp-cause formation of hallow pods, result in low grain density, reducing the yield obtained
- flowers initiation induced by short day length
- yield reduced by water stress during the reproductive stage & also in grain filling stage. As water is necessary in the transport of photosynthetic products to the sinks in resource partitioning
- rainfall of 450 to 850mm is required for successfully growing the crop. This can be applied through irrigation.
- successful growth of the crop requires frost free environment

[b] Describe how fertilizer is managed during crop growth [5]

- all P & K requirements applied at planting as basal

- Part of N is applied as a starter through base dressing. It is usually applied as part of P 7 K in compound fertilizers eg compound D
- nitrogen topdressing may be required in soils with low fertility
- the amount of fertilizer depend on results of soil sample analysis
- gypsum applied at flowering
- all methods for application can be used as top dressing
- the farmer should consider timing with respect to growth stage

[c] Describe the importance of liming soils

- increase soil pH
- improve availability of nutrients
- flocculate the soil
- improve soil structure
- Supply calcium
- enhance activity of micro organisms
- improve soil workability

describe the characteristics of soyabeans or groundnuts cultivars recommended for marginal rainfall areas

groundnuts

- Upright growth habit
- short life cycle, to suit short season length, bunch type
- named groundnut varieties

soya beans

- short life cycle to suit short season length, root to shoot ratio
- Less leaf material
- determinate growth habit
- resistance to pod shattering
- named examples

describe soya beans production under the following headings

[a] soil and climatic requirements

- hot wet summer are best
- Annual rainfall 600-1000mm well distributed in the season

Discuss the importance aspect of legume that can be used to convince a farmer growing cereals to switch enterprise

- legumes have long taproot roots which can utilize nutrients and water within the profile
- long taproot roots can access water when shortages arise
- legumes also contain root nodules (a site where ribosome are obtained)
- legumes have a short life cycle, this gives the farmer enough time to prepare for the next crop to be grown
- legumes have leaf residues on the surfaces this facilitates in increasing organic matter content

- legumes have different botanical class with maize and wheat this reduce the rate of pest and diseases
- legumes like beans provides cheap source of proteins
- legumes have high product flexibility
- farmers can sale their products while still fresh or can sale them while dry e.g. olive oil

Discuss yields of soya beans or ground nuts of low in small holder farming areas. (10)

- yields of soya beans are low in small holder farming areas due to lack in practice in soil analysis. Small holders do not have enough money to hire skilled labour to take samples or they have money to pay the research boards.
- yields in small holder famers are low in soya beans because they practice mixed cultivation. They do not rely or focus on one product, time and money to buy herbicides is diverted to other enterprise. This reduces expected yields.
- small holder farmers lack skilled labour. They are not aware of recommended ploughing depths for soya beans 25-50mm. small/deep depths hinder dropper growth of soya beans.
- small holder farmers are not aware of row spacing required in the growth of soya beans 50-90mm.

Discuss how the following can be controlled in groundnuts or soya beans

i. Cutworms

- are dull brown caterpillars that hide under litter or soil during the day and come out in the dark to feed on young plants.
- Destroy crop residues, keep field weed free in winter. Hand picking on pests at night.
- chemical control use carbon malathan 25% w.p as baits

ii. semi-lopper caterpillar

- Bite the edges of the leaves and produce holes on the leaves

Explain why smallholder farmers are encouraged to grow soyabean or ground nuts. [10]

Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of using herbicides in the production of soya beans or ground nuts , [10]

Records- keeping

- Cultivar grown,
- Planting date.
- Spacing used.
- Harvesting date and yield.
- Type of fertiliser used.
- Number of bags of fertiliser used.

Importance of record keeping

- Keeping track of money owed to the business.
- Help farmers to detect mistakes.
- Help farmers to assess whether making profit or loss.
- Help to improve farm income.
- A basis of obtaining loans.
- Help in timing of farm operations.
- Help in controlling and preventing risks.
- Assist farmers in making decisions.
- To help avoid unnecessary expenditure.
- Used in budgeting for future enterprises.
- Help farmer to remember his debts.
- Show history of agricultural production.

Types of records

- The main types of records are:
 - ❖ Physical or production records, and
 - ❖ Financial records.

a) Physical records

- These contain information on farm productivity. Examples are farm diary and farm inventory.
- Production record for a cereal crop
 - ❖ Cultivar grown,
 - ❖ Planting date.
 - ❖ Spacing used.
 - ❖ Harvesting date.
 - ❖ Type of fertilizer used.
 - ❖ Number of bags of fertiliser used. • Yield obtained.

b) Financial records

These reflect the expenditure and income of a business.

Types of financial records

1. **An income statement:** It shows a projection of sales and receipts, against purchases and expenses, to determine profit or loss.
2. **A cash flow statement:** to measure flow of funds.
3. **A balance sheet:** It is a statement of all assets and liabilities of a business at a specific, to determine net worth or net capital of a farm.

Net worth is the difference between assets and liabilities of a business.

When assets exceed or equal (\geq) liabilities, the firm is solvent. It means the business can pay its debts.

When liabilities exceed assets, then the business is insolvent or bankrupt. It means the business is unable to pay its debts.